

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
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**COMMUNICATIVE (RE)PRODUCTION OF TEACHER AUTHORITY IN A
GENERATIVE AI-INFUSED AND GAMIFIED MULTICULTURAL CLASSROOM: AN
EXCHANGE ESL TEACHER'S AUTOETHNOGRAPHY**

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Acceptance Page

This paper prepared by **GINO P. PARADELA** with the title: **COMMUNICATIVE (RE)PRODUCTION OF TEACHER AUTHORITY IN A GENERATIVE AI-INFUSED AND GAMIFIED MULTICULTURAL CLASSROOM: AN EXCHANGE ESL TEACHER'S AUTOETHNOGRAPHY** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree, Doctor of Communication.

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Biographical Sketch

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Dedicated to
The Mystical Home of Nazareth: Jesus, Mary, and Joseph,

to
St. Jude Thaddeus, my patron saint,

and to my wife

H.P.

and daughter

S-M.

FOR THE GREATER GLORY OF GOD

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ABSTRACT

Throughout the teaching-learning process, I have noticed how the act of communication shapes the ongoing practice of meaning-making among members in the classroom, especially within my regards to my identity as the classroom's figure of authority. The classroom possesses a social order, created at the micro level through communication, headed by the authority of the teacher with the students as learners. With the encroachment of generative AI-infused technologies (GAI) however, this concept of teacher identity as authority within classroom social order has to be (re)created, maintained, repaired, and transformed (Craig, 1999) to accommodate new developments in space and time.

This study sought to explore how generative AI-infused educational technologies and gamification (re)produces the identity of the teacher as the authority in the multicultural classroom. It sought to answer the questions: *(1) How has generative AI in a multicultural classroom threatened teachers' authority?*; and *(2) How does GAI and gamification integration in communicative practices (re)produce teacher authority in a multicultural classroom?* This study made use of a qualitative research design, specifically autoethnography. Drawing from my lived experiences as a Filipino cultural exchange ESL teacher, I analyzed naturally-occurring data as situated descriptions of how my authority and identity are constructed through communication. Data was thematically organized using codes, sub-themes, and overarching themes related to GAI and gamification.

This study found that teacher authority has been threatened by GAI in four ways:

(1) threatening self-image as a content expert; (2) tendency to outsource thinking with GAI; (3) challenging traditional teacher roles; and (4) weakening teacher authority. The study then found that teacher authority is (re)produced through five themes processes: (1) Creating fun and engaging lessons through data-driven decision making; (2) monitoring progress and motivating learners through pleasurable learning; (3) using gamification to improve student performance; (4) partnering with parents and tailoring lessons to fit learners' needs; and (5) assessing learner's progress and awarding performance. The idea that authority is enacted not merely through formal institutional structures but through active engagement with GAI and gamified strategies shape and legitimize the teacher's central role emerged in the analysis, as well GAI's role as a tool for reflexivity which (re)constructs the professional identity and pedagogical interventions of the teacher.

Keywords: Generative AI, Gamification, Authority, Sociocultural, Exchange Teacher, Education, Autoethnography

CHAPTER I

RATIONALE

Teacher and Technology in a Multicultural Classroom

I have been teaching for more than a decade and as I grew as an educator, I have noticed more rapid technological advancements in the classroom especially during COVID-19 pandemic lockdowns, when classrooms have had to transform from brick-and-mortar infrastructures to a hybrid of physical and digital. Commensurate with the rise of technology, I have also noticed that student needs and engagement in the classroom are also changing. Following the urge for professional growth, I took the chance of teaching in the United States of America under the Cultural Exchange Program in 2023 as an English (ELA) and English as a Second Language (ESL) teacher. I had already been teaching in the Philippines for eleven (11) years when I made the decision to try professional growth abroad.

It was at this county that I encountered the multicultural classroom - an interactional meeting point where various students with different lived experiences, from different cultural and linguistic realities, intentionally situated together for English instruction (Malik et al, 2024). It was at this intention space that I experienced tensions in navigating my role and have started to question my authority in the teaching-learning process. Not only am I an international teacher with my own cultural framework and educational background, I am also a teacher forced to navigate the encroachment of AI into my classroom.

With the proliferation of Generative AI-infused (GAI) Educational technologies in the ESL classroom where both students and I have encountered it and how the educational system reacts to its adoption - I experienced a series of tensions on how I exercise and define my authority in the classroom, where my identity as the classroom authority and leader is challenged by generative AI-infused technologies as well as the need to be responsive to the varied needs to engage multicultural learners in the classroom .

Being in a multicultural classroom and having students from various lived realities each with their own interest and feeling about the classroom structure I experienced tensions on how to establish rapport and classroom engagement to bolster learning outcomes. Walking in the middle of this tension and through the communicative act and in addition to encountering generative AI-infused technology, I thus also encountered gamification as a technique to bolster classroom experiences.

Generative AI-infused and gamified multicultural classroom

It could not be denied that the landscape of education has been that of constant evolution. The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools has become a hot-button issue, one where various educational experts and practitioners have had to contend with. The coming of AI in education is more than mere technological advancement. It is reshaping the experience of how teaching and learning is done in its very center (Walter, 2024). With roles and processes that extend beyond traditional modalities of content delivery, AI offers personalized learning experiences and enhances essential skills like computational and critical thinking, intimately connected with machine learning and educational robotics (Walter, 2024) .

AI's arrival in the classroom however, has also brought about a crisis in how teachers make sense of the technology. Some teachers have started to report feeling marginalized due to a perceived lack of technical skills, perceiving that AI systems will soon weaken their role or worse replace them (Shao & Sun, 2025). The automation of tasks and trend of replacing employees in other fields have shaken the professional identity of teachers (ibid). Shao and Sun (2025) notes three threats to teacher's identity: the weakening of their role and authority, the threat of professional status, and the pressure of professional skills. With personalized learning paths that AI technology can mediate and process, teachers are starting to re-examine their role in this new environment. Teachers have also been worried about their careers, fearing being replaced by intelligent machines; not to mention their challenges of adapting to new skills. They highlight the importance of role positioning, building professional self-confidence, and reinforcing professional identity.

Generative AI (GAI) is an artificial intelligence technology that can create content by responding to prompts written in natural-language interface by statistically analyzing words, pixels, and other elements through identifying and repeating common patterns in a variety of texts (Miao & Holmes, 2023). The use of generative AI technology such as ChatGPT has been seen as having the potential to contribute towards creating a more personalized, inclusive, and effective learning experience; its use in the classroom prepares students not only for current academic challenges but also for the changing demands of the future (Walter, 2024). Likewise, gamification is a pedagogical technique that includes game design elements and mechanics in non-gaming contexts, aiming to adopt motivation, engagement, and desired behaviours in the classroom by capitalizing

on the appeal of games to enrich, immerse, and facilitate a practical learning experience (Deterding, et al., 2011; Kapp, 2012).

Throughout the teaching-learning process, I have noticed how the act of communication shapes the ongoing practice of meaning-making among members in the classroom, especially within my regards to my identity as the classroom's figure of authority. Teacher authority refers to the legitimized combination of institutional traditions, professional regulations, and personal expertise and charisma that validates specific knowledge and reinforces power structure in the classroom (Lu & Hu, 2021). It is dynamic and relational - forged by the interaction between teachers and their instructional practice and the responses of the students that reflects a shared moral order whereby teachers and students uphold for the purposes of education (ibid).

My identity as a teacher as the figure of authority is seen in my leading role in facilitating the process of assigning, negotiating, and participating in outcomes in the classroom. The classroom possesses a social order, created at the micro level through communication, headed by the authority of the teacher with the students as learners. With the encroachment of generative AI-infused technologies however, this concept of teacher identity as authority within classroom social order has to be (re)created, maintained, repaired, and transformed (Craig, 1999) to accommodate new developments in space and time.

The idea of "communicative construction" is referenced in this study, derived from Dionson's (2020) dissertation *A Communicative Construction of Teacher Identity: A Phenomenological Study of Being a Non-native English-Speaking teacher in the United States* whereby he defines communicative construction in relation to teacher identity as

constructed by “narrative encounters... [where] teachers not only reflect on their classroom practice but also develop discourses that anchor their professional identities” (96). Dionson focused on how he situated himself as a Non-native English-speaking teacher in the English Language Teaching Industry. This study will build on his foundations and seek to recontextualize the idea of narrative encounters. While Dionson’s work is introspective in the sense that teachers construct their identities through narrative encounters in a foreign classroom, my work seeks to build on this by exploring how a foreign teacher (re)creates, maintains, repairs, and transforms their *identity and authority* in a multicultural classroom where generative AI-infused technologies have become an all too common reality.

As a method, this study makes use of autoethnography. Autoethnography is a research approach that systematically analyzes (*graphy*) one’s personal experience (*auto*) in order to understand one’s cultural experience (*ethno*) and treats the research objectives as a political, socially just and conscious act (Ellis, 2004; Holman Jones, 2005, Adams & Holman Jones, 2008 cited by Ellis, et al., 2010).

This present study hopes to benefit various groups by providing insights into the lived reality of a practitioner in the process of “meaning-making”. Firstly, Cultural Exchange Teachers can benefit from this study by providing insight and further context regarding their present experiences, and how teacher identities can be calibrated to fit the need of a technologically advancing world where Generative AI is increasingly encroaching in the classroom. This study can provide teachers with a kind of solidarity as it presents common experiences and challenges that fellow teachers are currently facing. Next, Exchange Program Sponsors can use the findings herein to improve their

systems, knowledge of educational technologies, and practices to fit the cultural context of exchange teachers. It can also provide them, more importantly, with insights on how to equip teachers in the multicultural and technologically updating classroom. Then, Policy Makers and Educational Authorities can make use of the insights found in this study by providing them with on-the-ground experiences and challenges of cultural exchange teachers especially in the United States. This will be able to reinforce their policies related to teacher exchange programs, as well as provide a benchmark for the creation of more engaging and customized professional development programs. Finally, future Exchange Teachers can benefit from this study by providing on-the-ground insights on what to expect and how to navigate their experiences realistically and effectively and will be able to help them collaborate with local and fellow exchange teachers to enhance teaching-learning outcomes.

It is in these lines that this study is undertaken.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter presents and reviews pertinent literature related to this study.

Teacher Professional Identity

Teacher professional identity is a role identity composed of the teacher's perception of the different aspects of their role in the teaching profession (Lai & Jin, 2021). Teachers look at their profession through a lens by which they give meaning to who and what they are as teachers and act in it (Brenner, et. al. , 2018; Kelchtermans, 2009 cited by Lai & Jin, 2021). Thus, teacher identity can be seen as an communicative act of construction - an on-going process of "interpretation and reinterpretation" of experiences , requiring people and contexts, involving various sub-identities, and agency (Beijaard, et al., 2004). Likewise, Reeves (2018) echoes that the construction of teacher identity requires a significant effort to construct and re-evaluate their identities. The process requires negotiation and movement within a complex social, political, and ethical context characterized by diverse perspectives (Ulla, et al. 2024).

The practice of teachers in the classroom is beset with many challenges, adjustments, and new experiences which require them to negotiate the development of their professional identities that requires the interplay of individual decisions, attitudes, motivations, and external factors (Avidov-Ungar & Forkosh-Baruch 2018 cited by Ulla, et al, 2024)

The study of Hiver & Whitehead (2018) establishes a link between teacher identity, practices, and ongoing learning which requires them to constantly negotiate

and form and re-form their teacher identity. Likewise, they argue that teacher identity is blended together with other social identities such as race, gender, and ethnicity that affect how they attach, mediate, and mind meaning (ibid.)

Hiver & Whitehead's (2018) show how teachers, through their classroom practice, co-construct a sense of agency and professional identity. This is of breadth with Widodo, et al. (2020) who discussed professional identity as further defined by the teacher's agency and capacity to behave and act professionally towards students, colleagues, and curriculum artifacts such as technologies and textbooks; this identity is historically, culturally, and socially constructed.

Yazan (2018) defines teacher identity as "a dynamic self-conception whereby teachers imagine themselves as "teachers", which is always in the process of change as they interact with various communities, individuals, and position themselves (and by others) in various social contexts. Teachers, therefore, constantly engage in the process of participation in various communities within their institutions and it is there that they encounter beliefs, histories, and concepts that challenge their beliefs and practices which prompts them to re-evaluate and re-negotiate their identities and practices (Tokoz Goktepe & Kunt 2021). It is in the process of interaction, feedback, and support from colleagues, administrators, students, and parents that the perception of effectiveness as a teacher stems from constructing the concept of one's teacher identity (Ulla et al., 2024).

One study to illustrate the idea that identity is communicatively constructed has been done by Tokoz Goktepe & Kunt (2021). Their study follows a new English as

Foreign Language teacher in Turkey and how she constructed her identity over time. Rooting themselves on socio-cultural methods, they noted that certain teacher-induction programs have had a negative effect on how they form their identity, particularly by not being allowed to experiment and apply their pedagogical perspectives in the classroom. As she was not “seen” as at-par with her mentor-teachers, she notes how she has had to constantly re-negotiate her place in the system and from this built her a construct of who she is as a teacher in that she “... sees herself as a guess, under the power of a mentor...” making her “... uncomfortable ... for her to develop [her] desired language-teacher identity (483).

The study of Macapagong et al. (2023) documents the experiences of Filipino Cultural exchange teachers in the United States. Their study sought to look into the personal experiences of Filipino teachers whilst living and teaching in the United States. They also wanted to know how teachers cope with the challenges of living and teaching in the United States and what strategies they have found to best improve their careers, as well as what the challenges they faced as teachers. Their study on the experiences of cultural exchange teachers hints how navigating into a new system has posed a great challenge to their identities as teachers. Being in a new environment and a new culture, preconceived meanings have to be constantly negotiated. An experience was chronicled by Macapagnong et al for example, that one teacher has had to navigate classroom management because they were not accustomed “.... to learners being rude and talking back” and that they “missed the respect” they were afforded by Filipino learners. Though after this period of culture shock, the teachers in the study revealed how they have had to cope through opening up and modeling their practice after what

worked best for local teachers which provides them “... with a lot of opportunity to learn and grow.”

They provided insights on how cultural practices and values of the United States may at times be at odds with Filipino values. Participants in the study noted how despite mental preparations, they still had to experience and contend with culture shock. Filipino teachers also reported that they found the use of new technological resources intimidating, especially for those who are used to traditional instructional materials. Teachers note that they were impressed with the teaching load with that of their workload in the Philippines, saying that it is “lighter”. Whereas the biggest challenge was classroom management. Teachers have to contend with “rude” students who talk back which is categorized as being “rude” and “disrespectful” according to Filipino values. This raises an interesting point on how the meaning of certain concepts are ascribed differently based on the culture from where it is expressed. In this case, “teacher workload” has a completely different meaning in their interactions within the United States. And that “rude” and “disrespectful” within the Filipino framework is radically different from what the American classroom defines it to be. The struggle highlights how exchange teachers are constantly in the process of negotiation and reflection to make sense out of these experiences. Teachers reported admiration about how local teachers interacted with them and how open they are to help them. Teachers for example learned how important the creation of rewards systems are for students. The study highlights the importance of peer interactions which enables them to engage in the process of minding, or thinking through their experiences. Open and supportive local teachers likewise afford them to model and negotiate their practices.

Additional studies also have provided more context about the experiences of international teachers teaching in the United States. Lee's (2015) study reports that foreign teachers report difficulties in classroom discipline due to cultural differences and have experienced a different level of students' respect towards them. Lee's study also highlights the difficulties teachers have with parents due to the teachers' lack of understanding with the cultural milieu of the United States. This "gap" stems from a different set of assigned meanings since exchange teachers, coming from different parts of the world, have their own ascribed meanings as to how students must behave and treat adults. Likewise, communication and cultural gaps exist between parents and teachers (44). As with the case observed by Macapagong et al's study where cultural meanings are shaped by interaction, exchange teachers have to go through the communicative process of approaching, negotiating, and minding to reproduce social order within the new classroom context they are currently situated in. They constantly form and re-form their identity and practices.

The integration of Generative AI in the Classroom

Shao and Sun (2025) cites a case study where a primary school started to integrate AI tools for personalized teaching and have yielded better learning outcomes . Teachers were praised and given positive feedback and reported that teachers had an enhanced sense of professional identity. This mirrors a study by Kim and Kwon (2025). Their study takes place in a rural middle school and its implementation of an AI curriculum; it is a single-case study that looks into how a teacher's identity is shaped by institutional adoption of AI. At first, they noticed that the teacher exhibited passive engagement and noted that they have low confidence and unfamiliarity with AI content

and operations. However, when researcher-supported strategies were implemented such as modeling, collaborative reflection, and scaffolded implementation in relation to AI use, the teacher started to view their role as an active facilitator of learning. The process of collaboration enabled them to enrich their sense of participation and began to show improvement in their self-identification as a competent AI educator. This boosted their professional confidence. This study highlights identity transformation as a socially mediated, practice-centered process that requires sustained interaction, support, and contextual sensitivity. Their study highlights the importance of modeling, collaboration, and self-reflection as fundamental to confidence and growth. It advances the importance of localized support systems and peer collaboration for shaping teacher identity, especially in under-resourced areas.

The study of Kim &Kwon (2025) is a foundational study that is of interest in the discussion of teacher identity in relation to AI technology in the classroom. Grounding their study in the idea that teacher identity is dynamic and is influenced by both personal experiences and contextual factors such as the grade level of students, technological demands, and demographic (Rodgers & Scott, 2008; Beauchamp & Thomas, 2009 cited by Kim & Kwon, 2025).

The points raised by Kim and Kwon mirror that of Walter (2024)'s layout. Walter collected the current concerns of educational professionals with regards to AI integration in the classroom:

- Some teachers may feel overwhelmed because they do not know much about the technology and how it could be best used.

- Teachers and students sometimes are not aware of the limitations of the AI model and its potential negative outcomes.
- Students using AI technology uncritically, and merely using the machine to do their work rather than use it as reinforcement.
- Students increasingly become heavily reliant on AI and not seek to learn new materials because they do not want to exert effort.

Walter argues that developing skills on AI literacy, knowledge about prompt engineering, and critical thinking can best remedy the following problems he raised.

Gamification is the integration of video game components to promote a “gameful experience” in the classroom (Ratinho & Martins, 2023). Gameful experiences refers to a psychological state that stems from the interaction of an autonomous yet perceived feeling attainable (winnable) and non-trivial goals leading to high levels of engagement (Landers, 2014 cited in Ratinho & Martins, 2023). Kiryakova, Angelova, & Yordanova (2014) defines gamification as the integration of game elements and game thinking in activities that are not games. In the classroom, it is the act of using game metaphors, elements, ideas, and elements with the intention of increasing motivation and commitment to engage students.

Gamification has been implemented by various teachers due to lack of student engagement in the classroom in addition to the lack of motivation of students to participate actively in the teaching learning process (Kiryakova, Angelova, & Yordanova, 2014). Gamification is made favorable in settings where e-learning platforms are based on modern ICT because it enables the processing of student data and automate

analysis through the generation of reports. Huang and Soman (2013 cited in Kiryakova et al, 2014) stresses that gamification does not correlate with the development of knowledge and skills in itself, rather by positively affecting behavior and learning motivation, knowledge and skills are improved. Khoshnoodifar, Ashouri, and Taheri (2023)'s study found that gamification positively influenced student attitudes and learning outcomes especially when it comes to assessment. There is significant correlation between learning and students' perceived experience with feedback, concentration, and challenge of the gamified content.

Teachers have noted that gamification has been able to provide extrinsic motivation which, when activated, will hopefully change students' internal drive to study the content, gain a depth of understanding, and master the material (McCarthy, 2021). Sanchez, Langer, and Kaur (2019) examined how gamified quizzes influence student learning outcomes and found that gamification did initially benefit student learning. They noted, however, that using the same game elements to enhance learning permanently or for long-term assignments is not effective. Gamification in the long run, they found, is not sustainable for improving student learning in itself as game features may lose their influence after a short period. They advise that teachers approach the application of gamification with intention and use it as features for a contextualized group of learners. In any case, gamification is not a long-term fix.

Gamification is made easy and possible with software tools. Kiryakova et al (2014) highlights how Learning Management Systems (LMS) such as Moodle can allow integration of Web 2.0 tools LMS offers.

While some literature exists on how AI communicatively constructs the social

order in the classroom such as has been noted by Kim and Kwon (2023) and gamification (Sanchez et.al 2019), it is relatively few based on the current survey. The literature reveals the need to further discuss how teacher identity and teaching learning experiences are constructed through communication, especially with the blossoming of new technologies and teaching approaches in the ESL classroom.

The literature shows a gap demonstrably in how individual teachers communicative construct their authority and identities vis-a-vis the arrival of new educational technologies, particularly that of Generative AI-infused applications. Voices and experiences of how Filipino cultural exchange teachers deal with different educational realities and how they make attempts to interculturally communicate and solicit expected outcomes from students in various multicultural realities are likewise significantly lacking. Furthermore, Filipino exchange teachers' in the United States, how the classroom social order and identity is shaped by their communication and experiences in a foreign classroom, as well as encounters with new technologies and approaches in shaping their instructional design (i.e. with Generative AI and new approaches like gamification within the context of Exchange teachers) are still not heavily represented in the literature. With the influx of teachers to the United States, drawing from the insights of this research will be able to enrich the discourse of this current phenomenon .

While most of the surveyed literature examines teachers' in aggregate or macro-policy lenses, this study seeks to contribute and fill in the gaps by providing a microscopic, embodied, and reflexive voice to the experiences of teachers in the classroom as agents responding to change through communicative construction and

adaptation.

Likewise, my survey of the current literature seems to show that voices from non-Western teachers and their pedagogical responses to Generative AI and gamification are scant and muted. This study seeks to bridge this gap by adding a more nuanced voice into the discourse.

It is the hope of this present study to address these gaps and provide more insights about the research questions at hand.

CHAPTER III

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH QUESTION

This chapter discusses the theoretical framework that guides this study and presents the research question.

The Sociocultural Tradition

This research situates itself in the sociocultural tradition and theorizes communication as a *symbolic process that produces and reproduces shared cultural patterns* (Craig, 1999). Within this framework, communication explains how social order (the macro) is created, maintained, and transformed through micro level interactional processes (145).

This study conceptualizes the identity of the teacher as authority in the multicultural classroom as being communicatively constructed. Meaning, that identity and authority is shaped through the process of assigning, negotiating, mediating, and modifying meaning through the process of communication and interaction. It further proposes the idea that the classroom, as a micro level site where communication takes place, creates a normative social order. Communication problems arise due in part to “gaps” across space and time, space and time being sociocultural diversity and relativity as well as changes in society (such as the appearance of new technology) upsetting the social order (145). The upset of the social order is due to “difficulties in coordination...” due to “...a scarcity of shared rituals, rules, and expectations among [a society’s] members...” (145). He points out that these “... perturbations in the ecology of codes... disrupt interaction, but at the same time enable the creative production of new meaning

and new means of communication...” (ibid). This being said, this study conceptualizes the idea that through the emergence of AI-infused technology and gamification in the classroom communicative tensions surface *the social order whereby teacher identity as the authority and students as learners in the classroom is communicatively (re)produced*.

Due to generative AI’s appearance in the classroom, disruptions to the status quo such as in traditional learning hierarchies have become prevalent. The normative classroom order where the teacher as the content specialist and learning leader is challenged and due generative AI’s emergence. Students are questioning approaches and teacher authority, as well as peers and various stakeholders. Teachers are still trying to make sense of the role that generative AI-infused technologies would have in their practice, identity, and authority (Ghamrawi, Shal, and Ghamrawi, 2024). Furthermore, exchange teachers being of different cultural paradigms entering the United States classroom, dialectical tensions arise due cultural differences such as student level of respect and parental expectations (Lee, 2015). The process of navigating this reality, therefore, shapes the practice of re-conceptualizing and re-negotiate professional identities and authorities to make sense with the changes in a classroom beset by generative AI-infused technology and cultural shifts.

Symbolic Interactionism

This study primarily situates its discussion framework within with the insights from Symbolic Interactionism. A prominent voice within this tradition is Harold Blummer’s (Griffin, et al. 2023). Building on his mentor George Herbert Mead, Blummer develops the idea that words capture what is most the human activity that people do -

talking.

Blummer's Symbolic Interactionism advances three core premises which centers around *meaning, language, and thought*. These three principles shape a person's conception of *self and identity* and *socialization* into the larger community (ibid.). A symbol is a stimulus (a prompt) forged by learned meaning and value for people (Schramm, 1986 cited by (Griffin,et al, 2023).

Blummer starts with the premise that *humans act toward people or things on the basis of the meanings they assign to people or things* ((Griffin,et al, 2023). Facts in themselves cannot spur action, rather the interpretation of it is the basis for social action. This premise can be seen, for example, in how students perceive the figure of a teacher. How students respond to the teacher - whether hostile or diffident - is shaped by the meanings they have had on what a *teacher* is. The same can be said in reverse, as an exchange teacher, what do I mean by "student" and how do I negotiate, as an exchange teacher, the assigned meaning of "student" in a multicultural environment? The interactionist perspective can be best diagrammed as Stimulus - Interpretation - Response (ibid.). Humans act on their definition of the stimulus.

Blummer's second premise is that *meaning arises out of social interaction that people have with one another* ((Griffin,et al., 2023). Blummer argued that meaning is not inherent in objects and that meaning is not a pre-existent or default state of nature but rather *negotiated* through language (ibid.). For the interactionist, symbols, which are stimuli learned through meaning and value for people, convey how we are to feel, respond to people, situation, objects, to which it refers. In a multicultural classroom,

meanings are always negotiated and learned through modeled behavior and social cues. Meaning must not be assumed for there is no such thing as a universal set of cultural idioms, gestures, and norms. Words like “black” and “white” carry strong connotations in the United States of America that may not exist within the cultural framework of a student from Yemen. Furthermore, the classroom and technology-mediated spaces become *sites of symbolic interaction* whereby communication takes place and meaning is negotiated.

Blummer’s third premise states that *an individual’s interpretation of symbols is modified by their own thought processes (inner conversation or minding)* (Griffin, 2023). Thinking, or one’s inner conversation, is where an individual rehearses further movement, thinks about alternative movements, and to anticipate the other’s responses or reactions. For Mead, this process of thinking affords the individual self-talk to sort out situations. To do this, we need language and before thought takes place, we need to interact. The value of “wait times” are important in the ESL classroom. This affords each student a way to internally rehearse reactions and adjust behavior accordingly. Feedback from the teacher and peers (i.e. good work!) is negotiated through minding and subsequent behaviors follow based on this act of self-negotiation. From a teacher’s perspective in the multicultural classroom, this is best practiced by deliberate reflection and strategic restraint of one’s reaction, especially that symbols are always in the process of negotiation and reproduction (ibid.)

For Mead (cited by (Griffin,et al., 2023), the self is forged by painting a self-portrait of who we are by *taking the role of the other*, that is by imagining ourselves based on how we look in relation to the other. The Mead-Cooley Hypothesis, popularly

known as the looking-glass self, claims that one's self conception stems from assimilating judgement from significant others. Thus the self is a social product. Within this framework, the self is a function of language because the self-concept is rooted in talk. The self is not a static concept because it can only be experienced in relation to someone. For Mead (ibid.), the self is composed of the "I" and the "Me". The "I" is conceived as a spontaneous, driving force that fosters all that is novel and it is unpredictable and unorganized. Mead sees it as forever elusive. The "Me" is the image seen in reference to the other and is the self reflected based on other people's reactions. The "Me" is how we see ourselves as objects. Within my lived reality, the "I" refers to the spontaneous part of myself. It is what makes me uniquely "Gino". However, I am not merely the unpredictable and spontaneous "Gino". I am also the "Gino" that reflects upon my self-conception in relation to my interactions with others - I am a "teacher", I am a "father", I am a "husband". I respond and behave in reference to the other.

Mead sees the "I" and the "Me" process in the Self as: When the "I" speaks, the "Me" hears, and the "I" of this moment is present in the "me" of the next moment (Griffin, Ledbetter, & Sparks, 2023). Mead further describes the composite image we put together as the generalized other (Kolloch and O'Brien, 2001 cited by Griffin, Ledbetter, & Sparks, 2023). The generalized other is an organized set of information that individuals carry within them and believe about the expectation and attitude of the social group. There is not "Me" at birth, it is only formed through constant interaction. The generalized other can be seen as the put together reflections we have in the "looking-glass self" and the social expectation that influences every conversation that

happens in our minds. In the multicultural classroom thus, we can see each participant in constant talk, negotiation, and minding of various lived experiences which creates the conception of the generalized other.

Blummer's three premises - *meaning, language, and thought* - as it relates to how a teacher assigns meaning, negotiates, and mediates meaning and how that builds identity, or the "self" through communicative construction is of main interest in this study and shapes how this present study presents and shapes the discourse.

The Research Questions

This study seeks to explore the social order whereby teacher identity as the authority and students as learners in the classroom is communicatively (re)produced .

Specifically, this study seeks to understand and answer the following questions:

1. How has generative AI in a multicultural classroom threatened teacher's authority?
2. How does GAI and gamification integration in communicative practices (re)produce teacher authority in a multicultural classroom?

CHAPTER IV

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter outlines the research methodology used in this study. It discusses the research design: the research method, the participant in this study, and where and when this study takes place. It also outlines the declaration for AI use for this study.

Autoethnography as Research Approach

This study makes use of a qualitative research design, specifically autoethnography. Autoethnography is the approach or writing that aims to describe and analyze (graphy) one's personal experience to understand cultural experience (ethno) (Hermann, 2017 as cited by Rosete, 2019)

Autoethnography is a qualitative research approach that requires reflexive self-reflection, and when used in the context of the classroom it may facilitate an educator's exploration of their own position and behavior and can influence their teaching process (Steiner, 2023). The autoethnographic approach provides peculiar ways of thinking and feeling which makes an educator make sense of themselves and their interaction with others, particularly in the presence of powerful relations (Starr, 2022; Steiner, 2023). Autoethnographic inquiry has the potential to be transformative for the author, reader, and the social construct to which they belong. Through this type of method, discourse is created between the subject and the relevant experiences they engage in socially, culturally, and personally (Starr, 2022). For the educator, autoethnography allows them the opportunity to effectively take note of the pragmatic

demands of teaching and of everyday life experiences and how they shape who they are and what they do (Starr, 2022).

Steiner (2023) states for example that as a teacher, has noted how the autoethnographic process enabled them to situate themselves in their classroom. In the process of doing their autoethnography, they posed the following: what barriers emerged when she tried to diversify their pedagogy, and how they overcame emergent barriers to improve their teaching. They noted that the process of self-reflection positively reinforced their desire to continue searching for ways to create a more collaborative learning environment.

Fujieda (2008 cited by Lapidus, Kaveh, & Hirano, 2013) explains that autoethnography is a valid research tool for ESL writers and researchers. While their research focuses specifically on autoethnography and academic L2 literacy, they do explain how it can explore the impact of “the cross-cultural environment” (American academic culture) and the social group (teachers and peers). It also enables teachers to search deeper within themselves, with their own biases and show “the hidden truth and agony in a writer’s heart” (Fujieda, 2008 cited by Lapidus et al., 2013)

Autoethnography as a research technique has been used by Filipino teachers teaching abroad to reflect upon what they have learned, their identity, and the growth of their practice in the practice of their profession.

Dionson (2021)’s autoethnographic study explores how non-native English Speaking teachers (NNESTs) such as himself, strove to construct an identity as a legitimate professional teaching the English Language. Reflecting on how his identity is

communicatively constructed through active dialogue with peers, students, and parents, he noted that the act of engaging *in dialogue* has afforded him many truths about himself as a teacher. Through the process of autoethnography, he was able to draw insights about his teacher identity as a supporter, facilitator, and motivator and integrated these identities into his general conception of who he is as a teacher. The ethnographic process allowed him to reflect upon his strengths and weaknesses even though he had previous conceptions on being a non-native English speaker. By interpreting his experiences, mediated and modified through his interaction with others, he found new ways of seeing himself in relation to others.

Ellis (2011) points out that in an autoethnography, the author's credibility is the ultimate litmus test of its plausibility. This can be verified by the following points: the coherence of the story told and its ability to engage the readers and communicate with others who are different from themselves. Its reliability lies if it has offered an approach to improve the lives of its participants and its readers. Autoethnography's generalizability moves from respondents to readers and it is tested *by readers* on how enriching it is. Readers provide the validation of an autoethnographic research.

I am the sole participant of this research. I am a Filipino cultural exchange teacher based in the State of North Carolina. As of the writing of this dissertation, I have been a professional teacher for 14 years, with three of those school years served in the United States. I teach standard English leveled for ESL learners and English as a Second Language.

Standard English is known as English Language Arts (ELA), the general curriculum of English in the school system, the type of English every student is taught

and focuses mainly on reading literature and informational texts. Though being an ESL teacher, my way of teaching is leveled to the needs of the ELL student for ELA.

English as a Second Language (ESL) is a different curriculum of English and it is taught for students who are identified by the school system as English Language Learners (ELLs) and its focus is on general American Culture literacy and Academic Language across the subjects.

The locale is a school system in the State of North Carolina whose actual name has been changed into Big River County. My experiences as a Filipino Cultural Exchange ESL teacher is within the vicinity of this county and its school system.

This study documents my experience and reflections from 2023 - 2025.

This study firmly holds on to the University of the Philippines - OU's Principles for Responsible and Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence and follows its prescriptions and principles. The use of generative AI technology through *ChatGPT* (Open AI, 2024), *Google Gemini*, and *Apple Intelligence* (Apple, 2025) are used for the following purposes only:

1. As a tool to brainstorm ideas (compare and contrast, summarize)
2. Cluster ideas together for analysis
3. Creation of the citations in the style format of the DCOMM Program Manual
4. Transcribe voice memos, the researcher's audio recorded notes.

The researcher ensures that ethical standards are met and that personal identifiers such as names and addresses are not fed into the generative AI system. Likewise, following Zhang et al. (2025)'s suggestions on the integration of AI in

qualitative research with an emphasis on *transparency and traceability*, the prompts used are disclosed in the appendix.

Data Collection

This study makes use of naturally-occurring data as an anchor to develop the themes and the analysis for this study. The data collected is from 2023 - 2025. Personal identifiers are scrubbed out.

The naturally-occurring data in this study are drawn from the following sources:

- Talker Diary Entries
- Lesson Plans
- Recommendation Letters
- Slide presentations
- Emails
- Generative AI-generated Reports

Data Analysis

This study makes use of inductive thematic analysis in its data analysis.

Drawing from Bingham & Witkowsky (2022), I read through all the naturally occurring data and then sort relevant topical categories together into “codes”. I then start my initial coding. According to their similarity, similar codes are clustered together and analyzed to produce sub-themes. Sub-themes are then analyzed to produce the final themes.

My analysis also presents key insights from Blummer (cited by Griffin et al., 2023) particularly his concept of *minding* and Hecht and Choi's (2011) concept of the centrality of the communication as identity itself. Hence, my analysis contains a *reflexive* dimension. I draw from the work of Martin, Nakayama, and Flores (2001) to shape more reflexive dimensions of the analysis. They (ibid) point out that communication is relational, there is a dynamic "...in-betweenness" (204) which goes beyond the sum of each part in any relationship. This means that at moments, through the interaction with the other, a dialectical tension is created whereby two contradictory ideas are held *simultaneously*. This tension requires negotiation and transcendence, with the goal of recognizing interdependence and complementarity between the seemingly opposite perspectives. This process mirrors Blummer's concept of *minding* where an individual negotiates, interprets, and attempts to synthesize new meanings out of the seeming contradiction.

Analytical Tables

Table 1.1. Talker's Diary - AI Threats Entries (TDAIT)

Excerpts	Code
<p>TDAIT, E1</p> <p>During my first year in the American classroom, generative AI was still at its infancy, but it had already slowly started to appear in my classroom.</p> <p>Being an English teacher, writing assignments is a common strategy in my repertoire. I was assigned a writing assignment on character analysis. There was this student who submitted an essay under ten minutes into the writing assignment - a full essay in under ten minutes. As I read through the essay, I noted how refined it was - too refined for the student who submitted it. I called the student and asked him to retell his analysis to me in his own words. He smirked and said that I could just read his essay. I told him that his content was AI-generated and that this was against my policy. He shrugged and just went back to his seat.</p>	<p>Threatening self-image as content expert</p>
<p>TDAIT, E2</p> <p>There have been more incidents, I remember, where students would use the AI features in some applications that they have on their phones</p>	<p>Outsourcing critical thinking to GAI</p>

<p>(such as Snapchat) to answer questions in worksheets. I recall one student, who was very close to me, holding his phone over a sheet of math homework to get the answer through AI. Seeing me, he laughed and said that I should be “cool.” I was personally frustrated and berated him, telling him that GAI should not be used in such a way. He put away his phone, as well as his math homework, and proceeded with the day.</p> <p>This incident highlights the main problem with GAI and teacher authority in the classroom: teacher authority, especially as the controller of meaningful experiences in the classroom and the content expert, is eroded and disrupted. This incident presented for me a concrete shift in the classroom environment, that GAI has affected how teacher authority is viewed by the students.</p>	<p>Weakening of authority</p>
<p>TDAIT, E3 GAI challenged the way I did assessment because I cannot truly measure or assess the actual transfer of learning. I felt that GAI had challenged my notion of assessment and that I had to create new criteria and frameworks to assess student learning.</p>	<p>Challenging traditional teacher roles Weakening of authority</p>
<p>TDAIT, E4 GAI’s instant access to information making my explanations seem less essential shows itself in some interactions I have with students. Given that it takes time for me to process and synthesize information upon a student question, the rapidity by which GAI instantly produces answers has made me realize that my presence has become more non-central.</p>	<p>Threatening self-image as content expert Outsourcing critical thinking to GAI</p>
<p>TDAIT, E5 I adjusted my teaching methods through focusing on content curation. As the teacher, whenever as a class we experiment with GAI, I go around and solicit responses from students as to what things they have learned in their interaction. I ask them to retell what insights they have gotten from GAI interaction and either correct or affirm their insights based on my professional judgement. Instead of being a source of all knowledge, I have become a kind of guide to make sure they arrive at the relevant and correct one.</p>	<p>Outsourcing critical thinking to GAI</p>
<p>TDAIT, E6 At first, I felt that GAI was replacing me as the primary source of knowledge in the classroom. I wanted to personally do away with GAI altogether in the classroom, but seeing students use it more and more meant that I should find ways to work with it. I realized that I could not possibly compete with GAI as the fountainhead of knowledge. So I started reevaluating my authority until I realized that while GAI is teeming with “knowledge,” ensuring that the correct and relevant kind of knowledge is delivered was something else. My professional judgement was needed to ensure that each student engaged with the relevant kind of knowledge to bridge learning gaps. I started focusing on curating and scaffolding rather than trying to outsmart the machine.</p>	<p>Threatening self-image as content expert Challenging traditional teacher roles</p>
<p>TDAIT, E7 GAI made me feel that I had to prove my worth in the classroom as an authority by making me feel “dumber.” Though it presented opportunities for me to use its personalization aspects to teach targeted skills to specific students—which I myself find too tedious or time-consuming to do.</p>	<p>Threatening self-image as content expert</p>
<p>TDAIT, E8 The presence of GAI in my multicultural classroom challenged me early on to try and find means and ways to subsume it within my practice because I saw how AI had the capacity to be very disruptive in my classroom, but at the same time I know that as a teacher, I could use, like a lot of things, what AI has to offer to streamline and simplify my</p>	<p>Challenging traditional teacher roles</p>

<p>workload. So it was a tension, really, on my part to try and subsume artificial intelligence within my practice early on.</p>	
<p>TDAIT, E9</p> <p>Personally, GAI made me feel replaced as a teacher in the classroom because, more and more, I've noticed that the features that AI has are indeed becoming very disruptive. For example, I remember when the AI tutor became a thing and I did not know how to place myself in relation to the AI tutor. Because if the AI platform can tutor students and direct them to the correct information, what does that mean for me as a teacher? This particular event triggered a feeling of fear and dread of being replaced because education is the only thing I felt I knew to do. I have been a teacher for a very long time and I love it, but with the arrival of this kind of technology that disrupts the way I look at things and the way I do things, it was scary and frankly difficult. So I had to find means and ways to try and navigate my identity and authority where this could be a norm in the classroom, and it increasingly is becoming a norm in the classroom - this integration of GAI technology.</p>	<p>Weakening of authority</p>
<p>TDAIT, E10</p> <p>At first, I felt my authority shaken and challenged because I knew that I could never outperform GAI in terms of speed, content generation, or language translation for multilingual learners. I felt that what made me a unique teacher was challenged by these innovative skills that AI has. Over time, however, I started placing myself as the human being, as the human agency, in GAI use in the classroom. When I started putting myself as the human first, the machine and the use of the machine became secondary, and I realized that GAI worked tremendously better if it were guided by me, the human and the content expert in the classroom. I felt that there is this human creativity element that GAI could never do. It could never foster relationships with students. It could never diagnose little cues that specific students have that they need, and it can only be experienced and felt and encountered human-to-human. GAI can never do this.</p>	<p>Threatening self-image as content expert</p> <p>Challenging traditional teacher roles</p>
<p>TDAIT, E11</p> <p>I recall a student laughing at me when she saw that I was using ChatGPT, and she said, "Why are you using ChatGPT? You're not allowed to use ChatGPT. You're supposed to be a teacher," and she laughed. I remember explicitly that I told her that, yes, I am using ChatGPT, but watch this - so I started using ChatGPT as a tool to prompt discussions, and we started talking about an idea that we synthesized through ChatGPT, and we talked about it in the classroom - the synthesized idea - whether or not we agreed.</p> <p>At first, I did feel that my authority was very much challenged, that the students were looking at me as if I were dumb or as if I were a teacher who was, so to say, "cheating" because I was using GAI tools to help me. But then, when I started integrating GAI tools and I started using them as a springboard to pique interest, to summarize ideas, and to see whether or not students agreed or disagreed, it radically altered the way I did things. So this initial threat of being replaced by the machine—I started to reflect on this and realized, through my interaction with the students and the machine, that my authority as a teacher, though seemingly at first undermined, was actually transformed and reproduced. Now, I feel more competent in the use of AI.</p>	<p>Outsourcing critical thinking to GAI</p> <p>Challenging traditional teacher roles</p> <p>Weakening of authority</p>

Table 1.2 Recommendation Letter 1 (RL1)

Excerpts	Code
<p>RL1, E1</p>	<p>Tailoring lessons that fit learners' needs</p>

[Mr. Paradela] uses AI not just to create materials, but to personalize instruction for his students, adjusting lessons based on their language proficiency levels and learning needs.	
RL1, E2 [Mr. Paradela] uses and has even found ways to make parent communication easier and more understandable through translation tools, always keeping families informed and involved.	Communicator with parents Partnering with parents in the learning process
RL1, E3 [Mr. Paradela's colleagues] look up to him as an expert, not only in integrating AI in his instruction but also for his impressive ideas on how to create lessons that are engaging and rigorous for his students.	Classroom designer

Table 1.3 Recommendation Letter 2 (RL2)

Excerpts	Code
RL2, E1 Mr. Paradela actively uses AI in his classroom as a teaching tool and parent outreach and communications.	Partnering with parents in the learning process
RL2, E2 For example, he recently engaged students in a theme-based writing project that used image creation and story frames to develop literacy skills with English language proficiency.	Creator of fun and engaging lessons
RL2, E3 He also uses AI to develop instructional materials based on the current English language proficiency and reading/comprehension level of each student based on their assessment scores.	Scaffolder of personalized learning Tailoring lessons that fit learners' needs
RL2, E4 He uses AI to communicate with parents through translation tools and multilingual family bulletins.	Communicator with parents Partnering with parents in the learning process
RL2, E5 Mr. Paradela is a team player who collaborates with his coworkers and is regarded as a valuable resource for innovative curriculum and instruction. He is more than willing to share his work and make himself available to advise other teachers on how to use technology to improve student outcomes.	Classroom designer
RL2, E6 The skills and strategies he will learn in the AI Fellows program will enhance his impact on the field, both in ESL education and district-level AI development through future presentations, professional development sessions and curriculum development that will deeply benefit our district and students.	Classroom designer

Table 1.4 Lesson Plan (March 3-7, 2025) (LP 1)

Excerpts	Code
<p>LP1, E2</p> <p>Inspire - Activity 1 (Direct Instruction)</p> <p>"I do" (:20)</p> <p>Teacher models lesson</p> <p>Students do 20 minutes of Khan Academy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Finding Theme and Central Ideal - Inferences - Citing Textual Evidences 	<p>Learning facilitator</p>
<p>LP1, E3</p> <p>Challenge - Activity 2 (Student Demonstrations & Connections)</p> <p>"We do" (:20)</p> <p>Teacher monitors student engagement/facilitates collaborations.</p> <p>Students do MagicSchool.AI / AI tutor for 20 minutes:</p> <p>Prompt: Teach me how to find the components of an Objective Summary</p>	<p>Learning facilitator</p>
<p>LP1, E4</p> <p>Empower - Activity 3 (Student Release Independent Practice)</p> <p>"You do" (:20)</p> <p>Teacher monitors student engagement, answers questions, and ensures differentiation</p> <p>Writing a theme Statement Project in class:</p> <p>ChatGPT: Using generative AI to "award" best work according to rubric. Show strengths and weaknesses for each submission.</p> <p>Prompt: Randomly assign a number for these submissions (Student A, Student B, etc.).</p> <p>Award the best work based on these details - a theme statement:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Author's + text + analytical verb + lesson. Provide the strength and weaknesses for each.</p>	<p>Monitoring learners' progress</p>
<p>LP1, E5</p> <p>Class Summative Work</p> <p>Writing an objective summary.</p> <p>Project in class:</p> <p>ChatGPT: Using generative AI to "aw</p>	<p>Assessing learners' needs</p>

<p>ard" best work according to rubric. Show strengths and weaknesses for each submission.</p> <p>Prompt: Randomly assign a number for these submissions (Student A, Student B, etc.).</p> <p>Award the best work based on these details - a theme statement:</p> <p>Step 1: Topic Sentence (Name it + Verb it + Motif it)</p> <p>Step 2: 3-5 key details (Think "beginning, middle, end;" also, "emergence, general idea into that poignant</p> <p>Step 3: Conclusion Sentence (Refine the general idea into that poignant</p> <p>Provide the strength and weaknesses for each.</p>	
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Table 1.5 Email (Solicitando colaboracion) (EM1)

Excerpts	Code
<p>EM1, E1</p> <p>I am not a Spanish-speaker so I am using an AI translator to help me communicate with you so I apologize if the grammar is a bit unusual. (P3)</p> <p><i>No hablo español, así que estoy utilizando un traductor de inteligencia artificial para comunicarme con usted, por lo que le pido disculpas si la gramática es un poco inusual.</i></p>	<p>Communicator with parents</p> <p>Partnering with parents in the learning process</p>

Table 1.6. Successmaker Student 1 Performance (SSP1)

Excerpts	Code
<p>SSP1, E1</p> <p>Successmaker's AI program:</p> <p>Student current course level: Far Below Level (8.70)</p> <p>[Student's] current course level is Far below grade level for grade 10. At this time of year, students' course levels should be at or above 10.00.</p>	<p>Data-driven decision maker</p> <p>Improving student performance</p>
<p>SSP1, E2</p> <p>Successmaker's AI program:</p> <p>Percentage Skills Mastered: 70%</p> <p>Areas for Growth - Since AP Skills not mastered:</p> <p>8.65 - Analyze how characters in literature deal with conflict, solve problems, and relate to real-life situations.</p> <p>8.65 - Use question-and-answer relationships to improve comprehension of texts: Right There questions</p> <p>8.49 - Identify incorrect shifts in verb tenses</p>	<p>Data-driven decision maker</p> <p>Improving student performance</p>

Table 1.7 Successmaker Student 2 Performance (SSP2)

Excerpts	Code
<p>SSP2, E1</p> <p>Successmaker's AI program:</p> <p>Student current course level: Far Below Level (7.74)</p> <p>[Student's] current course level is Far below grade level for grade 10. At this time of year, students' course levels should be at or above 10.00.</p>	<p>Data-driven decision maker</p> <p>Improving student performance</p>
<p>SSP2, E2</p> <p>Successmaker's AI program:</p> <p>Percentage of Skill Mastered: 50%</p> <p>Areas for Growth - Since AP Skills not mastered:</p> <p>7.56 - Use compare and contrast relationships to gain meaning</p> <p>7.61 - Paraphrase information from text</p> <p>7.61 - Compare themes</p> <p>7.63 - Use Greek and Latin roots to determine the meaning of unfamiliar words.</p>	<p>Scaffolder of personalized learning</p>

Table 1.8 Slide: Paradela Peso (PP1)

Excerpts	Code
<p>PP1, E1</p> <p>Once a week, I set up a pop-up shop where I sell chips, takis, airheads, jolly ranchers, etc.</p> <p>You can only "buy" them using Paradela Pesos.</p> <p>Paradela Pesos can also be used as experience points which can get you classroom perks!</p>	<p>Motivator towards a pleasurable learning experience</p>

Table 1.9 Slide: Magic School AI Tutor (MSAI1)

Excerpts	Code
<p>MSAI1, E1</p> <p>Get tutored with AI! You have 30 minutes to do as many as you can.</p> <p>Go to my AI Tutor:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Type this prompt: Teach me how to analyze characters in a story 2. Answer the questions 	<p>Tutoring student learning</p>

Table 1.10 Magic School AI Tutor Summary (AIT1)

Excerpts	Code
<p>AIT1, E1</p> <p>Tools Used: AI Tutor</p> <p>Behavioral Notes: No misbehaviors or concerns observed.</p> <p>Strengths & Weaknesses: Strong critical thinking and comprehension skills; express complex ideas well. Strategies: Encourage thematic developments</p> <p>Areas for Improvement: Focus on expanding thematic analysis to new genres. Suggest exploring diverse texts for broader perspectives.</p>	<p>Tutoring student learning</p>

Table 1.11 Gamified Classroom Guidelines Slide (GCGS1)

Excerpts	Code
<p>GCGS1, E1</p> <p>You level up in this class by doing the quests of the day. The main quests must be marked completed in order to level up.</p>	<p>Gamification strategist</p> <p>Improving student performance</p>
<p>GCGS1, E2</p> <p>Doing various quests really well will also give you a chance to win badges. Badges will give you perks in this classroom such as extra restroom time or getting the chance to choose your own music.</p>	<p>Gamification strategist</p> <p>Awarding performance</p>

<p>GCGS1, E3</p> <p>Once you reach level 5 and 10, you will receive a digital achievement badge. The level 5 achievement badge enables you to play your own preferred music during working period and an assignment pass (usable in the future) perfect score in one output</p>	<p>Motivator towards a pleasurable learning experience</p>
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Table 1.12 - Excerpts from my Talker’s Diary (ETD1)

Excerpts	Code
<p>ETD, E5: Toward the end of my first year teaching, AI had been something that really fascinated me. I wanted to see what the potential of AI was after Ms. J taught me what had worked for her. Following her example, I primarily experimented with ChatGPT and MagicSchool.AI to assist in lesson planning, differentiated materials, rubrics, writing feedback, and email responding. Being open to experiment with AI technology allowed me to develop new tools and strategies that have helped my teaching practice. It functioned as a kind of “teacher assistant” that allows me to easily reach teaching goals.</p>	<p>Classroom designer</p>
<p>ETD, E6: I was transitioning to become an English and ESL teacher the following school year. I noticed that my ESL students were more receptive and eager to learn than my previous group. I felt that they had higher appreciation for the material, being second language learners in a country where English was a necessity in daily life. I needed to sustain this engagement with the materials and started experimenting with various teaching styles. These strategies became standard in my repertoire and became the source of my gamification of the classroom.</p> <p>The key strategies I took from that summer, the ones that stuck, are what I call the Three Es: Engage, Explain, and Explore. A class session (one-hour and thirty minutes) generally looked like this:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Engage is what I call the first 15–20 minutes: students play a game, we go over objectives, and “get in the zone” using tools like Gimkit, Blooket, or Quizizz. 2. Explain is the next 30–40 minutes: I teach a mini-lesson using Nearpod. This part often feels like the day’s first quest. If they complete, join in my discussions, do my mini-activities correctly, they earn Paradela Pesos. 3. Explore is the last 30–40 minutes: students apply what they’ve learned through independent work using ESL Library (Ellii), CommonLit, or Edpuzzle. If they score 80% or higher (our “mastery” grade), they get five more Paradela Pesos. Some students earn up to 10 a day and save them for class rewards. 	<p>Gamification strategist</p>

<p>ETD, E7: Parents in my ESL classroom come from all walks of life and languages. I have Spanish speaking parents, Haitian Creole speaking parents, Thai, Arabic, and Filipino. With the exception of my Filipino parents, I have had difficulties communicating with parents of other linguistic groups, not because of fear but because I do not speak their language. AI has been a great help to translate communications from parents and vice versa. When I use AI to communicate with them, I am transparent that I am using ChatGPT and that personal identifiers are never fed into the app. AI technology has enabled me to automate some classroom practices such as grading, lesson planning, and the construction of levelled worksheets for individualized instruction. It has given me leisure time to do other classroom-relevant tasks such as parent communication and data dives. However, AI use must be guided by my judgement and must always be filtered and checked by me for accuracy.</p>	<p>Communicator with parents</p> <p>Data-driven decision maker</p> <p>Partnering with parents</p>
<p>ETD, E8: Having worked with AI technology and gamified practices in the classroom, and for all that it can seem to do, it has its limitations. Having an AI teaching assistant is quite useful. But its use, as I have experienced it, can never replace key processes in the classroom. While AI can generate content, it can hallucinate and give false information. The same goes for gamification techniques. Gamified techniques stimulate and engage pique interest but only to serve inquiry, attention, and analysis but only for short-periods of time. As the teacher, I am irreplaceable in the teaching-learning processes. Despite having the tools at my disposal, their effectiveness has to filter through my judgement and experience. I am a content specialist. I facilitate learning. Technology is wonderful but they do not replace me because they do not direct my students to clear goals in the classroom.</p>	<p>Learning facilitator</p>
<p>ETD, E9: In the few years that I have taught in the United States, I feel that I have learned a lot and that the way I now teach and facilitate my classroom processes has been forever changed. Having experienced and having been challenged by the needs and demands of a multicultural classroom, and as a response to these, I feel that I have grown in my cultural literacy and have become mindful of the diversity of experiences and learning styles. I have learned how to communicate content effectively through the mediation of a variety of EdTech tools, AI-infusion, and engage students through adopting gamification techniques.</p>	<p>Learning facilitator</p> <p>Assessing learners' progress</p>

Table 2.1 Threatening self-image as content expert

Excerpts	Code
<p>TDAIT, E1: During my first year in the American classroom, generative AI was still at its infancy, but it had already slowly started to appear in my classroom.</p> <p>Being an English teacher, writing assignments is a common strategy in my repertoire. I was assigned a writing assignment on character analysis. There was this student who submitted an essay under ten minutes into the writing assignment - a full essay in under ten minutes. As I read through the essay, I noted how refined it was - too refined for the student who submitted it. I called the student and asked him to retell his analysis to me in his own words. He smirked and said that I could just read his essay. I told him that his content was AI-generated and that this was against my policy. He shrugged and just went back to his seat.</p>	<p>Threatening self-image as content expert</p>
<p>TDAIT, E4: GAI's instant access to information making my explanations</p>	

<p>seem less essential shows itself in some interactions I have with students. Given that it takes time for me to process and synthesize information upon a student question, the rapidity by which GAI instantly produces answers has made me realize that my presence has become more non-central.</p>	
<p>TDAIT, E6: At first, I felt that GAI was replacing me as the primary source of knowledge in the classroom. I wanted to personally do away with GAI altogether in the classroom, but seeing students use it more and more meant that I should find ways to work with it.</p> <p>I realized that I could not possibly compete with GAI as the fountainhead of knowledge. So I started reevaluating my authority until I realized that while GAI is teeming with “knowledge,” ensuring that the correct and relevant kind of knowledge is delivered was something else. My professional judgement was needed to ensure that each student engaged with the relevant kind of knowledge to bridge learning gaps. I started focusing on curating and scaffolding rather than trying to outsmart the machine.</p>	
<p>TDAIT, E7: GAI made me feel that I had to prove my worth in the classroom as an authority by making me feel “dumber.” Though it presented opportunities for me to use its personalization aspects to teach targeted skills to specific students, which I myself find too tedious or time-consuming to do.</p>	
<p>TDAIT, E10: At first, I felt my authority shaken and challenged because I knew that I could never outperform GAI in terms of speed, content generation, or language translation for multilingual learners. I felt that what made me a unique teacher was challenged by these innovative skills that AI has. Over time, however, I started placing myself as the human being, as the human agency, in GAI use in the classroom. When I started putting myself as the human first, the machine and the use of the machine became secondary, and I realized that GAI worked tremendously better if it were guided by me, the human and the content expert in the classroom. I felt that there is this human creativity element that GAI could never do. It could never foster relationships with students. It could never diagnose little cues that specific students have that they need, and it can only be experienced and felt and encountered human-to-human. GAI can never do this.</p>	

Table 2.2. Tendency to outsource thinking to GAI

Excerpts	Code
<p>TDAIT, E2: There have been more incidents, I remember, where students would use the AI features in some applications that they have on their phones (such as Snapchat) to answer questions in worksheets. I recall one student, who was very close to me, holding his phone over a sheet of math homework to get the answer through AI. Seeing me, he laughed and said that I should be “cool.” I was personally frustrated and berated him, telling him that GAI should not be used in such a way.</p> <p>He put away his phone, as well as his math homework, and proceeded with the day.</p> <p>This incident highlights the main problem with GAI and teacher authority in the classroom: teacher authority, especially as the controller of meaningful experiences in the classroom and the content expert, is eroded and disrupted. This incident presented for me a concrete shift in the classroom environment, that GAI has affected how teacher authority is viewed by the students.</p>	<p>Tendency to outsource thinking to GAI</p>
<p>TDAIT, E4: GAI’s instant access to information making my explanations</p>	

<p>seem less essential shows itself in some interactions I have with students. Given that it takes time for me to process and synthesize information upon a student question, the rapidity by which GAI instantly produces answers has made me realize that my presence has become more non-central.</p>	
<p>TDAIT, E5: I adjusted my teaching methods through focusing on content curation. As the teacher, whenever as a class we experiment with GAI, I go around and solicit responses from students as to what things they have learned in their interaction. I ask them to retell what insights they have gotten from GAI interaction and either correct or affirm their insights based on my professional judgement.</p> <p>Instead of being a source of all knowledge, I have become a kind of guide to make sure they arrive at the relevant and correct one.</p>	
<p>TDAIT, E11: I recall a student laughing at me when she saw that I was using ChatGPT, and she said, "Why are you using ChatGPT? You're not allowed to use ChatGPT. You're supposed to be a teacher," and she laughed. I remember explicitly that I told her that, yes, I am using ChatGPT, but watch this - so I started using ChatGPT as a tool to prompt discussions, and we started talking about an idea that we synthesized through ChatGPT, and we talked about it in the classroom - the synthesized idea - whether or not we agreed.</p> <p>At first, I did feel that my authority was very much challenged, that the students were looking at me as if I were dumb or as if I were a teacher who was, so to say, "cheating" because I was using GAI tools to help me. But then, when I started integrating GAI tools and I started using them as a springboard to pique interest, to summarize ideas, and to see whether or not students agreed or disagreed, it radically altered the way I did things. So this initial threat of being replaced by the machine - I started to reflect on this and realized, through my interaction with the students and the machine, that my authority as a teacher, though seemingly at first undermined, was actually transformed and reproduced. Now, I feel more competent in the use of AI.</p>	

Table 2.3. Challenging traditional teacher roles

Excerpts	Code
<p>TDAIT, E5: I adjusted my teaching methods through focusing on content curation. As the teacher, whenever as a class we experiment with GAI, I go around and solicit responses from students as to what things they have learned in their interaction. I ask them to retell what insights they have gotten from GAI interaction and either correct or affirm their insights based on my professional judgement.</p> <p>Instead of being a source of all knowledge, I have become a kind of guide to make sure they arrive at the relevant and correct one.</p>	Challenging traditional teacher roles
<p>TDAIT, E6: At first, I felt that GAI was replacing me as the primary source of knowledge in the classroom. I wanted to personally do away with GAI altogether in the classroom, but seeing students use it more and more meant that I should find ways to work with it.</p> <p>I realized that I could not possibly compete with GAI as the fountainhead of knowledge. So I started reevaluating my authority until I realized that while GAI is teeming with "knowledge," ensuring that the correct and relevant kind of knowledge is delivered was something else. My professional judgement was needed to ensure that each student engaged with the relevant kind of knowledge to bridge learning gaps. I started focusing on curating and scaffolding rather than trying to outsmart the machine.</p>	
<p>TDAIT, E8: The presence of GAI in my multicultural classroom challenged me early on to try and find means and ways to subsume it within my practice because I saw how AI had the capacity to be very disruptive in my</p>	

<p>classroom, but at the same time I know that as a teacher, I could use, like a lot of things, what AI has to offer to streamline and simplify my workload. So it was a tension, really, on my part to try and subsume artificial intelligence within my practice early on.</p>	
<p>TDAIT, E10: At first, I felt my authority shaken and challenged because I knew that I could never outperform GAI in terms of speed, content generation, or language translation for multilingual learners. I felt that what made me a unique teacher was challenged by these innovative skills that AI has. Over time, however, I started placing myself as the human being, as the human agency, in GAI use in the classroom. When I started putting myself as the human first, the machine and the use of the machine became secondary, and I realized that GAI worked tremendously better if it were guided by me, the human and the content expert in the classroom. I felt that there is this human creativity element that GAI could never do. It could never foster relationships with students. It could never diagnose little cues that specific students have that they need, and it can only be experienced and felt and encountered human-to-human. GAI can never do this.</p>	
<p>TDAIT, E11: I recall a student laughing at me when she saw that I was using ChatGPT, and she said, "Why are you using ChatGPT? You're not allowed to use ChatGPT. You're supposed to be a teacher," and she laughed. I remember explicitly that I told her that, yes, I am using ChatGPT, but watch this - so I started using ChatGPT as a tool to prompt discussions, and we started talking about an idea that we synthesized through ChatGPT, and we talked about it in the classroom - the synthesized idea - whether or not we agreed. At first, I did feel that my authority was very much challenged, that the students were looking at me as if I were dumb or as if I were a teacher who was, so to say, "cheating" because I was using GAI tools to help me. But then, when I started integrating GAI tools and I started using them as a springboard to pique interest, to summarize ideas, and to see whether or not students agreed or disagreed, it radically altered the way I did things. So this initial threat of being replaced by the machine - I started to reflect on this and realized, through my interaction with the students and the machine, that my authority as a teacher, though seemingly at first undermined, was actually transformed and reproduced. Now, I feel more competent in the use of AI.</p>	

Table 2.4. Weakening teacher authority

Excerpts	Code
<p>TDAIT, E2: There have been more incidents, I remember, where students would use the AI features in some applications that they have on their phones (such as Snapchat) to answer questions in worksheets. I recall one student, who was very close to me, holding his phone over a sheet of math homework to get the answer through AI. Seeing me, he laughed and said that I should be "cool." I was personally frustrated and berated him, telling him that GAI should not be used in such a way.</p> <p>He put away his phone, as well as his math homework, and proceeded with the day.</p> <p>This incident highlights the main problem with GAI and teacher authority in the classroom: teacher authority, especially as the controller of meaningful experiences in the classroom and the content expert, is eroded and disrupted. This incident presented for me a concrete shift in the classroom environment, that GAI has affected how teacher authority is viewed by the students.</p>	<p>Weakening teacher authority</p>
<p>TDAIT, E3: GAI challenged the way I did assessment because I cannot</p>	

<p>truly measure or assess the actual transfer of learning. I felt that GAI had challenged my notion of assessment and that I had to create new criteria and frameworks to assess student learning.</p>	
<p>TDAIT, E9: Personally, GAI made me feel replaced as a teacher in the classroom because, more and more, I've noticed that the features that AI has are indeed becoming very disruptive. For example, I remember when the AI tutor became a thing and I did not know how to place myself in relation to the AI tutor. Because if the AI platform can tutor students and direct them to the correct information, what does that mean for me as a teacher? This particular event triggered a feeling of fear and dread of being replaced because education is the only thing I felt I knew to do. I have been a teacher for a very long time and I love it, but with the arrival of this kind of technology that disrupts the way I look at things and the way I do things, it was scary and frankly difficult. So I had to find means and ways to try and navigate my identity and authority where this could be a norm in the classroom, and it increasingly is becoming a norm in the classroom - this integration of GAI technology.</p>	
<p>TDAIT, E11: I recall a student laughing at me when she saw that I was using ChatGPT, and she said, "Why are you using ChatGPT? You're not allowed to use ChatGPT. You're supposed to be a teacher," and she laughed. I remember explicitly that I told her that, yes, I am using ChatGPT, but watch this - so I started using ChatGPT as a tool to prompt discussions, and we started talking about an idea that we synthesized through ChatGPT, and we talked about it in the classroom - the synthesized idea - whether or not we agreed. At first, I did feel that my authority was very much challenged, that the students were looking at me as if I were dumb or as if I were a teacher who was, so to say, "cheating" because I was using GAI tools to help me. But then, when I started integrating GAI tools and I started using them as a springboard to pique interest, to summarize ideas, and to see whether or not students agreed or disagreed, it radically altered the way I did things. So this initial threat of being replaced by the machine—I started to reflect on this and realized, through my interaction with the students and the machine, that my authority as a teacher, though seemingly at first undermined, was actually transformed and reproduced. Now, I feel more competent in the use of AI.</p>	

Table 2.5. Assessing learners' progress

Excerpts	Code
<p>LP1, E5: Class Summative Work Writing an objective summary. Project in class: ChatGPT: Using generative AI to "award" best work according to rubric. Show strengths and weaknesses for each submission. Prompt: Randomly assign a number for these submissions (Student A, Student B, etc.). Award the best work based on these details - a theme statement: Step 1: Topic Sentence (Name it + Verb it + Motif it) Step 2: 3-5 key details (Think "beginning, middle, end;" also, "emergence, general idea into that poignant Step 3: Conclusion Sentence (Refine the general idea into that poignant Provide the strength and weaknesses for each.</p>	<p>Assessing learners' progress</p>

Table 2. 6. Awarding performance

Excerpts	Code
GCGS1, E2: Doing various quests really well will also give you a chance to win badges. Badges will give you perks in this classroom such as extra restroom time or getting the chance to choose your own music.	Awarding performance

Table 2. 7. Communicator with parents

Excerpts	Code
RL1, E2: [Mr. Paradela] uses and has even found ways to make parent communication easier and more understandable through translation tools, always keeping families informed and involved.	Communicator with parents
RL2, E4: He uses AI to communicate with parents through translation tools and multilingual family bulletins.	
EM1, E1: I am not a Spanish-speaker so I am using an AI translator to help me communicate with you so I apologize if the grammar is a bit unusual. <i>No hablo español, así que estoy utilizando un traductor de inteligencia artificial para comunicarme con usted, por lo que le pido disculpas si la gramática es un poco inusual.</i>	
ETD, E7: Parents in my ESL classroom come from all walks of life and languages. I have Spanish speaking parents, Haitian Creole speaking parents, Thai, Arabic, and Filipino. With the exception of my Filipino parents, I have had difficulties communicating with parents of other linguistic groups, not because of fear but because I do not speak their language. AI has been a great help to translate communications from parents and vice versa. When I use AI to communicate with them, I am transparent that I am using ChatGPT and that personal identifiers are never fed into the app. AI technology has enabled me to automate some classroom practices such as grading, lesson planning, and the construction of levelled worksheets for individualized instruction. It has given me leisure time to do other classroom-relevant tasks such as parent communication and data dives. However, AI use must be guided by my judgement and must always be filtered and checked by me for accuracy.	

Table 2.8. Creator of fun and engaging lessons

Excerpts	Code
RL2, E2: For example, he recently engaged students in a theme-based writing project that used image creation and story frames to develop literacy skills with English language proficiency.	Creator of fun and engaging lessons
SE1, E3: I'm not sure, just love how the teacher teaches, makes lessons	

more fun.	
ETD, E1: I noticed that students get easily bored after doing a worksheet which they can finish in 20-30 minutes... I struggled early on in finding work for them to do that also corresponded to the standards for the week.	

Table 2.9. Data-driven decision maker

Excerpts	Code
SSP1, E1: Successmaker's AI program: Student current course level: Far Below Level (8.70) [Student's] current course level is Far below grade level for grade 10. At this time of year, students' course levels should be at or above 10.00.	Data-driven decision maker
SSP1, E2: Successmaker's AI program: Percentage Skills Mastered: 70% Areas for Growth - Since AP Skills not mastered: 8.65 - Analyze how characters in literature deal with conflict, solve problems, and relate to real-life situations. 8.65 - Use question-and-answer relationships to improve comprehension of texts: Right There questions 8.49 - Identify incorrect shifts in verb tenses	
SSP2, E1: Successmaker's AI program: Student current course level: Far Below Level (7.74) [Student's] current course level is Far below grade level for grade 10. At this time of year, students' course levels should be at or above 10.00.	
ETD, E7: Parents in my ESL classroom come from all walks of life and languages. I have Spanish speaking parents, Haitian Creole speaking parents, Thai, Arabic, and Filipino. With the exception of my Filipino parents, I have had difficulties communicating with parents of other linguistic groups, not because of fear but because I do not speak their language. AI has been a great help to translate communications from parents and vice versa. When I use AI to communicate with them, I am transparent that I am using ChatGPT and that personal identifiers are never fed into the app. AI technology has enabled me to automate some classroom practices such as grading, lesson planning, and the construction of levelled worksheets for individualized instruction. It has given me leisure time to do other classroom-relevant tasks such as parent communication and data dives. However, AI use must be guided by my judgement and must always be filtered and checked by me for accuracy.	

Table 2.10. Tutoring student learning

Excerpts	Code
MSAI1, E1: Get tutored with AI! You have 30 minutes to do as many as you can. Go to my AI Tutor: 1. Type this prompt: Teach me how to analyze characters in a story 2. Answer the questions	Tutoring student learning

<p>AIT1, E1: Tools Used: AI Tutor Behavioral Notes: No misbehaviors or concerns observed. Strengths & Weaknesses: Strong critical thinking and comprehension skills; express complex ideas well. Strategies: Encourage thematic developments Areas for Improvement: Focus on expanding thematic analysis to new genres. Suggest exploring diverse texts for broader perspectives.</p>	
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Table 2.11. Gamification strategist

Excerpts	Code
<p>PP1, E1: Once a week, I set up a pop-up shop where I sell chips, takis, airheads, jolly ranchers, etc. You can only "buy" them using Paradela Pesos. Paradela Pesos can also be used as experience points which can get you classroom perks!</p>	Gamification strategist
<p>GCGS1, E1: You level up in this class by doing the quests of the day. The main quests must be marked completed in order to level up.</p>	
<p>GCGS1, E2: Doing various quests really well will also give you a chance to win badges. Badges will give you perks in this classroom such as extra restroom time or getting the chance to choose your own music.</p>	
<p>ETD, E6: I was transitioning to become an English and ESL teacher the following school year. I noticed that my ESL students were more receptive and eager to learn than my previous group. I felt that they had higher appreciation for the material, being second language learners in a country where English was a necessity in daily life. I needed to sustain this engagement with the materials and started experimenting with various teaching styles. These strategies became standard in my repertoire and became the source of my gamification of the classroom.</p>	

Table 2.12. Improving student performance

Excerpts	Code
<p>GCGS1, E1: You level up in this class by doing the quests of the day. The main quests must be marked completed in order to level up.</p>	Improving student performance
<p>SSP1, E1: Successmaker's AI program: Student current course level: Far Below Level (8.70) [Student's] current course level is Far below grade level for grade 10. At this time of year, students' course levels should be at or above 10.00.</p>	
<p>SSP1, E2: Successmaker's AI program: Percentage Skills Mastered: 70% Areas for Growth - Since AP Skills not mastered: 8.65 - Analyze how characters in literature deal with conflict, solve problems, and relate to real-life situations. 8.65 - Use question-and-answer relationships to improve comprehension of texts: Right There questions 8.49 - Identify incorrect shifts</p>	

in verb tenses	
SSP2, E1: Successmaker’s AI program: Student current course level: Far Below Level (7.74) [Student’s] current course level is Far below grade level for grade 10. At this time of year, students’ course levels should be at or above 10.00.	

Table 2.13. Classroom designer

Excerpts	Code
RL1, E3: [Mr. Paradela’s colleagues] look up to him as an expert, not only in integrating AI in his instruction but also for his impressive ideas on how to create lessons that are engaging and rigorous for his students.	Classroom designer
RL2, E5: Mr. Paradela is a team player who collaborates with his coworkers and is regarded as a valuable resource for innovative curriculum and instruction. He is more than willing to share his work and make himself available to advise other teachers on how to use technology to improve student outcomes.	
RL2, E6: The skills and strategies he will learn in the AI Fellows program will enhance his impact on the field, both in ESL education and district-level AI development through future presentations, professional development sessions and curriculum development that will deeply benefit our district and students.	
ETD, E5: Toward the end of my first year teaching, AI had been something that really fascinated me. I wanted to see what the potential of AI was after Ms. J taught me what had worked for her. Following her example, I primarily experimented with ChatGPT and MagicSchool.AI to assist in lesson planning, differentiated materials, rubrics, writing feedback, and email responding. Being open to experiment with AI technology allowed me to develop new tools and strategies that have helped my teaching practice. It functioned as a kind of “teacher assistant” that allows me to easily reach teaching goals.	

Table 2.14. Learning facilitator

Excerpts	Code
LP1, E2: Inspire - Activity 1 (Direct Instruction) “I do” (:20) Teacher models lesson Students do 20 minutes of Khan Academy: - Finding Theme and Central Ideal - Inferences - Citing Textual Evidences	Learning facilitator

<p>LP1, E3: Challenge - Activity 2 (Student Demonstrations & Connections) “We do” (:20) Teacher monitors student engagement/facilitates collaborations. Students do MagicSchool.AI / AI tutor for 20 minutes: Prompt: Teach me how to find the components of an Objective Summary</p>	
<p>ETD, E2: I wanted to see what the potential of AI was after Ms. J taught me what had worked for her... I followed her best practices and began to experiment with the technology... Associating with her enabled me to be more confident in my instruction and has made me feel more “in control” insofar as content is concerned.</p>	
<p>ETD, E1: I communicated this struggle in passing to my immediate department head and fellow teachers... They sent me to observe teachers and their best practices and to talk to them informally and “compare notes”.... During Professional Learning Community (PLC) Sessions, they would also keep me updated with newer technological trends and best practices.</p>	
<p>ETD, E8: Having worked with AI technology and gamified practices in the classroom, and for all that it can seem to do, it has its limitations. Having an AI teaching assistant is quite useful. But its use, as I have experienced it, can never replace key processes in the classroom. While AI can generate content, it can hallucinate and give false information. The same goes for gamification techniques. Gamified techniques stimulate and engage pique interest but only to serve inquiry, attention, and analysis but only for short-periods of time. As the teacher, I am irreplaceable in the teaching-learning processes. Despite having the tools at my disposal, their effectiveness has to filter through my judgement and experience. I am a content specialist. I facilitate learning. Technology is wonderful but they do not replace me because they do not direct my students to clear goals in the classroom.</p>	
<p>ETD, E9: In the few years that I have taught in the United States, I feel that I have learned a lot and that the way I now teach and facilitate my classroom processes has been forever changed. Having experienced and having been challenged by the needs and demands of a multicultural classroom, and as a response to these, I feel that I have grown in my cultural literacy and have become mindful of the diversity of experiences and learning styles. I have learned how to communicate content effectively through the mediation of a variety of EdTech tools, AI-infusion, and engage students through adopting gamification techniques.</p>	

Table 2.15. Monitoring learners’ progress

Excerpts	Code
<p>LP1, E4: Empower - Activity 3 (Student Release Independent Practice) “You do” (:20) Teacher monitors student engagement, answers questions, and ensures differentiation Writing a theme Statement Project in class: ChatGPT: Using generative AI to “award” best work according to rubric. Show strengths</p>	<p>Monitoring learners’ progress</p>

and weaknesses for each submission. Prompt: Randomly assign a number for these submissions (Student A, Student B, etc.). Award the best work based on these details - a theme statement: Author's + text + analytical verb + lesson. Provide the strength and weaknesses for each.	
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Table 2.16. Motivator towards a pleasurable learning experience

Excerpts	Code
PP1, E1: Once a week, I set up a pop-up shop where I sell chips, takis, airheads, jolly ranchers, etc. You can only "buy" them using Paradela Pesos. Paradela Pesos can also be used as experience points which can get you classroom perks!	Motivator towards a pleasurable learning experience
GCGS1, E3: Once you reach level 5 and 10, you will receive a digital achievement badge. The level 5 achievement badge enables you to play your own preferred music during working period and an assignment pass (usable in the future) perfect score in one output	

Table 2.17. Partnering with parents in the learning process

Excerpts	Code
RL1, E2: [Mr. Paradela] uses and has even found ways to make parent communication easier and more understandable through translation tools, always keeping families informed and involved.	Partnering with parents in the learning process
RL2, E1: Mr. Paradela actively uses AI in his classroom as a teaching tool and parent outreach and communications.	
RL2, E4: He uses AI to communicate with parents through translation tools and multilingual family bulletins.	
EM1, E1: I am not a Spanish-speaker so I am using an AI translator to help me communicate with you so I apologize if the grammar is a bit unusual. <i>No hablo español, así que estoy utilizando un traductor de inteligencia artificial para comunicarme con usted, por lo que le pido disculpas si la gramática es un poco inusual.</i>	

Table 2.18. Scaffolder of personalized learning

Excerpts	Code
RL2, E3: He also uses AI to develop instructional materials based on the current English language proficiency and reading/comprehension level of each student based on their assessment scores.	Scaffolder of personalized learning
SSP2, E2: Successmaker's AI program: Percentage of Skill Mastered: 50% Areas for Growth - Since AP Skills not mastered: 7.56 - Use compare and contrast relationships to gain meaning 7.61 - Paraphrase information from text 7.61 - Compare themes 7.63 - Use Greek and Latin roots to determine the meaning of unfamiliar words.	

ETD, E1: I was mentored by a fellow Filipino teacher, who is one of our administrators, on how to use various educational technology apps to differentiate and enrich discussions with ESL learners... Having these sessions made me more “competent” in what I was doing and made me feel more in control.	

Table 2.19. Tailoring lessons that fit learners’ needs

Excerpts	Code
RL1, E1: [Mr. Paradela] uses AI not just to create materials, but to personalize instruction for his students, adjusting lessons based on their language proficiency levels and learning needs.	Tailoring lessons that fit learners’ needs
RL2, E3: He also uses AI to develop instructional materials based on the current English language proficiency and reading/comprehension level of each student based on their assessment scores.	

Table 2.20. Tutoring student learning

Excerpts	Code
MSAI1, E1: Get tutored with AI! You have 30 minutes to do as many as you can. Go to my AI Tutor: 1. Type this prompt: Teach me how to analyze characters in a story 2. Answer the questions	Tutoring student learning
AIT1, E1: Tools Used: AI Tutor Behavioral Notes: No misbehaviors or concerns observed. Strengths & Weaknesses: Strong critical thinking and comprehension skills; express complex ideas well. Strategies: Encourage thematic developments Areas for Improvement: Focus on expanding thematic analysis to new genres. Suggest exploring diverse texts for broader perspectives.	

Table 3.1. Communicative (Re)production - Excerpts, Codes, Sub-Themes, and Themes

Excerpts	Codes	Sub-themes	Themes
<p>LP1, E5: Class Summative Work Writing an objective summary. Project in class: ChatGPT: Using generative AI to "award" best work according to rubric. Show strengths and weaknesses for each submission. Prompt: Randomly assign a number for these submissions (Student A, Student B, etc.). Award the best work based on these details - a theme statement: Step 1: Topic Sentence (Name it + Verb it + Motif it) Step 2: 3-5 key details (Think "beginning, middle, end," also, "emergence, general idea into that poignant Step 3: Conclusion Sentence (Refine the general idea into that poignant Provide the strength and weaknesses for each.</p>	<p>Assessing learner's progress</p>	<p>Teacher authority as assessor, awardor, and communicator of learner progress</p>	<p>Assessing learner's progress and awarding performance</p> <p>Creating fun and engaging lessons through data-driven decision making</p>
<p>GCGS1, E2: Doing various quests really well will also give you a chance to win badges. Badges will give you perks in this classroom such as extra restroom time or getting the chance to choose your own music.</p>	<p>Awarding performance</p>		<p>Using gamification to improve student performance</p>
<p>RL1, E2: [Mr. Paradela] uses and has even found ways to make parent communication easier and more understandable through translation tools, always keeping families informed and involved.</p>	<p>Communicator with parents</p>		<p>Monitoring progress and motivating learners through pleasurable learning</p>
<p>EM1, E1: I am not a Spanish-speaker so I am using an AI translator to help me communicate with you so I apologize if the grammar is a bit unusual. (P3) No hablo español, así que estoy utilizando un traductor de inteligencia artificial para comunicarme con usted, por lo que le pido disculpas si la gramática es un poco inusual.</p>			<p>Partnering with parents and tailoring lessons to fit learner's needs</p>
<p>ETD, E7: Parents in my ESL classroom come from all walks of life and languages. I have Spanish speaking parents, Haitian Creole speaking parents, Thai, Arabic, and Filipino. With the exception of my Filipino parents, I have had difficulties communicating with parents of other linguistic groups, not because of fear but because I do not speak their language. AI has been a great help to translate communications from parents and vice versa. When I use AI to communicate with them, I am transparent that I am using ChatGPT and that personal identifiers are never fed into the app. AI technology has enabled me to automate some classroom practices such as grading, lesson planning, and the construction of levelled worksheets for individualized instruction. It has given me leisure time to do other classroom-relevant tasks such as parent communication and data dives. However, AI use must be guided by my judgement and must always be filtered and checked by me for accuracy.</p>			

<p>RL2, E2: For example, he recently engaged students in a theme-based writing project that used image creation and story frames to develop literacy skills with English language proficiency.</p>	<p>Creator of fun and engaging lessons</p>	<p>Teacher as lesson creator, making data-driven decisions to tutoring student learning</p>	
<p>SSP1, E1: Successmaker's AI program: Student current course level: Far Below Level (8.70) [Student's] current course level is Far below grade level for grade 10. At this time of year, students' course levels should be at or above 10.00.</p>	<p>Data-driven decision maker</p>		
<p>SSP1, E2: Successmaker's AI program: Percentage Skills Mastered: 70% Areas for Growth - Since AP Skills not mastered: 8.65 - Analyze how characters in literature deal with conflict, solve problems, and relate to real-life situations. 8.65 - Use question-and-answer relationships to improve comprehension of texts: Right There questions 8.49 - Identify incorrect shifts in verb tenses</p>			
<p>SSP2, E1: Successmaker's AI program: Student current course level: Far Below Level (7.74) [Student's] current course level is Far below grade level for grade 10. At this time of year, students' course levels should be at or above 10.00.</p>			
<p>ETD, E1: I noticed that students get easily bored after doing a worksheet which they can finish in 20-30 minutes... I struggled early on in finding work for them to do that also corresponded to the standards for the week.</p>			
<p>ETD, E7: There have been software applications that have been using AI software to make content creation for the classroom easier as time went on. Quizizz and Nearpod added the AI features on their platform, as well as AI auto-grading features with Ellii and EdPuzzle. Experimenting with AI automated certain processes such as assessment creation and grading has enabled me to become more "experimental" because it provides me with "leisure time", like using more assessment-as-learning experiences in my instruction with a gamified quiz. In a multicultural classroom, it means that I can also create specific worksheets for specific language groups that usually have no language support options in some apps like Arabic and Thai.</p>			
<p>MSAI1, E1: Get tutored with AI! You have 30 minutes to do as many as you can. Go to my AI Tutor: 1. Type this prompt: Teach me how to analyze characters in a story 2. Answer the questions</p>	<p>Tutoring student learning</p>		

<p>AIT1, E1: Tools Used: AI Tutor Behavioral Notes: No misbehaviors or concerns observed. Strengths & Weaknesses: Strong critical thinking and comprehension skills; express complex ideas well. Strategies: Encourage thematic developments Areas for Improvement: Focus on expanding thematic analysis to new genres. Suggest exploring diverse texts for broader perspectives.</p>			
<p>PP1, E1: Once a week, I set up a pop-up shop where I sell chips, takis, airheads, jolly ranchers, etc. You can only "buy" them using Paradela Pesos. Paradela Pesos can also be used as experience points which can get you classroom perks!</p>	<p>Gamification strategist</p>	<p>Teacher as gamification strategist And classroom designer to improve student performance</p>	
<p>GCGS1, E1: You level up in this class by doing the quests of the day. The main quests must be marked completed in order to level up.</p>			
<p>GCGS1, E2: Doing various quests really well will also give you a chance to win badges. Badges will give you perks in this classroom such as extra restroom time or getting the chance to choose your own music.</p>			
<p>ETD, E6: I was transitioning to become an English and ESL teacher the following school year. I noticed that my ESL students were more receptive and eager to learn than my previous group. I felt that they had higher appreciation for the material, being second language learners in a country where English was a necessity in daily life. I needed to sustain this engagement with the materials and started experimenting with various teaching styles. These strategies became standard in my repertoire and became the source of my gamification of the classroom.</p> <p>The key strategies I took from that summer, the ones that stuck, are what I call the Three Es: Engage, Explain, and Explore. A class session (one-hour and thirty minutes) generally looked like this:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Engage is what I call the first 15–20 minutes: students play a game, we go over objectives, and “get in the zone” using tools like Gimkit, Bloocket, or Quizizz. 2. Explain is the next 30–40 minutes: I teach a mini-lesson using Nearpod. This part often feels like the day’s first quest. If they complete, join in my discussions, do my mini-activities correctly, they earn Paradela Pesos. 3. Explore is the last 30–40 minutes: students apply what they’ve learned through independent work using ESL Library (Ellii), CommonLit, or Edpuzzle. If they score 80% or higher (our “mastery” 			

<p>grade), they get five more Paradela Pesos. Some students earn up to 10 a day and save them for class rewards.</p>			
<p>GCGS1, E1: You level up in this class by doing the quests of the day. The main quests must be marked completed in order to level up.</p>	<p>Improving student performance</p>		
<p>SSP1, E1: Successmaker's AI program: Student current course level: Far Below Level (8.70) [Student's] current course level is Far below grade level for grade 10. At this time of year, students' course levels should be at or above 10.00.</p>			
<p>SSP1, E2: Successmaker's AI program: Percentage Skills Mastered: 70% Areas for Growth - Since AP Skills not mastered: 8.65 - Analyze how characters in literature deal with conflict, solve problems, and relate to real-life situations. 8.65 - Use question-and-answer relationships to improve comprehension of texts: Right There questions 8.49 - Identify incorrect shifts in verb tenses</p>			
<p>SSP2, E1: Successmaker's AI program: Student current course level: Far Below Level (7.74) [Student's] current course level is Far below grade level for grade 10. At this time of year, students' course levels should be at or above 10.00.</p>			
<p>RL1, E3: [Mr. Paradela's colleagues] look up to him as an expert, not only in integrating AI in his instruction but also for his impressive ideas on how to create lessons that are engaging and rigorous for his students.</p>	<p>Classroom designer</p>		
<p>RL2, E5: Mr. Paradela is a team player who collaborates with his coworkers and is regarded as a valuable resource for innovative curriculum and instruction. He is more than willing to share his work and make himself available to advise other teachers on how to use technology to improve student outcomes.</p>			
<p>RL2, E6: The skills and strategies he will learn in the AI Fellows program will enhance his impact on the field, both in ESL education and district-level AI development through future presentations, professional development sessions and curriculum development that will deeply benefit our district and students.</p>			

<p>LP1, E4: Empower - Activity 3 (Student Release Independent Practice) "You do" (:20) Teacher monitors student engagement, answers questions, and ensures differentiation Writing a theme Statement Project in class: ChatGPT: Using generative AI to "award" best work according to rubric. Show strengths and weaknesses for each submission. Prompt: Randomly assign a number for these submissions (Student A, Student B, etc.). Award the best work based on these details - a theme statement: Author's + text + analytical verb + lesson. Provide the strength and weaknesses for each.</p>			
<p>My knowledge for software was greatly enhanced when I transferred to the ESL Department. I was mentored by a fellow Filipino teacher, who is one of our administrators, on how to use various educational technology apps to differentiate and enrich discussions with ESL learners. My experience in the United States could not be shaped without the collaboration of my professional community. Though at times difficult due to cultural differences, reaching out to your community of practice will help you cope with the different realities of the U.S. classroom. The advice, mentorship, and help I received from my U.S. peers allowed me to grow into the current teacher I am today.</p>			
<p>ETD, E5: Toward the end of my first year teaching, AI had been something that really fascinated me. I wanted to see what the potential of AI was after Ms. J taught me what had worked for her. Following her example, I primarily experimented with ChatGPT and MagicSchool.AI to assist in lesson planning, differentiated materials, rubrics, writing feedback, and email responding. Being open to experiment with AI technology allowed me to develop new tools and strategies that have helped my teaching practice. It functioned as a kind of "teacher assistant" that allows me to easily reach teaching goals.</p>			
<p>LP1, E2: Inspire - Activity 1 (Direct Instruction) "I do" (:20) Teacher models lesson Students do 20 minutes of Khan Academy: - Finding Theme and Central Ideal - Inferences - Citing Textual Evidences</p>	<p>Learning facilitator</p>	<p>Teacher as motivator, monitoring learner's progress through a pleasurable learning experience</p>	
<p>LP1, E3: Challenge - Activity 2 (Student Demonstrations & Connections) "We do" (:20) Teacher monitors student engagement/facilitates collaborations. Students do MagicSchool.AI / AI tutor for 20 minutes: Prompt: Teach me how to find the components of an Objective Summary</p>			
<p>ETD, E2: I wanted to see what the potential of AI was after Ms. J taught me what had worked for her... I followed her best practices and began to experiment with the technology... Associating with her enabled me to be more confident in my instruction and has made me feel more "in</p>			

control”insofar as content is concerned.			
<p>ETD, E1: I communicated this struggle in passing to my immediate department head and fellow teachers... They sent me to observe teachers and their best practices and to talk to them informally and “compare notes”.... During Professional Learning Community (PLC) Sessions, they would also keep me updated with newer technological trends and best practices.</p>			
<p>ETD, E8: Having worked with AI technology and gamified practices in the classroom, and for all that it can seem to do, it has its limitations. Having an AI teaching assistant is quite useful. But its use, as I have experienced it, can never replace key processes in the classroom. While AI can generate content, it can hallucinate and give false information. The same goes for gamification techniques. Gamified techniques stimulate and engage pique interest but only to serve inquiry, attention, and analysis but only for short-periods of time. As the teacher, I am irreplaceable in the teaching-learning processes. Despite having the tools at my disposal, their effectiveness has to filter through my judgement and experience. I am a content specialist. I facilitate learning. Technology is wonderful but they do not replace me because they do not direct my students to clear goals in the classroom.</p>			
<p>LP1, E4: Empower - Activity 3 (Student Release Independent Practice) “You do” (:20) Teacher monitors student engagement, answers questions, and ensures differentiation Writing a theme Statement Project in class: ChatGPT: Using generative AI to “award” best work according to rubric. Show strengths and weaknesses for each submission. Prompt: Randomly assign a number for these submissions (Student A, Student B, etc.). Award the best work based on these details - a theme statement: Author’s + text + analytical verb + lesson. Provide the strength and weaknesses for each.</p>	Monitoring learner’s progress		
<p>PP1, E1: Once a week, I set up a pop-up shop where I sell chips, takis, airheads, jolly ranchers, etc. You can only “buy” them using Paradela Pesos. Paradela Pesos can also be used as experience points which can get you classroom perks!</p>	Motivator towards a pleasurable learning experience		
<p>GCGS1, E3: Once you reach level 5 and 10, you will receive a digital achievement badge. The level 5 achievement badge enables you to play your own preferred music during working period and an assignment pass (usable in the future) perfect score in one output</p>			

<p>RL1, E2: [Mr. Paradela] uses and has even found ways to make parent communication easier and more understandable through translation tools, always keeping families informed and involved.</p>	<p>Partnering with parents in the learning process</p>	<p>Teacher partnering with parents in scaffolding and tailoring the learning process</p>	
<p>RL2, E1: Mr. Paradela actively uses AI in his classroom as a teaching tool and parent outreach and communications.</p>			
<p>RL2, E4: He uses AI to communicate with parents through translation tools and multilingual family bulletins.</p>			
<p>EM1, E1: I am not a Spanish-speaker so I am using an AI translator to help me communicate with you so I apologize if the grammar is a bit unusual.</p> <p><i>No hablo español, así que estoy utilizando un traductor de inteligencia artificial para comunicarme con usted, por lo que le pido disculpas si la gramática es un poco inusual.</i></p>			
<p>ETD, E1: I was mentored by a fellow Filipino teacher, who is one of our administrators, on how to use various educational technology apps to differentiate and enrich discussions with ESL learners... Having these sessions made me more "competent" in what I was doing and made me feel more in control.</p>			
<p>RL2, E3: He also uses AI to develop instructional materials based on the current English language proficiency and reading/comprehension level of each student based on their assessment scores.</p>	<p>Scaffolder of personalized learning</p>		
<p>SSP2, E2: Successmaker's AI program: Percentage of Skill Mastered: 50% Areas for Growth - Since AP Skills not mastered: 7.56 - Use compare and contrast relationships to gain meaning 7.61 - Paraphrase information from text 7.61 - Compare themes 7.63 - Use Greek and Latin roots to determine the meaning of unfamiliar words.</p>			
<p>RL1, E1: [Mr. Paradela] uses AI not just to create materials, but to personalize instruction for his students, adjusting lessons based on their language proficiency levels and learning needs.</p>	<p>Tailoring lessons that fit learners' needs</p>		
<p>RL2, E3: He also uses AI to develop instructional materials based on the current English language proficiency and reading/comprehension level of each student based on their assessment scores.</p>			

CHAPTER V

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter discusses the results of my analysis and reflection with the naturally-occurring data. This study seeks to look into the communicative (re)production teacher as authority and identity in GAI-infused and gamified Multicultural ESL Classroom. I will present the results and discussion into two parts. The first part seeks to answer the question: *How has generative AI in a multicultural classroom threatened teachers' authority?* The second part answers the question: *How does GAI and gamification integration in communicative practices (re)produce teacher authority in a multicultural classroom?*

When Generative AI Threatens the Teacher's Authority

An analysis of the naturally-occurring data, particularly that of my talker's diary entries on my encounters with generative AI, I was able to draw out four key areas as to how generative AI has threatened my teacher authority. They are:

- (1) threatening self-image as a content expert;
- (2) tendency to outsource thinking to GAI;
- (3) challenging traditional teacher roles; and
- (4) weakening teacher authority.

Threatening self-image as content expert

TDAIT, E1

During my first year in the American classroom, generative AI was still at its infancy, but it had already slowly started to appear in my classroom.

Being an English teacher, writing assignments is a common strategy in my repertoire. I was assigned a writing assignment on character analysis. There was this student who submitted an essay under ten minutes into the writing assignment - a full essay in under ten minutes. As I read through the essay, I noted how refined it was - too refined for the student who submitted it. I called the student and asked him to retell his analysis to me in his own words. He smirked and said that I could just read his essay. I told him that his content was AI-generated and that this was against my policy. He shrugged and just went back to his seat.

TDAIT, E4

GAI's instant access to information making my explanations seem less essential shows itself in some interactions I have with students. Given that it takes time for me to process and synthesize information upon a student question, the rapidity by which GAI instantly produces answers has made me realize that my presence has become more non-central.

TDAIT, E6

At first, I felt that GAI was replacing me as the primary source of knowledge in the classroom. I wanted to personally do away with GAI altogether in the classroom, but seeing students use it more and more meant that I should find ways to work with it.

TDAIT, E7

GAI made me feel that I had to prove my worth in the classroom as an authority by making me feel "dumber." Though it presented opportunities for me to use its personalization aspects to teach targeted skills to specific students, which I myself find too tedious or time-consuming to do.

My image of myself as a teacher is shaped by my expertise. Being a professional, I see my ability to deliver content effectively as a key asset. However, when GAI started to enter my classroom, my self-concept as the content expert was threatened. The use of AI has not only proliferated among teachers. Students have also been using AI a lot to answer their school work. I have observed that students have been using AI to answer the homework other teachers assign in my class.

I feel that I am part of an interesting moment in the development of education. I am teaching, as it were, at the crux where the nature of teacher authority in the age of AI is shifting and shifting fast. Teachers in the past saw themselves as wellsprings of

authority and content knowledge. Because they had this knowledge, they tried to find creative ways to teach, discuss, or transfer this knowledge to students.

The age of AI has shifted teacher authority, it has also shaken my self-identity. In the past, the teacher was seen as the authority. But now, with GAI, content is easily accessible. It can be generated in real time. It can correct grammar, write essays, explain lessons, and more. In a way, the past notion that the teacher is the authority figure and the wellspring of knowledge is now challenged in the classroom. I, at least, have to redefine and recontextualize how I look at myself as a teacher in relation to AI technologies. I have to try and be relevant to the times. Instead of seeing myself as the central point where authority and insights start, I now believe the emphasis should be placed on individual learning experiences mediated by GAI technology. The teacher as an authority becomes someone who facilitates and creatively creates strategies to assess student learning and to transfer knowledge contextually to individual learners based on data generated by GAI-infused technologies.

Tendency to outsource thinking to GAI

TDAIT, E2

There have been more incidents, I remember, where students would use the AI features in some applications that they have on their phones (such as Snapchat) to answer questions in worksheets. I recall one student, who was very close to me, holding his phone over a sheet of math homework to get the answer through AI. Seeing me, he laughed and said that I should be “cool.” I was personally frustrated and berated him, telling him that GAI should not be used in such a way.

He put away his phone, as well as his math homework, and proceeded with the day.

TDAIT, E4

GAI’s instant access to information making my explanations seem less essential shows itself in some interactions I have with students. Given that it takes time for me to process and synthesize

information upon a student question, the rapidity by which GAI instantly produces answers has made me realize that my presence has become more non-central.

TDAIT, E11

I recall a student laughing at me when she saw that I was using ChatGPT, and she said, “Why are you using ChatGPT? You’re not allowed to use ChatGPT. You’re supposed to be a teacher,” and she laughed. I remember explicitly that I told her that, yes, I am using ChatGPT, but watch this - so I started using ChatGPT as a tool to prompt discussions, and we started talking about an idea that we synthesized through ChatGPT, and we talked about it in the classroom - the synthesized idea - whether or not we agreed.

The current school environment that I am in has really positive attitudes toward technology. The way they look at technology is that it is something useful, which I agree with. But without a formal guideline or ethical framework - like an standardized honor code system backed up by the county itself and by the school system on how we should react to AI cheating, I think there is no clear definition of what constitutes cheating and what the consequences for cheating are. Students outsource critical thinking abilities to the GAI platforms to get away from higher order thinking tasks. This has greatly challenged my authority as the content leader in the classroom because it disrupts the social order of the classroom to begin with.

Challenging traditional teacher roles

TDAIT, E6

At first, I felt that GAI was replacing me as the primary source of knowledge in the classroom. I wanted to personally do away with GAI altogether in the classroom, but seeing students use it more and more meant that I should find ways to work with it.

I realized that I could not possibly compete with GAI as the fountainhead of knowledge. So I started reevaluating my authority until I realized that while GAI is teeming with “knowledge,” ensuring that the correct and relevant kind of knowledge is delivered was something else. My professional judgement was needed to ensure that each student engaged with the relevant kind of knowledge to bridge learning gaps. I started focusing on curating and scaffolding rather than trying to outsmart the machine

TDAIT, E8

The presence of GAI in my multicultural classroom challenged me early on to try and find means and ways to subsume it within my practice because I saw how AI had the capacity to be very disruptive in my classroom, but at the same time I know that as a teacher, I could use, like a lot of

things, what AI has to offer to streamline and simplify my workload. So it was a tension, really, on my part to try and subsume artificial intelligence within my practice early on.

TDAIT, E10

At first, I felt my authority shaken and challenged because I knew that I could never outperform GAI in terms of speed, content generation, or language translation for multilingual learners. I felt that what made me a unique teacher was challenged by these innovative skills that AI has.

I feel that my place in the classroom has been increasingly encroached upon. My traditional roles as assessor, awardor, and content delivery have had to adjust to accommodate the new digital landscape where GAI is increasingly becoming prominent. With these tensions happening in my classroom, I am re-imagining my role in the classroom not as the origin of knowledge but as its contextualizer. With the advent of educational technologies like SuccessMaker and Khan Academy, which already have the content and are able not only to effectively deliver these lessons but level it according to individual needs, I have had to shift the way of seeing myself as someone who delivers and contextualizes these technologies for individual needs. The data cannot interpret itself. There is a requirement for creativity in using the insights from the data and finding technologies that are relevant, timely, and context-based for each learner.

Weakening teacher authority

TDAIT, E2

There have been more incidents, I remember, where students would use the AI features in some applications that they have on their phones (such as Snapchat) to answer questions in worksheets. I recall one student, who was very close to me, holding his phone over a sheet of math homework to get the answer through AI. Seeing me, he laughed and said that I should be "cool." I was personally frustrated and berated him, telling him that GAI should not be used in such a way.

He put away his phone, as well as his math homework, and proceeded with the day.

This incident highlights the main problem with GAI and teacher authority in the classroom: teacher authority, especially as the controller of meaningful experiences in the classroom and the content expert, is eroded and disrupted. This incident presented for me a concrete shift in the classroom environment, that GAI has affected how teacher authority is viewed by the students.

TDAIT, E3

GAI challenged the way I did assessment because I cannot truly measure or assess the actual transfer of learning. I felt that GAI had challenged my notion of assessment and that I had to create new criteria and frameworks to assess student learning.

TDAIT, E9

Personally, GAI made me feel replaced as a teacher in the classroom because, more and more, I've noticed that the features that AI has are indeed becoming very disruptive. For example, I remember when the AI tutor became a thing and I did not know how to place myself in relation to the AI tutor. Because if the AI platform can tutor students and direct them to the correct information, what does that mean for me as a teacher? This particular event triggered a feeling of fear and dread of being replaced because education is the only thing I felt I knew to do. I have been a teacher for a very long time and I love it, but with the arrival of this kind of technology that disrupts the way I look at things and the way I do things, it was scary and frankly difficult. So I had to find means and ways to try and navigate my identity and authority where this could be a norm in the classroom, and it increasingly is becoming a norm in the classroom - this integration of GAI technology.

There was this one notable experience I had with a student whom I reprimanded for cheating in his Math class with Snapchat's generative AI during free period. He laughed at me and said to the effect: "Don't worry, Mr. Paradela, everyone's doing it. As long as we turn in our work, it's fine. Be cool." The emotions that honestly surfaced when the student told me to be cool were mixed. I was happy because I was seen as the cool teacher - that I was not seen as a narc - and they had established that kind of rapport and trust with me. But at the same time, it annoyed me because I have always seen myself as someone who does not care if I were cool because my job as a teacher is to teach.

When they said that I should be cool about them cheating, it made me question if I was still being an effective authority figure. I felt that my authority had been whittled away because I was a cool teacher. I am trying to navigate how I could be most effective. I

have a relationship with the students. I have established high rapport with them, but I want that rapport to be the reason they respect me—not just personally, but also professionally. The way I look at my authority as a teacher in the Philippines is as the guardian of knowledge, so to say. How students in the United States of America look at and perceive authority is radically different. I think it is more of a deeper cultural misalignment. It is the students' perception of me being fairly cool - to borrow their term - that made it so that they would open up with cheating on me.

My teacher authority, as I see it, has been greatly weakened. It is not about control anymore, because control has become almost impossible with generative AI. Rather, teacher authority has transformed from control to ethical dialogue with the students by trusting the students to make good choices, but at the same time, always reminding them of what the good choices are and always reminding them of the importance of maintaining ethical standards not as an imposition, but rather as somewhat of a cost-benefit dialogue between the teacher as an authority figure and the student learning about these things in the age of generative AI.

Becoming a GAI and Gamification-integrated teacher

In my first year at Pine City High School, my classroom included students with various IEPs and English Learner (EL) plans, each with unique needs.

I wanted to try something new, something that would help me support them more effectively and efficiently. The use of AI tools came from a genuine desire to simplify my workload and individualize instruction especially because I had so many students in my U.S. classroom, all with different needs and support requirements. In my ESL

classroom, the demands that pushed me to explore AI as a tool were rooted in the diversity of my students' English proficiency levels. Many of them belonged to different categories in the WIDA levels, so I had to adjust and level my instruction and materials accordingly.

I cautiously decided to start making use of Generative AI to help me in planning. Aware of how it threatened my authority in the classroom, I wanted to navigate the tension and integrate this perceived threat into something that would work for me in enhancing my authority and instruction rather than be wary and afraid of its existence in the classroom. Rather than ignoring GAI, I decided to integrate it and subsume it into my repertoire.

It was when I started using GAI tools that I found that I realized its potential in the creation of leveled, differentiated, and leveled materials for multicultural students with varying English skills. For example, if we were analyzing Haruki Murakami's *The Seventh Man*, I could create different versions of the same worksheet based on WIDA levels. I experimented with prompting and realized that if I were very specific with what I wanted, it would give me the content that I really wanted. I even asked AI to help me develop prompts.

Chatbots such as ChatGPT and Gemini specifically, had a significant impact on my lesson planning and instructional decision-making. It made planning less time-consuming and more productive. Using platforms like Quizizz, I created engaging games and quizzes based on AI-generated content. There were moments when AI-supported materials noticeably improved student engagement and comprehension

especially through formative assessments. For example, one time we were studying tone words, and I asked ChatGPT to make example sentences that 7th- and 8th- grade students could understand. Students were engaged, and their understanding improved significantly.

What used to take me 30 minutes to an hour, now takes just 30 seconds and that frees up more time for other important tasks or even rest. For example, one time we were studying tone words, and I asked ChatGPT to make example sentences that 7th- and 8th- grade students could understand. Students were engaged, and their understanding improved significantly. Because generative AI is able to help streamline, individualize lessons, and take the burden of instructional design and do adaptive learning for me, I feel more in control and more at ease thinking about my instruction being personalized, standard-based, and relevant. Being in the United States gave me the openness and opportunity to adopt AI tools is something I did not think I could do in the Philippines due to many factors: a key is the lack of digital access and infrastructure. Whereas my experience in the United States has shown that the material resources and tech support allowed me to explore and experiment in ways I never imagined before. It has personally stirred a slight irritation at the digital divide whereby groups of students in the global north (i.e. United States) are afforded this opportunity and access but not my fellow Filipinos.

Nonetheless, the willingness to experiment with GAI showed me a side of myself that is actually pragmatic - focused not on what's popular, but on what works. From being threatened, I noticed myself becoming an integrator. At the end of the day, the most important question is always: Does this help my students? This served as the

catalyst in integrating GAI into my practice and how it (re)produces identity as the teacher as the authority in the classroom.

(Re)production of the teacher's authority by Generative AI and Gamification

In this part , I will present the main themes that emerged in this study, followed by the sub-themes under each theme, and then the codes with excerpts from the naturally occurring data. The themes are as follows:

- (1) Creating fun and engaging lessons through data-driven decision making
- (2) Monitoring progress and motivating learners through pleasurable learning
- (3) Using gamification to improve student performance
- (4) Partnering with parents and tailoring lessons to fit learners' needs
- (5) Assessing learners' progress and awarding performance

Various screenshots from naturally-occurring data will also be presented to support and develop each discussion. Being autoethnographic, each analysis integrates reflexivity that further provides context.

Creating fun and engaging lessons through data-driven decision making

Teacher as lesson creator, making data-drive decisions to tutoring student learning

The following cluster of sub-themes demonstrates how teacher authority is (re)produced through the teacher's role as a data-informed instructional engineer. The codes reveal how, through the integration of generative AI platforms such as

SuccessMaker (SSP1, E1) and MagicSchool.AI's tutor function (MSAI1,E1) shifts the identity of the teacher from a one-size-fits-all lesson planner to a precise and personalized educator.

Mediated by GAI technology, and communicating with it, the teacher develops materials that directly addresses key areas for growth. Likewise, through interaction with an GAI platform, the teacher can direct students to specialized GAI tutors by means of specific prompts such as what is found in MSAI1, E1: Teach me how to analyze characters in a story. Teacher authority is (re)produced as an expert who diagnoses learning gaps through highly-specified data points, who can also prescribe the right interventions by means of technological tools to address them.

From resisting to engaging

You can always try to condition yourself for what is to come, they said, but you can never fully fathom a situation until you have been there. This short quip encapsulates my experience of my first year teaching in the United States.

There were two things that I particularly found challenging: first is on student attitude and behavior; second, on classroom procedures.

A great majority of students in my classes seemed to me indifferent to my instruction. I noted how engaging them to care about learning was really a challenge. Since my classroom standards as an English teacher required reading from both literary and informational texts, it was really difficult to get them to read. Insofar as resources are concerned, I was very happy with the fact that all my students are given a

chromebook and access to special applications such as Common Lit or EasyBridge where our electronic textbook can be found.

Furthermore, there are some cultural habits that students have that as a Filipino I perceived as quite offensive but are actually not. There was this one episode in my first year teaching that a student suddenly opened the door without knocking as I was in the middle of instruction. I looked at him and he likewise looked at me. He then pointed at me and did the “come here” gesture with his extended index figure. Where I grew up, pointing at someone (and especially an adult) is considered to be very disrespectful. Annoyed, I raised my voice and said to him not to do it again. Perplexed, he said “okay”. I could also see how the other students were perplexed with what I just did. It was then that I realized that that was considered normal. Another is on how outspoken they are. They have a habit of speaking what is on their minds and they could be sometimes challenging when they blurt out what was in their mind bluntly. I could say that this cultural gap made it difficult for me to forge connections and communicate effectively. Though I spoke English, there was something missing - there was something beyond the element of spoken language that played a huge factor. Communication is not just a spoken thing, there was “text in the subtext”, things communicated that were not only communicated by mere words but I felt unable to fully comprehend.

The biggest threat I encountered, however, is the low initial engagement with the academic content. My students’ indifference to reading texts created resistance that greatly undermined my influence. My previous practice as an English teacher in the Philippines always started with a quick motivational activity followed by a short lecture that could take around 20 minutes before the main task of the day. My expectation was

for the students to listen to the short lecture. This approach in classes in the United States however, did not find much success. Some students would complain about my 20-minute lectures because they were too long and usually asserted that I could just proceed with the text or work of the day. Most, it felt to me, also did not like my motivational task (which was journaling based on writing prompts) and despite going around telling them to write following the rubrics posted on the board, many would not follow it.

Cellphone use and curbing it is the most taxing enterprise. My students are always on their phones and asking them to put it away takes time and effort because they do not want to put it away. Confiscating it is not an option because of the liabilities one can have should I damage their property. I had to find a way to engage students. This led me to explore gamification as a teaching strategy after hearing about it from a fellow teacher.

I realized my ESL students were more eager to learn came from seeing just how motivated they were. Most of them, being English learners, had a strong desire to succeed. I remember asking a student why they had failed English I, and they said it was hard for them to understand the lessons - but they still really wanted to learn. They wanted to read and speak English because they hoped to go to college in the U.S. and eventually land a good job. That was my so-called “aha” moment. I noted that these students were not just learning English for school and that they were learning it for life in this county. I thought if I can tap into that motivation, I can be more successful in the classroom. I started designing lessons that engage them and make them more receptive to learning.

Knowing that my students use English everyday shaped how I plan and teach. I always aim to make lessons relevant to their daily lives at school. For example, I structure quizzes around academic vocabulary they might encounter in other subjects like Biology, Math, Social Studies, or English - especially with subjects with standardized testing. I also include what I call “free topics” - topics or activities not explicitly required by the curriculum, but they were areas that I think had great value. One of these activities I did, toward the end of the second semester, focused on careers in STEM. It gave my bilingual students a glimpse into what they could pursue after high school. One student appreciated the activity and told me that she had plans to try out some of the careers I placed onto the sheet.

What really helped me make my content more meaningful was learning about my students’ lives outside the classroom. That ongoing dialogue between us was key for it provided me with perspectives to better address the needs of each student. It also afforded me with further perspective about my own privilege and my place in relation to them. During independent work, I would visit each table and strike up a conversation and ask how they were. Many of my students in grades 10–12 work. One student worked at a flea market and needed to negotiate and advocate for herself in English. Another student’s father owned a convenience store. He came from Yemen, so I gave him small talk phrases to help him connect with customers and he actually used them. Personalizing activities based on their real experiences made a big difference. In my gamified classroom, these small real-world tasks became “challenges” with rewards. For instance, if a student could memorize five small talk phrases, they’d earn 10 Parabela Pesos to exchange for perks or prizes later on.

Creating an engaging classroom culture with varied groups of students, from different language groups and cultures requires openness and constant configuration of procedures through feedback. I found that the most effective classroom strategy was gamification — turning classroom tasks into game-like experiences. Games are cross-cultural and it extends language boundaries. When students complete tasks, they earn rewards which I Paradela Pesos, which they can trade for classroom perks. This approach made the classroom feel more like a game and less like a pressure cooker. It relaxed the students and gave them confidence. For example, standardized testing environments can make ESL students panic and they think *I can't understand English, so I'm going to fail*. That defeatist mindset kills engagement especially that there are periods that we would have to teach to the test. However with gamification, I reframed lessons as “quests”, which gave students room to experiment and take risks. This allowed me to motivate them to lower their affective filters and resistance towards learning academic vocabulary and English in general.

Creator of fun and engaging lessons

RL2, E2

For example, [Mr. Paradela] recently engaged students in a theme-based writing project that used image creation and story frames to develop literacy skills with English language proficiency.

Finding engaging activities is one of the most difficult parts of my job. Learning with a more experienced peer in the person of Ms. V. was a valuable experience. She would learn from me and I from her, sharing best practices to keep the classroom engaging. Using platforms like Quizizz, I created engaging games and quizzes based on AI-generated content. These tools have significantly improved student engagement especially for English learners since Quizizz is interactive and has game-like elements

which students enjoy. SuccessMaker, likewise, is engaging because no two users have the same experience; it is adaptive, based on individual needs. I have noted that collaboration also increases due to the platform interface since students use GIFs, pictures, and videos to express their answers on Nearpod.

Figure 1.

Image generated with GAI for a writing project.

Figure 2

A speaking task utilizing Canva's AI image creator and students collaborating in-real time through Nearpod (n.d.).

Gamified techniques stimulate and engage pique interest but only to serve inquiry, attention, and analysis but only for short-periods of time. I have noticed that

students are excited for the first 15 to 30 minutes when playing games. While it is fun, I remind students that the concepts are what matter. Now, I define effective teaching as engaging students while delivering content in a way that is relevant to their daily lives. When I integrate gamification and technology into instruction, I see how engagement drives learning. Gamification and technology help communicate standards in engaging ways and provide immediate feedback.

Figure 3

A “Quest” slide for my Beginning of the Year Diagnostic test.

Figure 4

A slide of my “instruction board” for the first day of school on how my classroom tasks and procedures look like.

Creating an engaging classroom culture with varied groups of students, from different language groups and cultures, requires openness and constant configuration of

procedures through feedback. Gamification has been transformative not just for my students, but for me as a teacher. It has made my instructional process more data-driven and engaging thanks to the assistance of gaming tools that communicate feedback in real time.

Data-driven decision maker

SSP1, E1

Successmaker's AI program:

Student current course level: Far Below Level (8.70)

[Student's] current course level is Far below grade level for grade 10. At this time of year, students' course levels should be at or above 10.00.

Generative AI tools have transformed my teaching as they provided real-time feedback on student understanding and served both formative and summative assessment purposes. I know this because of the feedback I got from digitally mediated AI-infused apps such as Successmaker. Now, with AI-infused educational technologies, gamified platforms have already started bringing in analytics that communicate to me - the teacher- how effective instruction has been. It has made my instructional process more data-driven and engaging thanks to the assistance of gaming tools that communicate feedback in real time. This data communicates to me whether my processes are still effective or if it is time for me to shift them to fit the context.

Platforms like Successmaker and Quizizz provide immediate analytics on student performance and help me determine whether it is time to move on to the next lesson or whether I need to reinforce certain concepts. Having technology that provides me with real-time communication through grade and standard feedback allows for real-time

shifts in instruction and a more personalized direction for tasks in the classroom. With these tools, I can drill down to individual student performance and provide timely reinforcements based on data. This dynamic interplay between student performance, instructional adaptation, and data analysis allows for a more responsive and differentiated learning experience.

SSP1, E2

Successmaker's AI program:

Percentage Skills Mastered: 70%

Areas for Growth - Since AP

Skills not mastered:

8.65 - Analyze how characters in literature deal with conflict, solve problems, and relate to real-life situations.

8.65 - Use question-and-answer relationships to improve comprehension of texts: Right There questions

8.49 - Identify incorrect shifts in verb tenses

Furthermore, AI helps process data chunks to implement interventions faster and in real-time, delivering bite-sized insights that are fast and easy to understand. This enables me to design instruction that is more targeted, effective, and data-driven. Having their own diagnostic tools with an easy interface, I noticed how the various AI-infused educational and software tools have a feature wherein they can give me a report of each student's performance in real time. It provides me with detailed, data-based feedback on how my students are doing standard-wise in real time. That data was incredibly helpful because he was actually in ninth grade. With real-time data, I can reinforce what they know and help them grow.

With GAI-infused platforms, the ability to get assessment in real-time transforms the nature of assessment to become an informational tool that allows me to reevaluate and shift best practices away from ineffective ones. Based on GAI-infused data, I realized that most students did not understand how character interactions advanced the plot and that concept was frequently missed. Having engaging AI-infused platforms that provide me with real-time analytics and do the grading for me has allowed me to focus on instruction and face-to-face interaction, which is necessary for ESL instruction. It has allowed me to plan ahead, create more targeted experiences, and communicate to students with numbers.

My teaching is now more data-driven and grounded in the needs of my students, rather than simply following a standard or pacing guide. Generative AI has molded me into becoming a fully data-driven, digitally literate ESL teacher. Through AI-infused applications, which have the ability to track my students' progress in real time, standard-wise, I am able to shift practices based on communicated feedback and provide more specialized support to individual students. Having this data on hand has enabled me to effectively differentiate and individualize my teaching method to help individual students attain competency with the standards. AI has molded me into becoming a fully data-driven, digitally literate ESL teacher. Having this data on-hand will enable teachers to effectively differentiate and individualize teaching methods to help individual students attain competency with the standards.

Figure 5.

Successmaker Reading (Savass Learning Company, n.d) and its proprietary GAI function showing the current reading development skill of a student. The student is an ESL Newcomer 10th grade student. They started with a score of 8.25 (8th grade reading level) at the start of the semester and grew by 0.42 with continued sustained practice. Successmaker shows immediate feedback after the practice session.

Tutoring student learning

MSAI1, E1

Get tutored with AI! You have 30 minutes to do as many as you can.
Go to my AI Tutor: 1. Type this prompt: Teach me how to analyze characters in a story 2. Answer the questions

AIT1, E1

Tools Used: AI Tutor Behavioral Notes:

No misbehaviors or concerns observed.

Strengths & Weaknesses: Strong critical thinking and comprehension skills; express complex ideas well.

Strategies: Encourage thematic developments

Areas for Improvement: Focus on expanding thematic analysis to new genres. Suggest exploring diverse texts for broader perspectives.

I primarily experimented with ChatGPT, Google Gemini, and MagicSchool.AI to assist in lesson planning, differentiated materials, rubrics, writing feedback, email responding, and more recently - AI tutoring. My district currently is starting to grant access to personalized AI tutors as of the writing of this work such as in MagicSchool.AI. Personalized AI tutoring has been linked to improved test scores and academic performance, highlighting the potential of AI to enhance student learning. MagicSchool.ai's "AI Tutor" function. Generative AI has become my "co-teacher", I use it to reinforce "Raina" to help me see students' thought processes, skills, and content mastery and "co-teach" the class with me.

GAI-infused platforms, such as Quizizz, allows me to do Mastery Peak, wherein students are continually practicing a question or skill until the platform is convinced that the student has understood it. It gamifies mastery, and students compete to reach the top.

Figure 6-7.

MagicSchool.ai's "AI Tutor" function. Generative AI has become my "co-teacher", I use it to reinforce learning outcomes. Raina, MagicSchool's AI tutor bot, help me see students' thought processes, skills, and content mastery and "co-teach" the class with me.

Through GAI-infused applications, which have the ability to track my students' progress in real time, standard-wise, I am able to shift practices based on communicated feedback and provide more specialized support to individual students. However, when the student asked me about it, I was able to individually re-teach the topic, and this moment really showed one of the dangers or pitfalls of modern technology. When the student asked me about it, I was able to individually re-teach the topic. If not, they go back, interact with the platform, and try again until they reach

mastery. I also show students gains or losses and tell them what to do to improve their performance based on the data.

Monitoring progress and motivating learners through pleasurable learning

Teacher as motivator, monitoring learners' progress through a pleasurable learning experience.

This sub-theme shows how teacher authority is (re)produced in the person of the teacher as an active facilitator and curator of engagement and experiences in the classroom who makes use of GAI and gamification to track student engagement with the curriculum and the materials. The teacher's identity shifts from disciplinarian into an authority who generates learning motivation by means of creating an enjoyable learning environment.

Through the teacher's active monitoring of student engagement and facilitation of students to work independently through their interactions with generative AI tools (LP1,E3;E4), the teacher's authority is maintained through constant observation and strategic observation. The teacher, likewise, is the principal person to design and oversee the entire ESL classroom system ensuring that despite "fun" games being played, everything is still congruent in achieving standard-based goals.

Becoming a motivator

The thing that greatly impressed me in the United States classroom was its availability of resources. This was on a scale that I personally have not expected nor

have dreamed of in the Philippine classroom. As a teacher, I had access to vast libraries and software tools that could help me do my work - EdPuzzle, Canvas, Nearpod, CommonLit - and of course, AI-technologies and applications such as ChatGPT and MagicSchool.AI. The issue was, however, that I did not know how to use them. My students have started using GAI in the classroom for their own purposes, which were oftentimes not in accordance with how I wanted them to use GAI.

Threatened, I had to actively assert my role as the filter and decision maker in the classroom or risk AI and technology becoming the only authority in the classroom - becoming in effect a machine-first classroom than human-centered. I was lucky, because the existence of Professional Learning Communities (PLCs), formal sessions where we would gather to talk about important updates from the county, allowed for opportunities where more seasoned teachers in the department would help the newer teachers to better their teaching styles. It was also a norm that teachers helped each other out by sharing their resources and operating them freely. As mentioned, I felt like I was a fish out of water and was personally overwhelmed by the many tools at my disposal. Overwhelmed, I then reached out to my classroom neighbor, Ms. J., who when finding me overwhelmed offered to mentor me to use various classroom applications by showing me how she works with them. She encouraged me to try her techniques if it worked out for me and give her feedback. She also helped me connect with the other teachers in my department who in turn helped me to use the resources at my disposal effectively. They taught me how to use technology such as CommonLit to differentiate instruction to suit the various learning needs in the classroom.

My interaction with peers and mentors have taught me that teaching and learning requires the human element. While technology can certainly reinforce and help streamline and automate processes, it can never replace human creativity. Technology has made me realize that technology should serve the human, and not the other way around. For example, AI tools are prone to error or hallucinations and can phrase these as if they are factual. In my practice, even when AI is used to generate content, it will always be filtered in the light of my experience and content specialty.

The way I determine traditional methods versus when to use technology is largely based on how I “read” the situation. Some standards, such as finding figurative language and word meaning, can be best taught with AI assistance. However, some standards like poetry analysis and tasks that require higher levels within Bloom’s Taxonomy, I shift towards traditional paper and pen practices. My reason for this is because the screen is overstimulating, and so is pretending it to be a “game”, students would have a hard time narrowing in. These lessons require attention to detail and a calm and collected disposition, and so I rule technology out. I call these “lock-in standards” and the students usually do not like them though the results say otherwise.

ETD, E8

Having worked with AI technology and gamified practices in the classroom, and for all that it can seem to do, it has its limitations. Having an AI teaching assistant is quite useful. But its use, as I have experienced it, can never replace key processes in the classroom. While AI can generate content, it can hallucinate and give false information. The same goes for gamification techniques. Gamified techniques stimulate and engage pique interest but only to serve inquiry, attention, and analysis but only for short-periods of time. As the teacher, I am irreplaceable in the teaching-learning processes. Despite having the tools at my disposal, their effectiveness has to filter through my judgement and experience. I am a content specialist. I facilitate learning. Technology is wonderful but they do not replace me because they do not direct my students to clear goals in the classroom.

The human element can be best described as the teacher functioning as judge - as the teacher you are the final say of everything that will be communicated to and delivered in the teaching-learning process. AI spews materials, it does not judge. The human element is the most important element even in AI content creation.

I can recall a moment when technology could not meet a student's need, but a personal interaction did. It was one of my classes where I used differentiated instruction, and I noticed that AI was not giving what I really wanted, especially in teaching the standard I intended. The student became confused, and I did not realize that the AI platform had made a mistake. I had not reviewed it as thoroughly as I should have. However, when the student asked me about it, I was able to individually re-teach the topic, and this moment really showed one of the dangers or pitfalls of modern technology. Technology gives us content, but often, it just regurgitates information and dumps content. What is needed sometimes is personal interaction.

I have also noticed this in my classroom when we use Nearpod, which blends digital learning with classroom instruction. My students feed off the back-and-forth interaction we have in class. While technology is great for delivering content, it still requires a human element to make learning truly effective. Based on what I have experienced, AI can only take us so far. To deeply engage students, human connection is essential.

What students gain from direct human connection, something no tool or AI could replicate, is that sense of being seen and understood. As human beings, we communicate not only with what we say but also with what we do not say. Students pick

up on that. In my classroom, I have noticed that when I personalize my interaction with students, I do not just deliver content; I also learn about their lives. Machines do not make eye contact. Machines cannot give you a nod or a high five. These little things actually make teaching and learning effective.

Learning facilitator

LP1, E2

Inspire - Activity 1 (Direct Instruction) "I do" (:20) Teacher models lesson Students do 20 minutes of Khan Academy: - Finding Theme and Central Ideal - Inferences - Citing Textual Evidences

LP1, E3

Challenge - Activity 2 (Student Demonstrations & Connections) "We do" (:20) Teacher monitors student engagement/facilitates collaborations. Students do MagicSchool.AI / AI tutor for 20 minutes: Prompt: Teach me how to find the components of an Objective Summary

Being an ESL teacher now means being open to differentiated instruction and using tools - like AI - to scaffold, support, and enhance student learning. Generative AI-infusion allows for having a digitally-mediated space such as Nearpod, where students can communicate in real-time using multimedia, and has allowed students of various levels of English to share their thoughts and have their voices be heard. Furthermore, having a digitally mediated space such as Nearpod, where students can communicate in real time using multimedia, has allowed students of various levels of English to share their thoughts and have their voices be heard. Digital sites of communication, such as the one constructed by Nearpod, provide an avenue for interaction for reserved and non-confident English learners to express their thoughts and be validated. It provides a space to make sure that all perspectives are heard, and I have noticed that it promotes inclusion in the classroom. Students who are comfortable

writing can write their thoughts, others record a short video, others a short voice memo, still others (especially those who are newcomers) upload pictures. Nearpod, for example, has a collaborative board feature wherein I (and everyone in the lesson) can see all posts and do peer commentaries. I can ask students in real time if they have understood the content, and most importantly, those who normally do not talk during normal question-and-answer instruction. It also gives students who are shy to speak up the opportunity to converse with their classmates. I even apply what I have learned from UPOU by asking students to comment on each other's work - agree, disagree, give feedback. The games also afforded me and the students the opportunity of a cross-cultural way to communicate, create relationships, reinforce existing ones, and provide opportunities for students who are hesitant to express themselves.

As a teacher, I facilitate learning. I have come to appreciate my role as a facilitator of learning. I see myself not only as a facilitator of learning but also as a reservoir of knowledge. I do not have all the answers, and I am co-exploring the world with my students, through their diverse lenses. As a teacher, I am the content specialist. I filter, I contextualize, I judge what is best for the individual students in my class. Technology is wonderful but they do not replace me because they do not direct my students to clear goals in the classroom.

I also use it as a teachable moment to go over the ethical use of AI with my students. I am humble enough to admit the error and explain to students that the worksheet was AI-generated. The honor code is given to all students and we read it together as a class and go over each ethical point. Each point is voted upon. If a

number lower than half of the class disagrees with the point, we rewrite it based on their comments. Students will be asked to sign the honor code.

Figure 8

A student's feedback sheet from Summer 2024.

ESL Summer School Survey

Please provide your honest opinions and recommendations about your experience during the ESL Summer Program.
You can remain anonymous if you prefer.

Which class did you complete (select one)?
 English Math

Circle one answer for each question:

My teacher was helpful (explained concepts, offered assistance, etc)
 Excellent Good Fair Poor

How would you rate the quality of teaching?
 Excellent Good Fair Poor

The ESL staff made me feel welcome.
 Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree

The smaller class size was helpful (more one-on-one help, less distractions, etc)
 Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree

If I needed to, I would participate in ESL Summer School again to recuperate a credit.
 Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree

What motivated you to participate in the ESL Summer Program?
I wasn't trying to fail, but after I came here I feel like it helped a lot, I've learned so much.

What was something that should continue in the ESL Summer Program?
Mr Parabela he's a good teacher.

What is something that should be added to the program?
I'm not sure, just love how the teacher makes lessons more fun.

What is something that you would change about the program?
Putting AC on the bus, I'm dying.

Enjoy your summer!

Monitoring learners' progress

LP1, E4

Empower - Activity 3 (Student Release Independent Practice) "You do" (:20)

Teacher monitors student engagement, answers questions, and ensures differentiation Writing a theme

Statement Project in class: ChatGPT: Using generative AI to "award" best work according to rubric. Show strengths and weaknesses for each submission.

Prompt: Randomly assign a number for these submissions (Student A, Student B, etc.). Award the best work based on these details - a theme statement: Author's + text + analytical verb + lesson. Provide the strength and weaknesses for each.

GAI technologies (like ChatGPT) and Gamified strategies have made my instructional process more data-driven and engaging thanks to the assistance of gaming tools that communicate feedback in real time. There were moments when AI-supported materials noticeably improved student engagement and comprehension especially through formative assessments. Platforms like Quizizz provide immediate analytics on student performance and help me determine whether it is time to move on to the next lesson or whether I need to reinforce certain concepts. I can ask students in real time if they have understood the content, and most importantly, those who normally do not talk during normal question-and-answer instruction. Now, with immediate feedback from digital tools, I can adjust my instruction in real time.

However, I eventually noticed that the focus shifted from the educational content to the entertainment value of the games. The students were enjoying the games, but the intended learning outcomes were not being met. I know this because of the feedback I got from digitally mediated AI-infused apps such as Quizizz. Based on Mastery Peak data, I realized that most students did not understand how character interactions

advanced the plot and that concept was frequently missed based on the Quizizz data. This forced me to redesign my instructional approach and renegotiate how to structure teaching-learning experiences in the classroom. Through AI-infused applications, which have the ability to track my students' progress in real time, standard-wise, I am able to shift practices based on communicated feedback and provide more specialized support to individual students.

I started to become a deliverer of instructional content that matched the students' needs, because I could now see where each student was, especially in a multicultural ESL classroom, where students come from different walks of life. I can see how well students are doing and show me areas for improvement. Platforms like Quizizz and SuccessMaker are helpful because they show students how well they are doing right away, and I can monitor their growth. Having engaging GAI-infused platforms that provide me with real-time analytics and do the grading for me has allowed me to focus on instruction and face-to-face interaction, which is necessary for ESL instruction.

I started integrating it into my instruction as independent work three times a week, so I could monitor progress. From my elementary school co-teachers, I learned how to make use of Successmaker Reading, an adaptive learning app, to show me the student's growth and which makes each student individualized questions based on their current reading level. To my surprise, SuccessMaker gave immediate feedback on reading levels and showed me percent gains each time students logged in. The student is an ESL Newcomer 10th grade student. They started with a score of 8.25 (8th grade reading level) at the start of the semester and grew by 0.42 with continued sustained practice. I get to see in real time how my ESL students write in English.

Generative AI tools transformed my teaching as they provided real-time feedback on student understanding and served both formative and summative assessment purposes. As mentioned in the previous parts of this paper, generative AI has become my “co-teacher.” I use it to reinforce “Raina” to help me see students’ thought processes, skills, and content mastery and “co-teach” the class with me. These tools help communicate standards in engaging ways and provide immediate feedback to teachers. Real-time diagnosis and feedback helps identify what individual students need and highlights limitations.

Motivator towards a pleasurable learning experience

PP1, E1

Once a week, I set up a pop-up shop where I sell chips, takis, airheads, jolly ranchers, etc. You can only “buy” them using Parabela Pesos. Parabela Pesos can also be used as experience points which can get you classroom perks!

After the COVID-19 pandemic, I noticed students were deeply attached to their devices, smartphones, laptops, tablets, and they responded better when content was delivered through technology. There were moments when AI-supported materials noticeably improved student engagement and comprehension, especially through formative assessments. Students were engaged, and their understanding improved significantly. I needed to sustain this engagement with the materials and started experimenting with various teaching styles.

GCGS1, E3

Once you reach level 5 and 10, you will receive a digital achievement badge. The level 5 achievement badge enables you to play your own preferred music during working period and an assignment pass (usable in the future) perfect score in one output.

Games speak to something universal - fun. When I began incorporating gamification techniques and practices into my classroom, I noticed that my students became more engaged. The kids were appreciative, highly motivated, and it showed in their assessments, in their writing, and in their efforts to communicate in English. This approach made the classroom feel more like a game and less like a pressure cooker. It relaxed the students and gave them confidence. However, after the change, they started doing the work because it was fun. If they are not doing well, they are motivated to try harder.

Through observation with other ESL teachers and their practices, I also started using Quizizz, Blooket, and Gimkit to engage students before the actual lesson and during the independent reading sessions. One of these activities I did, toward the end of the second semester, focused on careers in STEM. It gave my bilingual students a glimpse into what they could pursue after high school. Since AI tailors questions to their English proficiency, it reduces frustration. It gamifies mastery, and students compete to reach the top. Students are engaged because they want a Parabela Peso, experience points, or even candy.

Figure 9

My Gimkit class page. This is an interactive site where we play educational games. Data is generated after to show me the frequency of errors for each student for each question.

What I do to deepen engagement is prolong immediate rewards. For example, if a student is shy and doing a task for the first time, rewarding them immediately and praising them in front of classmates can have a powerful impact. But for students already engaged, I have seen that delaying gratification for a day or two is more effective. By being judicious in implementing gamified structures, I am able to channel student fun into learning outcomes.

Using gamification to improve student performance

Teacher as gamification strategist and classroom designer to improve student performance

This sub-theme explores how teacher authority is (re)produced by surfacing the teacher's roles as an overseer and strategist in the creation of a dynamic and game-based learning ESL classroom. The teacher's identity shifts from lesson-giver to co-constructor of the classroom ecosystem mediated by game-like elements to stimulate engagement and collaboration.

The teacher establishes norms and rewards by means of quests (GCGS1,E1) and the creation of a virtual economy through the "Paradela Pesos" system (PP1,E1). By the teacher's role as classroom designer, through the creation of "lessons that are engaging and rigorous" (RL1, E3), the teacher's authority is recognized as "a valuable resource for innovative curriculum and instruction" that highlights their professional mastery of both traditional teaching techniques and modern, tech-based strategies such as gamification.

Emerging as a strategist and classroom designer

ETD, E6

I was transitioning to become an English and ESL teacher the following school year (2024-2025). I noticed that my ESL students were more receptive and eager to learn than my previous group. I felt that they had higher appreciation for the material, being second language learners in a country where English was a necessity in daily life. I needed to sustain this engagement with the materials and started experimenting with various teaching styles. These strategies became standard in my repertoire and became the source of my gamification of the classroom.

The key strategies I took from that summer, the ones that stuck, are what I call the Three Es: Engage, Explain, and Explore. A class session (one-hour and thirty minutes) generally looked like this:

Engage is what I call the first 15–20 minutes: students play a game, we go over objectives, and “get in the zone” using tools like Gimkit, Blooket, or Quizizz.

Explain is the next 30–40 minutes: I teach a mini-lesson using Nearpod. This part often feels like the day’s first quest. If they complete, join in my discussions, do my mini-activities correctly, they earn Paradela Pesos.

Explore is the last 30–40 minutes: students apply what they’ve learned through independent work using ESL Library (Ellii), CommonLit, or Edpuzzle. If they score 80% or higher (our “mastery” grade), they get five more Paradela Pesos. Some students earn up to 10 a day and save them for class rewards.

Working with various students of various cultural backgrounds is challenging. My students come from varied cultural norms and they have varied ways of understanding what my authority as a teacher was. Furthermore, I felt that it was becoming increasingly difficult to “reach” different students given a one-size-fit all approach to the multicultural classroom. I felt my authority as a teacher threatened. In order to address this threat I started becoming open to adjusting my classroom approaches, which led to me gamification as a strategy to engage the class.

The specific moment I shifted my teaching approaches, especially by becoming more open to gamification as a strategy, is when I realized my ESL students were more eager to learn came from seeing just how motivated they were. Most of them, being English learners, had a strong desire to succeed. I remember asking a student why they had failed English I, and they said it was hard for them to understand the lessons—but they still really wanted to learn. They wanted to read and speak English because they hoped to go to college in the U.S. and eventually land a good job. That was my so-called “aha” moment. I noted that these students were not just learning English for school and that they were learning it for life in this county. I thought if I can tap into that motivation, I can be more successful in the classroom. I started designing lessons that engage them and make them more receptive to learning.

Knowing that my students use English everyday shaped how I plan and teach. I always aim to make lessons relevant to their daily lives at school. For example, I structure quizzes around academic vocabulary they might encounter in other subjects like Biology, Math, Social Studies, or English - especially with subjects with standardized testing. I also include what I call “free topics” - topics or activities not explicitly required by the curriculum, but they were areas that I think had great value. One of these activities I did, toward the end of the second semester, focused on careers in STEM. It gave my bilingual students a glimpse into what they could pursue after high school. One student appreciated the activity and told me that she had plans to try out some of the careers I placed onto the sheet.

What really helped me make my content more meaningful was learning about my students’ lives outside the classroom. That ongoing dialogue between us was key for it

provided me with perspectives to better address the needs of each student. It also afforded me with further perspective about my own privilege and my place in relation to them. During independent work, I would visit each table and strike up a conversation and ask how they were. Many of my students in grades 10–12 work. One student worked at a flea market and needed to negotiate and advocate for herself in English. Another student’s father owned a convenience store. He came from Yemen, so I gave him small talk phrases to help him connect with customers and he actually used them. Personalizing activities based on their real experiences made a big difference. In my gamified classroom, these small real-world tasks became “challenges” with rewards. For instance, if a student could memorize five small talk phrases, they’d earn 10 Parabela Pesos to exchange for perks or prizes later on.

Creating an engaging classroom culture with varied groups of students, from different language groups and cultures requires openness and constant configuration of procedures through feedback. I found that the most effective classroom strategy was gamification. Responding to this, I started applying gamification as a strategy.

ETD, E5

Toward the end of my first year teaching, AI had been something that really fascinated me. I wanted to see what the potential of AI was after Ms. J taught me what had worked for her. Following her example, I primarily experimented with ChatGPT and MagicSchool.AI to assist in lesson planning, differentiated materials, rubrics, writing feedback, and email responding. Being open to experiment with AI technology allowed me to develop new tools and strategies that have helped my teaching practice. It functioned as a kind of “teacher assistant” that allows me to easily reach teaching goals.

Like an old dog learning new tricks, once I whetted myself with the software offerings, towards the end of my first year, Ms. J then introduced me to various AI

websites. She became my mentor for all things AI. She told me that the AI program can generate and provide engagement activities when given a prompt. I tried experimenting with it and to my surprise it provided me with engagement activity ideas to use in the classroom that are based on the standards. I have been using AI ever since, it has been a game-changer for me since I can differentiate instruction more effectively.

The use of AI tools came from a genuine desire to simplify my workload and individualize instruction especially because I had so many students in my U.S. classroom, all with different needs and support requirements. If I were the only one designing instruction for every student, it would be incredibly time-consuming. However, to be effective in communicating the standards, I had to make use of technology to mediate authentic and personalized experiences to fit students because it allows immediate and leveled feedback.

Gamification strategist

GCGS1, E1

You level up in this class by doing the quests of the day. The main quests must be marked completed in order to level up.

Through observation with other ESL teachers and their practices, I started using Quizizz, Blooket, and Gimkit to engage students before the actual lesson and during the independent reading sessions. These strategies became standard in my repertoire and became the source of my gamification of the classroom.

My first experience with gamification involved integrating pop culture games like Super Mario and Pac-Man into my instruction. Because of that, I transitioned away from

those kinds of games and began using more purposeful educational games, implementing them more strategically and periodically within my instruction. I found that the most effective classroom strategy was gamification, turning classroom tasks into game-like experiences.

Figure 10

A picture of the Paradela Peso

PP1, E1

Once a week, I set up a pop-up shop where I sell chips, takis, airheads, jolly ranchers, etc. You can only "buy" them using Paradela Pesos. Paradela Pesos can also be used as experience points which can get you classroom perks!

Game-like experiences feature as a challenge, a quest, and added entertainment elements into my instruction. In my gamified classroom, these small real-world tasks became “challenges” with rewards. For instance, if a student could memorize five small talk phrases, they would earn 10 Paradela Pesos to exchange for perks or prizes later on. Gamification, therefore, has not only increased classroom engagement, it has redefined my approach to teaching. By being judicious in implementing gamified structures, I am able to channel student fun into learning outcomes.

Figure 11

The Digital Badges. I give students digital badges that they can show off if they can demonstrate proficiency in either reading, writing, speaking, or listening.

Technology can help differentiate instruction. Gamification can boost engagement. Educational technologies, AI-infused instruction, and gamified strategies help teachers deliver content; they are not replacements. What I do to deepen engagement is prolong immediate rewards. If I reward students instantly, it becomes all about the prize and not the content. Delaying gratification is powerful. Delaying gratification for a day or two is more effective.

GCGS1, E2

Doing various quests really well will also give you a chance to win badges. Badges will give you perks in this classroom such as extra restroom time or getting the chance to choose your own music.

I also use a checklist system, usually three items that students have to demonstrate before they get a reward or a Paradelo Peso. The tool should be secondary, it is just a vehicle to reach a learning goal.. Gamified tools should never replace content. They should be imaginative techniques, but content mastery is still

king. I tell my students, “We will stop this gaming activity if you do not show me at least 60 percent mastery.”

Figure 12

Gamified perk shop: students can buy classroom perks using Paradela Pesos.

Improving student performance

SSP2, E1

Successmaker's AI program:

Student current course level: Far Below Level (7.74)

[Student's] current course level is Far below grade level for grade 10. At this time of year, students' course levels should be at or above 10.00.

As my tech skills grew, I became better at meeting the needs of my ESL learners. I was able to differentiate instruction and provide appropriate resources tailored to their current English language proficiency levels. Learning about differentiated instruction through educational technology influenced my lesson planning and classroom management in two important ways. First, it made lesson planning more efficient because many resources were already available and adaptable. Second, it reduced behavior issues because students better understood the materials, which were now more aligned with their learning levels.

There were moments when GAI-supported materials noticeably improved student engagement and comprehension, especially through formative assessments. Students were engaged, and their understanding improved significantly. Integrating technology into my instruction has helped students practice English, improve comprehension, and become more successful learners overall. It functioned as a kind of “teacher assistant” that allows me to easily reach teaching goals. Whether low-tech or high-tech, a tool’s effectiveness is measured by how successful the transfer of learning is done.

SSP1, E2

Successmaker’s AI program: Percentage Skills Mastered: 70%

Areas for Growth - Since AP

Skills not mastered:

8.65 - Analyze how characters in literature deal with conflict, solve problems, and relate to real-life situations.

8.65 - Use question-and-answer relationships to improve comprehension of texts: Right There questions

8.49 - Identify incorrect shifts in verb tenses

When I structured my lessons in this way, students were more receptive and participative. They were better prepared and more willing to engage in the teaching-learning process. Through gamification, I noticed they became more participative in completing microtasks, more responsive to my assessments, and more receptive toward instruction. Individualized feedback from these tools also impacted participation. Gaming apps and tools have significantly improved student engagement, especially for English learners. Quizizz, for example, is interactive and has game-like elements which students enjoy. Collaboration also increases due to the platform’s

interface; students can use GIFs, pictures, and videos to express their answers on Nearpod, and they enjoy those features.

Classroom designer

RL1, E3

[Mr. Paradela's colleagues] look up to him as an expert, not only in integrating AI in his instruction but also for his impressive ideas on how to create lessons that are engaging and rigorous for his students.

RL2, E5

Mr. Paradela is a team player who collaborates with his coworkers and is regarded as a valuable resource for innovative curriculum and instruction. He is more than willing to share his work and make himself available to advise other teachers on how to use technology to improve student outcomes.

RL2, E6

The skills and strategies he will learn in the AI Fellows program will enhance his impact on the field, both in ESL education and district-level AI development through future presentations, professional development sessions and curriculum development that will deeply benefit our district and students.

My journey with educational technology began with learning impactful tools like Nearpod, CommonLit, Edpuzzle, Quizizz, and Gimkit. Over time, I started designing lessons that engage students and make them more receptive to learning. The multicultural diversity of my students also challenged me to refine my teaching, in the materials I used, in the way I structured lessons, in the vocabulary I chose, even how I phrased things. This forced me to redesign my instructional approach and renegotiate how to structure teaching-learning experiences in the classroom. This is when I started integrating educational technology, which allowed me to redesign my instruction specifically for a student who needed specialized support. That summer became the foundation for how I now structure my classes.

The intrinsic motivation part can really be a struggle, and I would have to constantly assign meaning to what we do based on the standards. I also include what I call “free topics” - topics or activities not explicitly required by the curriculum, but they were areas that I think had great value. I started integrating it into my instruction as independent work three times a week so I could monitor progress. I started using generative AI-infused technology to create various worksheets for students with different English levels and extract key vocabulary terms from standards. I primarily experimented with ChatGPT, Google Gemini, and MagicSchool.AI to assist in lesson planning, differentiated materials, rubrics, writing feedback, and email responding. ChatGPT and Google Gemini specifically, had a significant impact on my lesson planning and instructional decision-making. Because generative AI is able to help streamline, individualize lessons, and take the burden of instructional design and do adaptive learning for me, I feel more in control and more at ease thinking about my instruction being personalized, standard-based, and relevant. I tried to plan and differentiate everything on my own, but it was extremely time-consuming. Because of that, I transitioned away from those kinds of games and began using more purposeful educational games, implementing them more strategically and periodically within my instruction.

Learning these technologies afforded me more control in the instructional process. Now, with immediate feedback from digital tools, I can adjust my instruction in real-time. So I scrapped my original agenda and went back to reinforce that skill - all thanks to immediate feedback from Quizizz. Assessment becomes an informational tool that allows me to reevaluate and shift best practices away from ineffective ones. This

enables me to design instruction that is more targeted, effective, and data-driven. It has allowed me to plan ahead, create more targeted experiences, and communicate to students with numbers. My interaction with AI and gamified approaches has been melded as part of my repertoire. It is part of my lesson plans, my engagement with parents, and how I run my classroom. Over time, I began breaking lectures into smaller chunks and embedding them into more engaging, interactive lessons often using Nearpod, EdPuzzle, Quizizz, and interactive games found in Blooket and Gimkit. Technology has enabled me to differentiate instruction really well. Because of this, I have continually become a dabbler in different educational techniques so that I can communicate content more effectively.

Technology has enabled me to do and communicate teacher-related goals through more mechanical spaces such as the creation of multimedia, digitally-mediated communication spaces, and real-time, adaptive technologies to enhance standards. The way I determine traditional methods versus when to use technology is largely based on how I “read” the situation. Some standards, such as finding figurative language and word meaning, can be best taught with AI assistance. However, for standards like poetry analysis and tasks that require higher levels within Bloom’s Taxonomy, I shift towards traditional paper and pen practices. A “technology fast” is sometimes necessary to realign classroom practices with human-centered, analog experiences such as reading a book or handwriting a journal entry. I let my students and myself step away from screens and do some good old-fashioned reading and writing. As the teacher, I am the content specialist. I filter, I contextualize, I judge what is best for the individual students in my class. The human element can be best described as the teacher

functioning as judge - as the teacher, you are the final say of everything that will be communicated to and delivered in the teaching-learning process. My role in the classroom has transformed to become a curator, gatekeeper, and strategist of learning experiences.

In my practice, even when GAI is used to generate content, it is always filtered in the light of my experience and content specialty. I train myself and others to use AI critically, not blindly. I treat AI as a scaffold, not a replacement. I verify and contextualize AI outputs by reading through them. If anything looks off, I do my due diligence and make the necessary corrections. I try my best to study the content and judge if it is accurate. If not, I discard it. I may use it to create leveled worksheets, but I make sure I am the final judge of the content. Generative AI may generate leveled materials, but I hold onto my responsibility as the teacher to verify their accuracy and relevance. I ask myself: How is this material relevant for my students today? Is there another way I can deliver this content without using AI? Can I teach this lesson without gamifying it? What are the privacy and technological issues with the use of this tech? My colleagues look up to me as an expert, not only in integrating AI in his instruction but also for my ideas on how to create lessons that are engaging and rigorous for my students. I am a team player who collaborates with his coworkers and is regarded as a valuable resource for innovative curriculum and instruction.

Figure 13

Successmaker AI's cumulative performance board. This shows me the current level and skill mastery of all students enrolled in my class.

Partnering with parents and tailoring lessons to fit learners' needs

Teacher partnering with parents in scaffolding and tailoring the learning process

This sub-theme explores how teacher authority is (re)produced through the teacher's role as a technologically-adept bridge-builder who makes use of GAI tools to make communication easier and understandable for non-English-speaking families (RL1,E2; EM1, E1). Being crucial in the ESL classroom, removing language barriers has allowed for a shift in the teacher identity as the central figure who connects the school, the home, and the student's individual learning needs. The teacher becomes an actively involved agent in each student's learning journey.

The teacher's authority is also strengthened through the use of GAI to scaffold and tailor personalized lessons (RL2, E3) unique for each student. Teacher authority is based on the teacher's ability to expertly diagnose individual student needs and integrate technology to foster personalized learning; as well as to function as an expert who knows targeted resources and interventions for each student.

Developing as a partner and an instructional tailor

ETD, E7

Parents in my ESL classroom come from all walks of life and languages. I have Spanish speaking parents, Haitian Creole speaking parents, Thai, Arabic, and Filipino. With the exception of my Filipino parents, I have had difficulties communicating with parents of other linguistic groups, not because of fear but because I do not speak their language. AI has been a great help to translate communications from parents and vice versa. When I use AI to communicate with them, I am transparent that I am using ChatGPT and that personal identifiers are never fed into the app. AI technology has enabled me to automate some classroom practices such as grading, lesson planning, and the construction of levelled worksheets for individualized instruction. It has given me leisure time to do other classroom-relevant tasks such as parent communication and data

dives. However, AI use must be guided by my judgement and must always be filtered and checked by me for accuracy.

Given that all my students have access to technology and various software learning apps which have started the AI feature to make my work easier from the instructional material design end, I started focusing on reinforcing student engagement. The major threat I experienced in the classroom is that despite the technological access, the materials were as it were not properly engaged with by the students. Furthermore, I felt that my students have started using “AI as the real expert” in the classroom because it is able to create materials, translate things, and explain concepts quickly. I also felt threatened with my use of AI itself as my teacher authority because some students might believe teacher authority tied to visible effort and content knowledge and my use of AI could be thought to as “taking shortcuts” from both students and parents.

Nonetheless, I noticed that as some processes became more automated through GAI, such as brainstorming lessons and the creation of assessment materials, I had more time to plan lessons ahead and became more open to experimentation as to what strategies would work best to engage various social groups within my classroom. AI enabled me to generate “funner classroom quests” and started incorporating more varied vocabulary and grammar games through Quizizz, Blooket, and Gimkit. I do not have to painstakingly take the time to manually take apart academic vocabulary and create ESL-friendly definitions for them to teach my ESL students and have AI do it for me anymore. It became easier for me to differentiate instruction as well, I can give materials to students with different levels of English Language Proficiency in the

classroom. Differentiation means I can deliver leveled content to students who need specialized support, and second, with AI I can translate and translanguage materials to be easily understood by multilingual learners using their first language.

With this insight in mind, I started observing how my fellow teachers - both local and experienced cultural exchange - have been using technologies at their disposal. I then started trying these out by integrating their practices and seeing if it worked with my classroom context. If it did not work, I merely changed it.

Partnering with parents in the learning process

RL1, E2

[Mr. Paradela] uses and has even found ways to make parent communication easier and more understandable through translation tools, always keeping families informed and involved.

RL2, E1

Mr. Paradela actively uses AI in his classroom as a teaching tool and parent outreach and communications.

RL2, E4

He uses AI to communicate with parents through translation tools and multilingual family bulletins.

GAI technologies have allowed me to communicate with parents of various language groups because with real time translation functions, I am able to collaborate with parents and let them understand what is going on with their students in the classroom setting. With easy-to-understand generative AI reports, I am able to provide parents with targeted and specific areas that their child can improve on. I am able to hold parents accountable on their end, that the teaching-learning experience does not only end in the classroom but continues with them.

I am able to keep parents involved with their child's academic progress and we have created strategic partnerships because of this to make sure that their child is learning as effectively as they should.

Scaffolder of personalized learning

RL2, E3

He also uses AI to develop instructional materials based on the current English language proficiency and reading/comprehension level of each student based on their assessment scores.

Being an ESL teacher now means being open to differentiated instruction and using tools like AI to scaffold, support, and enhance student learning. As my tech skills grew, I became better at meeting the needs of my ESL learners. I was able to differentiate instruction and provide appropriate resources tailored to their current English language proficiency levels. Learning these technologies afforded me more control in the instructional process. I started using generative AI-infused technology to create various worksheets for students with different English levels and extract key vocabulary terms from standards. Now, I am able to individualize instruction, and that transformation has made me a better teacher.

Because generative AI is able to help streamline, individualize lessons, and take the burden of instructional design and do adaptive learning for me, I feel more in control and more at ease thinking about my instruction being personalized, standard-based, and relevant.

Having technology that provides me with real-time communication through grade and standard feedback allows for real-time shifts in instruction and a more personalized

direction for tasks in the classroom. It gives me suggested materials within the platform to scaffold the weak standards for each student.. This dynamic interplay between student performance, instructional adaptation, and data analysis allows for a more responsive and differentiated learning experience.

SSP2, E2

Successmaker's AI program:

Percentage of Skill Mastered: 50%

Areas for Growth - Since AP

Skills not mastered:

7.56 - Use compare and contrast relationships to gain meaning

7.61 - Paraphrase information from text

7.61 - Compare themes

7.63 - Use Greek and Latin roots to determine the meaning of unfamiliar words.

From my elementary school co-teachers, I learned how to make use of Successmaker Reading, an adaptive learning app, to show me the student's growth and which makes each student individualized questions based on their current reading level. SuccessMaker, likewise, is engaging because no two users have the same experience, it is adaptive, based on individual needs. Quizizz also allows me to do Mastery Peak, wherein students are continually practicing a question or skill until the platform is convinced that the student has understood it. Mastery Peak uses adaptive learning technology and it does not stop offering questions until the student has mastered the skill. Through AI-infused applications, which have the ability to track my students' progress in real time, standard-wise, I am able to shift practices based on communicated feedback and provide more specialized support to individual students. It has humbled me to realize that if you just guide students and scaffold effectively, they will learn independently. I treat AI as a scaffold, not a replacement. Technology should scaffold, not replace.

Tailoring lessons that fit learners' needs

RL1, E1

[Mr. Paradela] uses AI not just to create materials, but to personalize instruction for his students, adjusting lessons based on their language proficiency levels and learning needs.

RL2, E3

He also uses AI to develop instructional materials based on the current English language proficiency and reading/comprehension level of each student based on their assessment scores.

The use of GAI tools came from a genuine desire to simplify my workload and individualize instruction especially because I had so many students in my U.S. classroom, all with different needs and support requirements. The multicultural diversity of my students also challenged me to refine my teaching: in the materials I used, in the way I structured lessons, in the vocabulary I chose, even how I phrased things. I had to adjust and level my instruction and materials accordingly. I had to look for resources that could help them understand better, including ways to translate key terms into their home languages. I started to become a deliverer of instructional content that matched the students' needs, because I could now see where each student was, especially in a multicultural ESL classroom, where students come from different walks of life. I always aim to make lessons relevant to their daily lives at school. For example, I structure quizzes around academic vocabulary they might encounter in other subjects like Biology, Math, Social Studies, or English - especially with subjects with standardized testing. My teaching is now more data-driven and grounded in the needs of my students, rather than simply following a standard or pacing guide. Having this data on hand has enabled me to effectively differentiate and individualize my teaching method to help individual students attain competency with the standards.

Being an ESL teacher now means being open to differentiated instruction and using tools, like gAI, to scaffold, support, and enhance student learning. Being open to differentiated instruction and using tools like AI to scaffold and support student learning. As my tech skills grew, I became better at meeting the needs of my ESL learners. I was able to differentiate instruction and provide appropriate resources tailored to their current English language proficiency levels. Learning these technologies afforded me more control in the instructional process. I started using generative AI-infused technology to create various worksheets for students with different English levels and extract key vocabulary terms from standards. Technology has enabled me to differentiate instruction really well. Because of this, I have continually become a dabbler in different educational techniques so that I can communicate content more effectively. Now, I am able to individualize instruction, and that transformation has made me a better teacher.

Generative AI has enabled me to create leveled materials for multicultural students with varying English skills. AI can enable me to level my instructional content, goals, and tasks for my students. I can modify materials to suit their individual levels of English proficiency, reducing frustration and increasing engagement. Since AI tailors questions to their English proficiency, it reduces frustration. For example, if we were analyzing Haruki Murakami's *The Seventh Man*, I could create different versions of the same worksheet based on WIDA levels. We all read the same text and work on the same content, but the material is personalized. I can modify materials to suit their individual levels of English proficiency, reducing frustration and increasing engagement. Because generative AI is able to help streamline, individualize lessons, and take the

burden of instructional design and do adaptive learning for me, I feel more in control and more at ease thinking about my instruction being personalized, standard-based, and relevant.

AI technology has enabled me to bridge and communicate expectations to various groups of multilingual learners through its ability to level content and translate materials in real time. For example, one time we were studying tone words, and I asked ChatGPT to make example sentences that 7th- and 8th- grade students could understand. From my elementary school co-teachers, I learned how to make use of Successmaker Reading, an adaptive learning app, to show me the student's growth and which makes each student individualized questions based on their current reading level. It allowed me to redesign my instruction specifically for him. I could give him materials and tools that matched his current level in English. Having technology that provides me with real-time communication through grade and standard feedback allows for real-time shifts in instruction and a more personalized direction for tasks in the classroom. This dynamic interplay between student performance, instructional adaptation, and data analysis allows for a more responsive and differentiated learning experience.

Generative AI-infusion allows for having a digitally-mediated space such as Nearpod, where students can communicate in real-time using multimedia, has allowed students of various levels of English to share their thoughts and have their voices be heard. Furthermore, having a digitally mediated space such as Nearpod, where students can communicate in real time using multimedia, has allowed students of various levels of English to share their thoughts and have their voices be heard. The multimedia capacity of these digital spaces allows for a more individualized exchange of

ideas. Students who are comfortable writing can write their thoughts, others record a short video, others a short voice memo, still others (especially those who are newcomers) upload pictures. Translate what I was saying into language my students could understand.

Generative AI may generate leveled materials, but I hold onto my responsibility as the teacher to verify their accuracy and relevance. I may use it to create leveled worksheets, but I make sure I am the final judge of the content.

Assessing learner's progress and awarding performance

Teacher authority as assessor, awardor, and communicator of learner progress

This sub-theme highlights how teacher authority is (re)produced through the curated use of generative AI and gamification. Instead of being seen as the source of judgement and content mastery, the traditional view of teacher authority is shifted to that of an expert who curates, designs assessment, and communicates in accordance with the data supplied by generative AI systems. The excerpts and codes show how generative AI is masterfully used by the teacher to assess and “award” student work (LP1,E5), whereby I, as the teacher, co-construct and co-teach strengths and weaknesses for each student submission. From being considered as the singular judge to a framer of adaptive assessment processes, this sub-theme highlights how teacher authority has transformed to leverage expertise in using GAI technology to provide more efficient and personalized feedback.

Moreover, this sub-theme also explores the teacher's role as communicator

(RL1, E2; EM1, E1) to bridge multilingual realities together, mediated by GAI technologies. GAI's potential to bridge communication gaps (re)produces the role of the teacher, especially the ESL teacher, as the focus of empathy, inclusion, and multicultural partnership.

Becoming an assessor, awardor, and communicator

ETD, E9

In the few years that I have taught in the United States, I feel that I have learned a lot and that the way I now teach and facilitate my classroom processes has been forever changed. Having experienced and having been challenged by the needs and demands of a multicultural classroom, and as a response to these, I feel that I have grown in my cultural literacy and have become mindful of the diversity of experiences and learning styles. I have learned how to communicate content effectively through the mediation of a variety of EdTech tools, AI-infusion, and engage students through adopting gamification techniques.

Teaching in the U.S. has reshaped the way I understand teaching, learning, and my role as a teacher because it has challenged me to try out different strategies that I may have heard in teacher education or noticed with my peers in the Philippines. But when I was in the United States, I had to refocus, refine, and continually develop the way I communicate and deliver my lessons because I teach in a multicultural, multilingual classroom. I had to always adjust and change my pedagogy based on the needs and current realities of my classroom.

In the Philippines, I usually had a batch of students who were already good English speakers and fairly on the same level. But in the classrooms I have in the U.S., students come from all walks of life, from different linguistic groups with different needs and ways of speaking, listening, writing, and communicating in English. Technology has

enabled me to differentiate instruction really well. Because of this, I've continually become a dabbler in different educational techniques so that I can communicate content more effectively.

Though threats do exist, especially with the integration of GAI in the classroom vis-a-vis my teacher authority. I felt that the traditional perception of the teacher as the ultimate authority in terms of content in the classroom has become challenged. Furthermore, reliance on GAI technology would ultimately mean that errors and misalignments can challenge my professional credibility unless I carefully monitor them.

The challenges of working in a multicultural classroom pushed me to reconsider and reframe my prior beliefs about pedagogy. Whether I like it or not, I am teaching in a multicultural environment with multiple cultural expectations. The parents speak different languages. The students speak different languages. It has humbled me to realize that if you just guide students and scaffold effectively, they will learn independently. This has been one of the most important realizations for me. I tended to be very teacher-centered, but that approach doesn't work in the U.S. classroom. I'm grateful I realized this because it made me a better teacher. I've come to appreciate my role as a facilitator of learning. I do not have all the answers, and I am co-exploring the world with my students, through their diverse lenses.

Pivotal moments that helped me grow in cultural literacy and responsiveness came from encountering students from different walks of life. I have students who grew up in poverty, students from the middle class, and others who are affluent. They all come with different customs, cultures, races, and worldviews. I realized my own way of

looking at and interacting with the world - my experience of the English language - is radically different from theirs. These interactions with students and parents helped me grow in cultural literacy. I have become more of a cultural relativist. I now understand that different cultures are simply different ways of expressing ideas; they are not boundaries. Diversity is the strength of my classroom, not its uniformity. That has been a very important realization as a teacher.

Whether I like it or not, new technologies and AI platforms are part of the future. As a 21st-century teacher, I must consider them and shape my pedagogy accordingly. These tools will evolve with new generations of students who have different cultural realities and motivations. My role is to teach them, which means I must adapt to the changing landscape. I don't want to be an obsolete teacher. Traditional methods—pen and paper, lectures, group work—still have a place, but students today are different. I need to evolve with technology and teach students how to use it properly.

I now design lessons differently to reflect the diversity of learning styles and needs in my classroom. By integrating AI, I can personalize and level activities for different linguistic and cultural groups. Students also have varying levels of technological literacy, and I have to consider that.

One tension I've had to navigate is deciding when to use innovative tools versus traditional instruction. For example, oral recitation is useful for assessing speaking skills, especially with language support. Recording responses through Ellii.com is fine, but it misses the live interaction. Sometimes, speaking in front of peers is necessary, even if it's frightening, because real-life communication happens face-to-face. My ongoing

challenge is to find the balance between innovation—like AI and gamification—and traditional methods like lectures, paper-based assessments, and recitation. I'm constantly developing and refining this balance to become more effective in my instruction.

Assessing learners' progress

LP1, E5

Class Summative Work Writing an objective summary.

Project in class: ChatGPT: Using generative AI to "award" best work according to rubric. Show strengths and weaknesses for each submission.

Prompt: Randomly assign a number for these submissions (Student A, Student B, etc.). Award the best work based on these details - a theme statement:

Step 1: Topic Sentence (Name it + Verb it + Motif it)

Step 2: 3-5 key details (Think "beginning, middle, end;" also, "emergence, general idea into that poignant

Step 3: Conclusion Sentence (Refine the general idea into that poignant Provide the strength and weaknesses for each.

Generative AI tools have transformed how I go about formative assessment and diagnostics, as it has provided real-time feedback on student understanding and serves both formative and summative assessment purposes. There were moments when AI-supported materials noticeably improved student engagement and comprehension especially through formative assessments. Because of its ability to provide real-time data, GAI technologies are able to communicate and provide feedback that told me I was on the right track, that I was using the best tools I had, that I was truly engaging them, assessing them meaningfully, and creating something valuable in the classroom.

Generative AI has become my "co-teacher", particularly MagicSchool.ai 's "AI Tutor" function. I use it to reinforce "Raina" to help me see students' thought processes,

skills, and content mastery and “co-teach” the class with me. These tools help communicate standards in engaging ways and provide immediate feedback to teachers. This feedback helps identify what individual students need and highlights their limitations. Platforms like Quizizz and SuccessMaker are helpful because they show students how well they are doing right away, and I can monitor their growth. I can do two things in-real time: redirect content individually for mastery and measure gains or losses, growth and stagnation for each student.

Figure 14

Quizizz’s (n.d.) *Mastery Peak* game interface. Students go “up a mountain” to attain mastery.

After playing a game through Quizizz, its AI feature shows me student mastery of the standard and informs what content areas to reinforce. To my surprise, SuccessMaker gave immediate feedback on reading levels and showed me percent gains each time students logged in. When we used SuccessMaker, I found that his reading level was 1.0 - equivalent to a first-grade level. The student is an ESL

Newcomer 10th grade student. They started with a score of 8.25 (8th grade reading level) at the start of the semester and grew by 0.42 with continued sustained practice.

I always follow up with an assessment to see if learning happened; otherwise, they are just playing. I also show them their gains or losses and tell them what to do to improve their performance.

Figure 15

Quizizz (n.d.) results and the student's mastery of the standards in real time.

To make the classroom more engaging for assessment, I added quests, digital badges, and a whole reward system. When students complete tasks, they earn rewards, which I call Paradela Pesos, which they can trade for classroom perks. They have taken a liking, for example, to getting Paradela Pesos to trade for things like snacks, music privileges, extra bathroom time, or even a homework pass. For instance, if a student could memorize five small talk phrases, they would earn 10 Paradela Pesos to exchange for perks or prizes later on. I give students digital badges that they can show off if they can demonstrate proficiency in either reading, writing, speaking, or listening.

With increased access to a wide array of digital tools, it is easier for me to build incentives and adopt gamified approaches without manually doing everything myself.

Awarding performance

GCGS1, E2

Doing various quests really well will also give you a chance to win badges. Badges will give you perks in this classroom such as extra restroom time or getting the chance to choose your own music.

Finding ways to pique student engagement is one of the most challenging aspects of my job, especially in the ESL classroom. Considering that students come from different cultural backgrounds and realities, involving them could be quite a challenge.

To try and bridge this gap, and in response to modeling best practices, I have started integrating gamified classroom practices, such as the introduction of the “Paradela Peso” system whereby students can “earn” class currency whereby they can purchase items and class perks when they have gathered enough of it. When I started awarding performance, I noticed that students have become more engaged because they want a Paradela Peso, experience points, or even candy. What I do to deepen engagement is prolong immediate rewards. If I reward students instantly, it becomes all about the prize and not the content. But for students already engaged, I have seen that delaying gratification for a day or two is more effective.

Modeling my peers' best practice, I have also started using a checklist system, usually three items that students have to demonstrate before they get a reward or a

Paradela Peso. They must show me that they understand specific things. If not, they go back and try again until they reach mastery.

Communicator with parents

RL1, E2

[Mr. Paradela] uses and has even found ways to make parent communication easier and more understandable through translation tools, always keeping families informed and involved.

RL2, E4

He uses AI to communicate with parents through translation tools and multilingual family bulletins.

It feels very difficult to encounter language barriers when trying to build relationships with non-English speaking parents in such a way that they are more hesitant in approaching and collaborating with you. To be culturally responsive, I had to find means and ways to coordinate and collaborate with parents because my parents come from multifaceted classrooms. They have different backgrounds, and at the end of the day, they just really love their kids, and they want to communicate with me because they are very much concerned with how their children are doing in school. But the problem is, because of the communication barrier, they are not able to communicate with me.

When I started using AI to aid in translation, it was a game changer. Generative AI technology has greatly helped me engage multilingual and multicultural students by allowing me to speak the parents' language through language translation features. My mentors have noted how I use Generative AI in my classroom as a teaching tool and for parent outreach and communications and how I have used it to make parent

communication easier and more understandable through translation tools, always keeping families informed and involved.

EM1, E1

I am not a Spanish-speaker so I am using an AI translator to help me communicate with you so I apologize if the grammar is a bit unusual.

No hablo español, así que estoy utilizando un traductor de inteligencia artificial para comunicarme con usted, por lo que le pido disculpas si la gramática es un poco inusual.

Generative AI can generate emails for me. For example, MagicSchool.AI has a parent emailer where it generates emails for parents, and at the same time, ChatGPT is able to translate that email into the desired language. I am not a Spanish-speaker, so I am using an AI translator to help me communicate with you, and I apologize if the grammar is a bit unusual. What I have noticed about ChatGPT is that it is a bit more accurate, especially when I start translating things from English to Filipino and Cebuano. I have noticed that it is able to capture more of the information that I want to address. However, I must be transparent with my AI use and never put my students' or parents' names into the AI platform to maintain confidentiality.

Figure 16

An email exchange I had with a parent using Generative AI as a translation tool.

solicitando colaboración
3 messages

Fri, Feb 28, 2025 at 11:35 AM

To: "ginoparadela@ k12.nc.us"

Muy buenos días y deseando éxitos en su trabajo.
Clemmer Majano se dirige a usted como madre del alumno del grado 9 del centro educacional High School , Condado de con número de estudiante

El motivo del correo es para solicitarle su colaboración para que mi hijo sea incluido en algún curso, asesoría o acompañamiento de otra persona para que le ayude en el idioma inglés, ya que solo habla el idioma español y se le hace difícil su aprendizaje en el aula .

quedo a la espera de cualquier respuesta e información.

Gino Paradela
Fri, Feb 28, 2025 at 12:23 PM

To:

Inglés:

Hi Ms.

I am Mr. Paradela, and I am English as a Second Language (ESL) teacher. I am getting ready to get his English Learner (EL) Plan and I will test him to see where his current English Language Proficiency is. Once he is tested, he will have his EL Plan available which I will send out to all his teachers so that they will know where currently is in terms of his English Language Progress. I already received language card from you. The next step we are waiting for is for the ESL Office to send me the "go signal" to test him, hopefully next week.

As far as class progress goes, does some of his work in my class. But sometimes he is always on his phone and does not do what he is supposed to do. I would like to see exert some more effort so that he can learn and improve on his English. Would you like me to tag you in an email with all his teachers at High School and give his teachers your contact information?

I am not a Spanish-speaker so I am using an AI translator to help me communicate with you so I apologize if the grammar is a bit unusual.

Thank you for collaborating with me!

Very truly yours,

Mr. Paradela

Espanol:

Hola Sra.

Soy el Sr. Paradela, el maestro de Inglés como Segundo Idioma (ESL) de . Estoy preparando a para obtener su Plan de Aprendiz de Inglés (EL Plan), y le haré una evaluación para determinar su nivel actual de dominio del idioma inglés. Una vez que complete la evaluación, se elaborará su EL Plan, el cual enviaré a todos sus maestros para que sepan en qué nivel se encuentra en cuanto a su progreso en el idioma inglés. Ya he recibido de usted la tarjeta de idioma de . El siguiente paso es esperar a que la Oficina de ESL me dé la "luz verde" para evaluarlo, lo cual espero que suceda la próxima semana.

Theorizing the relationship of GAI, Gamification, and Teacher's Authority

The previous parts of this chapter discussed how the emergence of GAI technologies in the classroom has, in a way, threatened my teacher authority. Furthermore, it also discussed how teacher authority has been reproduced through the communicative act. This part discusses my attempt at theorizing the relationship among GAI, gamification, and teacher's authority centered around the communicative act as it is presented in Figure 17 below.

Figure 17

Conceptual map

How GAI threatens teacher authority

The sociocultural tradition theorizes communication as a symbolic process that produces and reproduces shape sociocultural patterns (Craig, 1999). Within this tradition, communication explains how social order is created, realized, sustained and transformed through microlevel interaction processes (Craig, 1999). Within the context of this study, the social order (the macrolevel phenomenon) is the classroom - one where the teacher is the authority and students are learning. The social order is communicatively constructed, that is "... it is constructed, constituted, and maintained in a greater degree, part by symbolic codes and media of communication." (ibid, 145). With the appearance of Generative AI-infused educational technologies, the social order is disrupted.

Rooted in the socio-cultural tradition therefore, tensions in the microlevel, which is communicatively constructed, reflect disruptions in the macrolevel. Thus, shifts in conceptions of authority and identity shows tensions being socially constructed and reinforced. It is through the communicative process that meanings are assigned, mediated, reinforced, changed, and enacted and (re)production in the macro-level of the social order is identified. Depending on contexts and the lived reality of students and educational technologies in the classroom, teachers shape and (re)produce their conceptions of authority and identity and with this (re)evaluate their place in the teaching-learning process (Griffin, et al., 2023).

The arrival of GAI into the classroom therefore, brought about a disruption in the social order. An analysis of the naturally-occurring data yielded four ways that it has disrupted the Social Order in the classroom. These are:

- (1) threatening self-image as a content expert;
- (2) tendency to outsource thinking with GAI;
- (3) challenging traditional teacher roles; and
- (4) weakening teacher authority.

What I have experienced in the classroom resonates with what has been discussed by Shao & Sun (2025). I have felt a degree of marginalization with the arrival of GAI in the classroom. Generative AI has brought about a crisis in how I make sense of my place in the classroom and have perceived, like Shao & Sun, how it has weakened my role in the classroom space or worse replaced them. The automation of tasks and trend of replacing employees in other fields have shaken the professional identity of teachers.

Shao and Sun (2025) notes three threats to teacher's identity: the weakening of their role and authority, the threat of professional status, and the pressure of professional skills. These three threats are reminiscent of my personal experience.

How is teacher authority (re)produced

As a Filipino teacher entering into a different cultural paradigm in terms of education, my initial authority was challenged by linguistic barriers and unfamiliar codes of interactions which prompted me to seek out and negotiate and emerge new educational meanings and shared understanding over time. This is so because gaps across space (sociocultural diversity relativity) and time (sociocultural change) have depleted the stock of shared patterns on which interactions depend (Craig, 1999).

Hence, viewed in this light - my teacher authority and identity has been disrupted due to the arrival of generative AI technology in the classroom *and* the multicultural nature of my ESL classroom where my students come from various symbolic worlds (i.e. cultures).

Likewise, through the communicative act - my teacher authority and identity is continuously (re)negotiated through symbolic and social interactions with peers, students, families, and even with machines. As such, my encounters with Generative AI (GAI) technologies for education became an integral part of my teacher authority and identity as it mediates communication (especially across multicultural and multilingual stakeholders like students and parents) and instructional delivery while constantly shaping my teacher identity.

My delving into the naturally-occurring data found that interactions with GAI and gamification my *becoming* in the process of (re)producing authority has emerged the following:

1. Teacher authority is (re)produced as an expert who diagnoses learning gaps through highly-specified data points, who can also prescribe the right interventions by means of technological tools to address them.
2. The teacher's identity shifts from disciplinarian into an authority who generates learning motivation by means of creating an enjoyable learning environment.
3. Identity shifts from lesson-giver to co-constructor of the classroom ecosystem mediated by game-like elements to stimulate engagement and collaboration.
4. Teacher authority is based on the teacher's ability to expertly diagnose individual student needs and integrate technology to foster personalized learning; as well as to function as an expert who knows targeted resources and interventions for each student.
5. Instead of being seen as the source of judgement and content mastery, the

traditional view of teacher authority is shifted to that of an expert who curates, designs assessment, and communicates in accordance with the data supplied by generative AI systems

Blumer's first premise is that humans act towards things based on assigned meaning (Griffin, et al., 2023). This meaning is drawn from the communicative act. Meaning-making is not an individual affair (his second premise), but rather drawn from social interaction. Within the parameters, the assigned meaning of words such as "authority" and "identity" is an on-going process. My encounters with peers, students, administrators, GAI technology, in and out of the multicultural ESL classroom is therefore a process of meaning-making by which "authority" and its meaning is constantly negotiated and (re)defined.

My becoming, as the classroom authority, thus, is formed by my participation in the meaning-making process in the classroom. Teacher authority could not have arisen were it not for my participation in the assignment of meanings in the teaching-learning process. Interaction, negotiations, and renegotiations of my identity and authority. Having an open work culture in my experience in the American classroom, I experienced an environment where GAI use is effectively modeled, collaborative reflected, and scaffolded implementation (Kim & Kwon, 2025). Because of this kind of culture, I have started to view my role as an active facilitator of learning. The process of collaboration enabled me to enrich their sense of participation and began to show improvement in their self-identification as a competent GAI educator. This has personally boosted my professional confidence. The way I have experienced it, teacher identity is dynamic and is influenced by both personal experiences and contextual

factors such as the grade level of students, technological demands, and demographic (Kim & Kwon, 2025). Commenting further into Blumer's second premise that meaning is socially created, my use of gamification resulted from my interaction with the students and through this interaction assigned new concepts and meanings (symbols) for teacher authority. In my desire to deeply understand my students and to establish new norms and symbols, I started integrating gamified elements in the classroom to (re)produce a social space where new meaning and values are co-created. The (re)production of authority is by the communicative act.

The transformation of my teacher authority and its (re)production happened due to the presence of generative AI and gamification and the communicative process. The traditional meaning of "teacher authority" as the sole "center" of content mastery and the teacher's role as the source of discerning authority is shifted. The first sub-theme reveals that my teacher authority has been socially (re)produced by GAI and gamification - my *becoming an authority* is no longer drawn from my implicit expert knowledge but from my "expert curation" of GAI technology to reinforce strengths and mitigate weaknesses through personalization of lessons and "becoming" through interaction. Furthermore, this interaction with GAI and gamification has shifted my role from a one-size-fits-all lesson planner into a "precise and personalized educator". Thus, teacher authority is now tied to an expertise in diagnosing learning gaps which has been determined by GAI-infused platforms with specific targeted interventions.

Blumer's third and final premise advances the idea that an individual's interpretation of symbols are modified through one's personal process (or minding). My authority, agency, and reactions are not isolated from the "I" and "Me". The spontaneous

“I” reflects constantly on the “Me” - the self-image I formed based on how others (students, administrators, peers) see and react to me. The feedback provided by my administrators, for example, RL1 and RL2 reinforced my self-conception as a GAI expert within my department. As (Griffin, et al., 2023) have it, an abundance of positive feedback early in life, an individual might create an objective idea of “me” that has high self-esteem as opposed to someone who grew up with ridicule. Seen in this fashion, my *becoming* an authority arose from interaction with peers and administrators (RL1 and RL2) who validated and supported my explorations into GAI integration and gamification in the classroom therefore has made for a type of teacher identity that is inquisitive and open to technological change rather than against it.

In my interactions with Generative AI-infused technologies and gamification - and especially with technology - I have noted how my identity shifted in my interactions, especially with how I have appreciated and interpreted “teacher authority”. My experiences from positive validation from peers and bosses, and from experiments in GAI-infused and gamified techniques served as tools that not only augment instructional delivery and re-assert the my teacher role as the curator, gatekeeper, and chief strategist of knowledge transfer, but also the center from which classroom routines stem from and function as the architect of engagement and teaching-learning experiences. A new different form of teacher authority and identity emerged from the data - becoming an authority by means of a ***cyborg identity***, where human insight, technological expertise, and strategic pedagogy becomes connected to the teacher’s authority. Rather than erasing the traditional power structure of the teacher in the classroom as

the authority and the students role as learners, GAI and gamification afforded a transformation of how a teacher is now conceived.

Generative AI-infused technology reproduces the standard-based, bureaucratic, and culturally diverse multicultural AI classroom. Authority is expressed through the communicative act which is constantly negotiated. Through this, authority becomes further reinforced by technological fluency and adaptive pedagogy. Generative AI-infused technology and gamification allows for the decentralization of certain tasks (i.e. feedback, assessment). Likewise, it also centralizes the authority of the teacher as the initiator, facilitator, and regulator of teaching-learning experiences.

Generative AI allows the teacher to “talk” with themselves through the platform and through this process of conversing with generative AI constructs and curates experiences. Generative AI functions as a tool for minding, which allows the teacher to generate new insights and perspectives through “conversing with” and “interacting with” the machine. Through “talking” with Generative AI, the teacher takes part in the process of minding whereby they re-organize ideas, concretize tensions, synthesize disparate thought patterns, compare and contrast ideas and practices. This enables the teacher to curate educationally relevant experiences and shape and reinforce the teacher’s self-identity and authority - a process which can be called ***GAI-mediated minding***.

The authority of the ESL teacher in the age of generative AI-infused instruction is therefore a “cyborg mixture” of man and machine - a curator, gatekeeper, strategist, and designer of engagement - shaped by a cyborg identity, interactions, and GAI-mediated minding.

Traditional teaching hierarchies are (re)produced and are transformed to include technological tools that emphasize collaboration and contextual negotiation. The social order is not destroyed but rather (re)legitimated by transforming teacher identity and authority as instructor, curator, and cultural curator of learning experiences augmented by generative AI-infused technologies and gamification in the classroom.

CHAPTER VI

RESEARCH SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter provides the research summary, conclusion, and recommendations of the study undertaken. It serves as a summary for what has been discussed in the previous chapters and provides recommendations based on the findings.

Research Summary

This study sought to explore how generative AI-infused educational technologies and gamification (re)produces the identity of the teacher as the authority in the multicultural classroom. Specifically, through autoethnography, it looks into how teacher identity and authority are communicatively constructed. The study situates itself in the sociocultural tradition and theorizes communication as a *symbolic process that produces and reproduces shared cultural patterns* (Craig, 1999). Within this framework, communication explains how social order (the macro) is created, maintained, and transformed through micro level interactional processes (145).

This study conceptualized the identity of the teacher as authority in the multicultural classroom as being communicatively constructed - shaped through the process of assigning, negotiating, mediating, and modifying meaning through the process of communication and interaction. It also roots itself on the idea that the classroom, as a micro level site where communication takes place, (re)creates a normative social order.

This study sought to explore the social order whereby teacher identity as the authority and students as learners in the classroom is communicatively (re)produced.

Specifically, this study seeks to understand and answer the following questions:

1. How has generative AI in a multicultural classroom threatened teacher's authority?
2. How does GAI and gamification integration in communicative practices (re)produce teacher authority in a multicultural classroom?

This study was undertaken for the following reasons: 1. To contribute to the scholarly conversation on AI and Education by offering insights from a real, multicultural ESL classroom, especially with how teacher authority is communicatively (re)constructed through the interaction with Generative AI (GA) and gamified pedagogy; 2. To reframe the practice of teaching as not mere content delivery but as a practice of meaning making, identity negotiation, and cultural negotiation; 3. To offer an intercultural perspective of teacher identity and authority from the vantage point of an exchange teacher in a multicultural ESL classroom and how GAI and gamification impacts classroom dynamics, roles, and patterns; and 4. To provide a critically reflective model of technology-integrated teaching that is culturally responsive and adaptive to new technologies such as GAI while remaining conscious to its limitations, tensions, and influences in shaping the teaching-learning environment.

The only participant in this study is the research and his experiences as a Filipino Cultural Exchange teacher and their experience with AI-infusion and gamification within their multicultural ESL classroom in the United States.

This study made use of naturally-occurring data gathered from 2023-2025. The naturally occurring data made use of in this study are as follows: lesson plans, recommendation letters, slide presentations, emails, evaluation forms, and generative AI-generated reports.

This study was able to draw out four key areas as to how generative AI has threatened teacher authority. They are:

- (1) threatening self-image as a content expert;
- (2) tendency to outsource thinking to GAI;
- (3) challenging traditional teacher roles; and
- (4) weakening teacher authority.

Furthermore, this autoethnography has shown how teacher identity and authority is (re)produced by way of five major themes:

- (1) Creating fun and engaging lessons through data-driven decision making
- (2) Monitoring progress and motivating learners through pleasurable learning:
- (3) Using Gamification to improve student performance.
- (4) Partnering with parents and tailoring lessons to fit learners' needs
- (5) Assessing learner's progress and awarding performance

Authority is a result of the teacher's active engagement of formal institutional structures (i.e. peers, students, parents) but also through communication with GAI and gamified techniques which legitimized and shaped the teacher's role. Generative AI facilitated self-dialogue or "minding" which allowed the teacher to engage in internal meaning-making by (re)organizing ideas, (re)navigating tensions, and synthesizing new pedagogical approaches which bolsters the teacher's professional identity and authority.

This process I have come to call “GAI-mediated minding”. An emergent teacher identity called “cyborg identity” which blends teacher expertise and insight, technological fluency, and strategic / curated pedagogy is a product of a communicative constructed teacher authority. This study demonstrates how a teacher’s identity and authority is communicatively constructed and continually reshaped through interaction in a GAI-infused and gamified multicultural ESL classroom.

Conclusion

This study set out to look into how teacher authority is communicatively reproduced in a Generative AI-infused and gamified multicultural ESL classroom. It sought to answer two main questions: firstly, how has generative AI threatened teacher authority, and lastly how have encounters and interactions with GAI and gamification (re)produced teacher that authority. Anchoring on the sociocultural tradition, the findings highlight the constructive nature of teacher identity and authority as a communicative act.

Meaning is constantly assigned and negotiated by means of “talking”, that is, through the communicative act. Perceiving a threat in the social order, that is the teacher as classroom authority and the students are learning, communication thus became a way to reproduce it. This present study has shown that teacher authority is forged through communication and is shaped by external interactions (e.g. with other people such as peers and students) and by means of “internal talk” or minding (e.g. self-reflection, self-talk).

By engaging and participating, and in attempting to resolve tensions in the social order through the communicative act, I, as the teacher, engaged in the process of *becoming in the process of (re)production*. Through this, I was able to reproduce the social order by creating, assigning, mediating, and negotiating in the way I approached teaching vis-a-vis the arising of GAI technologies and gamification.

This present study has provided new discussion points on how teacher identity and teaching-learning experiences are constructed through the communicative act; how the classroom social order and identity is shaped by their communication; and experiences in a foreign classroom, as well as encounters with new technologies and approaches in shaping their instructional design (i.e. with Generative AI and new approaches like gamification within the context of Exchange teachers)

While literatures exist on exploring the experiences of teachers being threatened with the advent of GAI proliferating in the classroom (like Kim & Kwon, 2025) as well as its effects in instructional outcomes (Shao & Sun, 2025), this present study's contribution is on how teachers themselves as agents-in-interaction with new technologies like that of GAI attempt to reproduce the social order, resolve tensions, and go about the process of "becoming" through communication. What this study advances is not emphasized in prior literature is on the communicative (re)production of teacher authority. This study did not reject the existing literature, rather it reframed teacher authority as something that is not lost with the arrival of GAI but rather something that is dynamic and is constantly negotiated in the classroom.

Likewise, the methodology I made use of - that of autoethnography - has enabled me to demonstrate how I, as the subject, went through the process of "becoming" and

communicative construction- how my teacher authority has been socially (re)produced by GAI and gamification - that my *becoming an authority* is no longer drawn from my implicit expert knowledge but from my “expert curation” of GAI technology. Autoethnography thus offers a model for capturing the lived experiences of the individual agency of a teacher encountering and making sense of GAI technology and gamification in their classroom, this is an area not yet emergent in the literature which this present dissertation is advancing.

This study contributes to the field of communication by theorizing within the sociocultural tradition, and showing how the communicative act functions as a way to (re)produce the social order in the classroom and how notions of authority and identity are communicatively constructed. This dissertation underscores the importance of reflexivity, dialogue, and adaptive pedagogy - one where the teacher dynamically participates in, rather assumes statically, construction of authority and identity amidst rapid technological change and novelty.

Recommendations

The classroom has been forever changed due to the arrival of AI technology. Students are likewise forever changed as they encounter new technologies outside and inside the classroom. It is therefore imperative for more educational research pertaining to AI for Education (AI4Ed) , especially with regards to how teachers respond to AI and create varied teaching-learning approaches accommodating the technology being undertaken.

This study sought to explore how Generative AI-infused (GAI) educational technologies and gamification (re)produces the identity of the teacher as the authority in the multicultural classroom. It was able to discover a current lack of situated, classroom-based research on how Generative AI (GAI) (re)produces teacher identity and authority, particularly within a multicultural ESL classroom context. There is a scarcity of qualitative, autoethnographic studies that critically reflects on the lived experiences of teachers and their encounters with GAI and gamified pedagogy in the classroom. Given this, there is insufficient understanding of how communicative practices reproduce teacher authority and identity in GAI-infused and gamified classrooms explored in this study, I advance the following recommendations:

1. Develop more studies that contribute to the scholarly conversation on AI and Education by offering insights from a various classrooms and subject areas, especially with how teacher authority is communicatively reconstructed through the interaction with Generative AI (GA) and gamified pedagogy;
2. More studies that reframe the practice of teaching as not mere content delivery but as a practice of meaning-making, identity, and cultural negotiation can be further undertaken;
3. Situate more intercultural perspectives of teacher identity and authority from the vantage point of teachers in the class classroom and how GAI and gamification impacts classroom dynamics, roles, and patterns.
4. Draw out more critically reflective models of technology-integrated teaching that is culturally responsive and adaptive to new technologies such as GAI while

remaining conscious to its limitations, tensions, and influences in shaping the teaching-learning environment.

Furthermore, providing avenues for teacher skill-development on AI literacy, knowledge about prompt engineering, and critical thinking can best remedy the following problems of teacher overwhelm, positive and negative outcomes on GAI use, and heavy reliance of GAI technology (Walter, 2024).

Having more autoethnographies and case studies whereby individual teachers-as-practitioners share their experiences with generative AI technology in various classroom contexts - as well as how they (re)produce their roles and authorities in the classroom - in various cultures, and in various technological settings and how it creates unique teaching-learning experiences.

Autoethnographies with how teachers make use of generative AI technology to facilitate the process of minding (“talk”), facilitate the process of inner conversation and how interacting with generative AI technologies with how they structure and curate their classroom can also be undertaken.

Likewise, surveys and reflections on teacher identity and authority such as how individual teachers respond to this rapidly advancing resource should also be undertaken since teachers will have to grapple with AI encroachment into their profession. How teachers navigate, respond, react, and negotiate their practice is of great importance.

Aside from GAI-infusion, studies pertaining to new classroom engagement techniques apart from gamification can be undertaken. Gamification as an engagement technique can also be studied by teachers-as-practitioners from various contexts. For

example, how is implementing gamification in the rural, Filipino classroom different from how I practiced it in the United States - how does it (re)produce teacher authority in this context? Will creation of Professional Learning Communities focus on generative AI-infused tools help teachers boost their self-conceptions and approaches to their authorities in the Philippines to integrate generative AI technology more openly into their practice?

As a researcher, creating this study is an eye-opener. It made me reflect upon and made me realize the many things happening technologically in society that have affected my classroom practice. Technology has changed the way students interact, it has also challenged the way how I, as a teacher, communicate outcomes and standards. AI has been used by both teachers and students to help them with tasks, it comes with its own benefits and challenges for both parties. Studies on AI's effect on Education and practitioner research pertaining to it, as well as gamification and its adjacent engagement techniques, are not only needed but pressing in this rapidly changing world.

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GLOSSARY

AI / Generative AI (GAI) refers to Generative Artificial Intelligence. In this study, it is defined as a machine-learning model that can learn and make predictions based on data sets, and can create new data. It is trained using millions of examples and learns to generate more data based on the data it was trained on (Zewe, 2023).

Authority refers to the dynamic and communicatively constructed influence a teacher has in the classroom. It is the power the teacher has to give orders, make decisions, and dictate the direction of the teaching-learning experience by enforcing instructionally desirable outcomes such as compliance. In this study, authority is expressed through pedagogical choices, interactions, and technological mediation primarily led by the teacher. It is not static or hierarchical but emerges through a process of co-construction, contextual adaptation, and reflection between participants.

Assigned is a term from Blummer's first premise that stipulates that meanings are not inherent but are *assigned* by individuals that stems from their prior experience, cultural backgrounds, and social cues. This refers to how individual members of the classroom refer to items (such as the flag) and phenomenon (such as the grading system or how they should react to the teacher) being shaped by their cultural frames of reference.

Canva AI is Canva's AI-augmented features that creates AI generated templates, pictures, and layouts.

ChatGPT is a generative AI platform that produces human-like text responses based on user inputs or prompts.

Communicative construction is the process by which meanings, identities, relationships, norms - like teacher authority - are continuously assigned, negotiated, and shaped through communication and interaction. Authority and identity dialogically emerges through interaction and is constantly negotiated and reinforced in the classroom through culturally relevant teaching practices, educational technologies and techniques (such as Generative AI and Gamification).

Cultural Exchange Teachers are teachers, such as myself, who have relocated to the United States of America for a period of three to five years to teach in the United States under the J1 Visa Program.

Cultural Tools are symbolic material resources that mediate thinking, communication, and learning in the classroom. These tools include physical tools such as computers, digital technologies such as AI-infused educational and gamified platforms. Classroom routines and language also fall into this category.

Educational Technologies are information and communication technologies (ICT). They collectively refer to applications and platforms which deliver content to the learners, provide engagement tasks, assess learning formatively and summatively, and report feedback of student performance in real time to the teacher.

ESL stands for English as a Second Language. As a subject ESL teaches essential academic language and social skills needed for educational success within the context of the United States. ESL students are learners who come from various countries and cultural groups to live and study in the United States. “English Learners” or students who have come to the United States with limited English.

Gamification in this study refers to a *classroom strategy* I use where game design elements and mechanics in non-gaming contexts, aiming to adopt motivation, engagement, and desired behaviours in the classroom by capitalizing on the appeal of games to enrich, immerse, and facilitate a practical learning experience (Deterding et al, & Nacke, 2011; Kapp, 2012)

Generative AI-Infused (GAI) refers to digital tools infused with generative artificial intelligence to adapt, personalize, or automate aspects of the teaching-learning processes. Platforms such as Nearpod, Quizizz, Successmaker are used in my ESL classroom as mediating instructional tools that provide real-time feedback, adaptive tasks, and gamified experiences. It allows for the creation of a digital space where students can interact.

Google Gemini is a generative AI platform that produces human-like text responses based on user inputs or prompts.

Identity (Concept of Self) is the socially constructed understanding of one's self that is produced and shaped through interaction, symbolic exchange, and internal reflection. Identity is in constant flux.

Khan Academy is an AI-assisted, free platform with generative AI features for teachers called *Khan Migo*. Khan Academy provides content-rich and standard-based scaffolded activities for free.

MagicSchool AI is a teacher-facing generative AI assistant that has generative AI functions to help teachers with administrative tasks. It has also started to integrate student-facing generative AI features as well such as an AI tutor function named Raina.

Mediated refers to the role that cultural tools have, such as language, digital applications, classroom discourse, gamification, in supporting human thinking, learning, and interaction.

Modified refers to how meaning is rehearsed, anticipated, and adjusted through “minding” or inner dialogue. This can be seen in code-switching, reflecting, and shifting identity in real time.

Multicultural Classroom is a classroom set-up where various social, linguistic, and cultural groups and learners are physically and digitally grouped together for instruction.

Negotiated refers to how meaning is not fixed or static but is rather negotiated through social interaction. It is the process of working out an agreement that is reached through “talk” and reflection.

Practice refers to the methods, strategies, behaviors, and routines that a teacher makes use of to support learning in their classroom. It can be seen as encompassing what a teacher does - planning lessons, assessment, classroom management, interacting with students, parents and colleagues, etc.

Quizizz is a gamified, real-time assessment application that uses adaptive learning questions, performance analysis, and automated feedback systems. It has an generative AI feature that allows the creation of assessment tools quickly.

SuccessMaker is an adaptive learning application that has personalized pathways to develop literacy skills and math skills through its own AI-driven diagnostics. It functions as an adaptive and diagnostic AI tutor.

Teaching-learning Experiences is viewed as a dynamic, on-going, and interactive process where knowledge is co-constructed between the teacher and students. These

experiences are shaped by various contexts such as culture, history, and socio-economic status. Experiences are mediated by cultural tools, language, and relationships in the classroom and are foundational in the construction on how meaning is assigned, negotiated, mediated, and modified. Experiences, therefore, are socially mediated, culturally-shaped, and context-dependent interaction that occurs between teachers, students, cultural tools (ex. language and technology), and their environment.

Appendices

APPENDIX A

AI Prompts Used in this Study

The following prompts were fed into ChatGPT (OpenAI, 2024). No personal identifiers apart from the researcher's is fed into the generative AI platform.

1. As a tool to brainstorm ideas (compare and contrast, summarize):
 - *Summarize this paragraph by giving me the main ideas in three bullet points.*
 - *Give me the top (number) ideas the paper says in these paragraphs.*
 - *Compare [this idea] and [this idea].*
2. Creation of the citations in the citation style format of the DCOMM Program Manual:
 - *Make a citation for this paper into this format style: [Format style from the DCOMM Program Manual].*
 - *Ex: Printed book with one author*
Author Last Name, First Initial.Middle Initial. (Year of Publication). Title of work. Publisher Name.
3. Transcribe voice memos, the researcher's audio recorded notes.
 - *Transcribe the transcript from this voice memo. Fix the grammar of this transcription. Keep every word. Do not change anything with the word use.*

Remove redundancies (like repeated words and fillers such as “ummm”) in the transcription. [Paste Transcript]

4. As a tool to cluster themes in the transcript for analysis.
 - *Cluster ideas in this [transcript, journal entry, notes] together according to themes. Do NOT change any of the words, simply cluster similar ideas together for me to arrange and re-arrange further. [Paste transcript, journal entry, notes]]*
 - *Would you be able to restructure the analytical table with the first column where the data excerpt appears followed by the column on code that will be clustered (in the third column) into themes that would constitute the tensions? The first column should also identify where such data is located, what is the source (diary, email, etc.).*
 - *Cluster the same concepts from my Talker’s Diary together and group them into themes.*

Here's the transcript [vignette was pasted in full].

APPENDIX B

Recommendation Letters

April 28, 2025

Dear AI Fellows Selection Committee,

I am deeply honored to recommend Mr. Gino Paradela for the AI Fellows Program. Gino is a valued member of our ESL team, and his passion for helping students, both Native English Speakers and Multilingual Learners, has made a real difference in our classrooms.

Over the past year, I have seen firsthand how Gino has embraced AI tools in practical, thoughtful ways. He uses AI not just to create materials, but to personalize instruction for his students, adjusting lessons based on their language proficiency levels and learning needs. He uses and has even found ways to make parent communication easier and more understandable through translation tools, always keeping families informed and involved.

What stands out most about Gino is his desire to share what he learns with others. His colleagues look up to him as an expert, not only in integrating AI in his instruction but also for his impressive ideas on how to create lessons that are engaging and rigorous for his students. He doesn't just explore new technology for himself. He is eager to build up our team and strengthen our practices across the department. I do not doubt that he will take full advantage of the opportunities the Fellows Program offers and bring those benefits back to our students and staff.

Gino's combination of innovation, commitment, and leadership makes him a strong candidate for this fellowship. I fully support his application and am excited to see how he continues to grow as a leader in AI education.

Thank you for considering his application.

Sincerely,

ESL Lead Teacher
County Schools
k12.nc.us

RE: Professional Reference
DATE: 4/28/2025

To Whom It May Concern:

I am writing this letter as a reference for Gino Paradela who is applying to participate in the AI Fellows program. I am Mr Paradelo's department supervisor with County Schools in , NC, and have worked with Mr Paradela since June 2024.

In his work with the ESL Department, I have found Mr Paradela to be a very diligent, resourceful and organized individual who is committed to lifelong learning. His lessons are technology-based as well as hands-on, and promote collaboration among his students. Mr Paradela always provides the most rigorous and relevant learning opportunities for his students and strives to integrate adaptive tools and culturally responsive pedagogy to meet their diverse needs.

Mr Pardela actively uses AI in his classroom as a teaching tool and parent outreach and communications. For example, he recently engaged students in a theme-based writing project that used image creation and story frames to develop literacy skills with English learner students. He also uses AI to develop instructional materials based on the current English language proficiency and reading/comprehension level of each student based on their assessment scores. Additionally, he uses AI to communicate with parents though translation tools, and multilingual family bulletins

Mr Paradela is a team player who collaborates with his coworkers and is regarded as a valuable resource for innovative curriculum and instruction. He is more than willing to share his work and makes himself available to advise other teachers on how to use technology to improve student outcomes.

The skills and strategies he will learn in the AI Fellows program will enhance his impact on the field, both in ESL education and district-level AI development through future presentations, professional development sessions and curriculum development that will deeply benefit our district and students. We are a one-on-one district that supports effective technology-based instruction and highly promotes active learning among our educators to advance their skills.

Given the aforementioned qualities Mr Paradela demonstrates as an educator and his eagerness to learn and share his knowledge, I highly encourage you to consider Mr Paradela for participation in your program. If you have any further questions, please feel free to contact me.

Sincerely,

ESL Coordinator
County Schools, NC
Tel:
Email: k12.nc.us

APPENDIX C

Parent Email

Gino Paradela <

k12.no.us>

solicitando colaboración

3 messages

Fri, Feb 28, 2025 at 11:35 AM

To: "ginoparadela@k12.nc.us"

Muy buenos días y deseando éxitos en su trabajo.

Clemmer Majano se dirige a usted como madre del alumno _____, del grado 9 del centro educacional _____ High School, Condado de _____, con número de estudiante _____.

El motivo del correo es para solicitarle su colaboración para que mi hijo sea incluido en algún curso, asesoría o acompañamiento de otra persona para que le ayude en el idioma inglés, ya que solo habla el idioma español y se le hace difícil su aprendizaje en el aula.

Quedo a la espera de cualquier respuesta e información.

Gino Paradela

Fri, Feb 28, 2025 at 12:23 PM

To:

Inglés:

Hi Ms. _____,

I am Mr. Paradela, and I am _____ English as a Second Language (ESL) teacher. I am getting _____ ready to get his English Learner (EL) Plan and I will test him to see where his current English Language Proficiency is. Once he is tested, he will have his EL Plan available which I will send out to all his teachers so that they will know where _____ currently is in terms of his English Language Progress. I already received _____ language card from you. The next step we are waiting for is for the ESL Office to send me the "go signal" to test him, hopefully next week.

As far as class progress goes, _____ does some of his work in my class. But sometimes he is always on his phone and does not do what he is supposed to do. I would like to see _____ exert some more effort so that he can learn and improve on his English. Would you like me to tag you in an email with all his teachers at _____ High School and give his teachers your contact information?

I am not a Spanish-speaker so I am using an AI translator to help me communicate with you so I apologize if the grammar is a bit unusual.

Thank you for collaborating with me!

Very truly yours,

Mr. Paradela

Español:

Hola Sra. _____,

Soy el Sr. Paradela, el maestro de Inglés como Segundo Idioma (ESL) de _____. Estoy preparando a _____ para obtener su Plan de Aprendizaje de Inglés (EL Plan), y le haré una evaluación para determinar su nivel actual de dominio del idioma inglés. Una vez que complete la evaluación, se elaborará su EL Plan, el cual enviaré a todos sus maestros para que sepan en qué nivel se encuentra _____ en cuanto a su progreso en el idioma inglés. Ya he recibido de usted la tarjeta de idioma de _____. El siguiente paso es esperar a que la Oficina de ESL me dé la "luz verde" para evaluarlo, lo cual espero que suceda la próxima semana.

En cuanto a su progreso en clase, realiza parte de su trabajo en mi clase. Sin embargo, a veces está siempre en su teléfono y no hace lo que se supone que debe hacer. Me gustaría que Freddy hiciera un mayor esfuerzo para que pueda aprender y mejorar su Inglés.

¿Le gustaría que la incluya en un correo electrónico con todos los maestros de en High School y les proporcione su información de contacto?

No hablo español, así que estoy utilizando un traductor de inteligencia artificial para comunicarme con usted, por lo que le pido disculpas si la gramática es un poco inusual.

¡Gracias por colaborar conmigo!

Atentamente,
Sr. Paradela
[Quoted text hidden]

Fri, Feb 28, 2025 at 12:36 PM

To: Gino Paradela <ginoparadela@ccs.k12.nc.us>

Gracias por responder, acepto me incluya a la lista de correos de maestros .

Agradezco su interés por mi hijo.

[Quoted text hidden]

[Quoted text hidden]

This email is for the sole use of the individual for whom it is intended. If you are neither the intended recipient, nor agent responsible for delivering this email to the intended recipient, any disclosure, re-transmission, copying, or reliance on the information contained herein is prohibited. If you have received this email in error, please notify the person transmitting the correspondence immediately. All email correspondence to and from this email may be subject to disclosure to any third party upon request, including the media. It shall not be necessary to disclose: 1) (small correspondence which does not constitute a Public Record as defined under N.C.G.S. §132.1 or; 2) a public record which is exempt from disclosure under other applicable State or Federal law.

APPENDIX D

Student Evaluations

ESL Summer School Survey

Please provide your honest opinions and recommendations about your experience during the ESL Summer Program.
You can remain anonymous if you prefer.

Which class did you complete (select one)?

English Math

Circle one answer for each question:

My teacher was helpful (explained concepts, offered assistance, etc.)

Excellent Good Fair Poor

How would you rate the quality of teaching?

Excellent Good Fair Poor

The ESL staff made me feel welcome.

Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree

The smaller class size was helpful (more one-on-one help, less distractions, etc.)

Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree

If I needed to, I would participate in ESL Summer School again to recuperate a credit.

Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree

What motivated you to participate in the ESL Summer Program?

I wasn't trying to fail, but after I came here I feel like it helped a lot, I've learned so much.

What was something that should continue in the ESL Summer Program?

Mr. Parabela he's a good teacher.

What is something that should be added to the program?

I'm not sure, just love how the teacher teaches, makes lessons more fun.

What is something that you would change about the program?

Putting AC on the bus, I'm dying.

Enjoy your summer!

ESL Summer School Survey

Please provide your honest opinions and recommendations about your experience during the ESL Summer Program. You can remain anonymous if you prefer.

Which class did you complete (select one)?

English Math

Circle one answer for each question:

My teacher was helpful (explained concepts, offered assistance, etc)

Excellent Good Fair Poor

How would you rate the quality of teaching?

Excellent Good Fair Poor

The ESL staff made me feel welcome.

Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree

The smaller class size was helpful (more one-on-one help, less distractions, etc)

Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree

If I needed to, I would participate in ESL Summer School again to recuperate a credit.

Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree

What motivated you to participate in the ESL Summer Program?

Cause they said I would pass

What was something that should continue in the ESL Summer Program?

the teaching

What is something that should be added to the program?

more time in bedroom

What is something that you would change about the program?

The time we leave

Enjoy your summer!

ESL Summer School Survey

Please provide your honest opinions and recommendations about your experience during the ESL Summer Program.
You can remain anonymous if you prefer.

Which class did you complete (select one)?

English Math

Circle one answer for each question:

My teacher was helpful (explained concepts, offered assistance, etc)

Excellent Good Fair Poor

How would you rate the quality of teaching?

Excellent Good Fair Poor

The ESL staff made me feel welcome.

Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree

The smaller class size was helpful (more one-on-one help, less distractions, etc)

Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree

If I needed to, I would participate in ESL Summer School again to recuperate a credit.

Strongly Agree Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree

What motivated you to participate in the ESL Summer Program?

What motivated me I had to do it to make me pass

What was something that should continue in the ESL Summer Program?

Something that should is the teaching.

What is something that should be added to the program?

Something should be added is more time in the bathroom.

What is something that you would change about the program?

The time we leave for school

Enjoy your summer!

APPENDIX E

Successmaker Student Performance - AI

successmaker report viewer

Cumulative Performance

Reading

Report Run:

School:

Teacher: Gino Paradela

Grade: Multiple Grades Selected

Group: Multiple Groups Selected

Date Range: All Session Dates

Selected Options:

- No sub-grouping (grouped by course only)
- Sort by Student Name
- All groups selected

Legend:

- At or above AP (75+%)
- Near AP (68-74%)
- Far from AP (0-67%)
- In IP: Student still in Initial Placement
- AP Acceptable Performance (75% Skills Mastered)
- Skills Percent Mastered meets AP
- NA Data does not apply. Some courses and settings may not report data for all columns
- No data reported

Skills Mastery

Student	Level Data ¹				Usage ²		Instructional Performance ³			Mastery			
	Assigned Course Level	Current Course Level	IP Level	Gain	Time Spent (min)	Session Count	Exercises Correct	Exercises Attempted	Exercises Percent Correct	Skills Assessed	Skills Mastered	Skills Percent Mastered	AP
	8	7.74	7.50	0.24	08:21	23	131	298	44%	12	6	↓	50%
	8	7.35	7.25	0.10	05:20	14	87	228	38%	7	0	↓	0%
	8	7.61	7.50	0.11	07:49	21	61	118	52%	4	0	↓	0%
	8	8.14	8.00	0.14	06:30	17	97	198	49%	7	3	↓	43%
	8	7.18	7.00	0.18	09:24	27	117	225	52%	9	3	↓	33%
	8	7.44	7.25	0.19	07:32	21	153	266	58%	8	4	↓	50%
	8	8.19	8.00	0.19	06:41	19	163	253	64%	9	6	↓	67%
	8	8.70	8.25	0.45	15:08	43	391	549	71%	23	16	→	70%
	8	8.07	8.00	0.07	06:29	17	48	111	43%	4	1	↓	25%
	8	8.39	8.25	0.14	07:16	20	140	258	54%	6	2	↓	33%
	8	7.94	7.75	0.19	08:35	22	102	269	38%	11	2	↓	18%
	8	8.44	8.25	0.19	07:32	21	150	190	79%	8	8	→	100%
	8	8.04	8.00	0.04	01:25	5	9	25	36%	2	0	↓	0%
	8	8.32	8.25	0.07	04:25	12	47	131	36%	4	0	↓	0%
	8	7.85	7.75	0.10	07:33	22	55	160	34%	6	0	↓	0%
	8	7.63	7.50	0.13	05:57	17	53	152	35%	5	0	↓	0%
	8	7.68	7.50	0.18	06:59	19	98	206	48%	9	6	↓	67%
	8	8.05	8.00	0.05	08:00	22	44	120	37%	4	1	↓	25%
Mean - 18 Students	8.00	7.93	7.78	0.15	07:16	20.11	108.11	208.72	48.22%	7.67	3.22	32.28%	
Standard Deviation	0.00	0.40	0.38	0.09	02:35	7.29	81.14	107.29	12.76%	4.53	3.98	29.56%	

Percentage of Students with AP: 6%

Student Performance

Reading

Report Run:

School:

Teacher: Gino Paradela

Grade: 10

Group: 10222X0 21 English II- (40473)

Initial Placement:

- IP Level: 8.25
- IP Correct: 24
- IP Attempted: 25
- IP Percent Correct: 96%
- IP Time Spent: 00:18
- Placed: 01/17/2025

Legend:

- IP Initial Placement
- NA Not Applicable
- TOP Topped out
- Data not available
- ++ Strand is on but level not yet reached

Performance Summary

Current Course Level Far Below Level

8.70

current course level is Far below grade level for grade 10. At this time of year, students' course levels should be at or above 10.00.

School Year 01/06/2025 - 05/23/2025

Gain +0.45

IP Level 8.25
Assigned Course Level 8.00

Skills Mastery

Skills Mastered/Assessed

16/23

Percentage of skills mastered

70%

● 0-50% ● 51-74% ● 75+%

Instructional Performance by Strand - Cumulative

Strand	Strand Level	Exercises Correct	Exercises Attempted	Exercises Percent Correct
Foundational Skills				
Concepts of Print				Not yet active
Fluency	8.58	1	1	100%
Phonics				Not yet active
Phonological Awareness				Not yet active
Spelling	8.51	24	25	96%
Totals		25	26	96%
Making Meaning				
Comprehension	8.65	195	288	68%
Grammar	8.68	47	68	69%
Vocabulary	8.67	124	167	74%
Totals		366	523	70%

Areas For Growth - Since IP

Skills Not Mastered

Strand	Level	Skill Description	Date at Risk
Comprehension	8.65	Analyze how characters in literature deal with conflict, solve problems, and relate to real-life situations.	04/10/2025
Comprehension	8.65	Use question-and-answer relationships to improve comprehension of texts: Right There questions	04/22/2025
Grammar	8.49	Identify incorrect shifts in verb tenses	03/17/2025

Student Performance

Reading

Report Run: _____

School: _____

Teacher: Gino Paradela

Grade: 10

Group: 10222X0 21 English II- (40473)

Initial Placement:

- IP Level: 7.50
- IP Correct: 24
- IP Attempted: 35
- IP Percent Correct: 69%
- IP Time Spent: 00:34
- Placed: 01/17/2025

Legend:

- IP Initial Placement
- NA Not Applicable
- TOP Topped out
- Data not available
- ↔ Strand is on but level not yet reached

Performance Summary

Current Course Level Far Below Level

7.74

Gain IP Level 7.50

+0.24

Assigned Course Level 8.00

School Year 01/06/2025 - 05/23/2025

7.74: current course level is Far below grade level for grade 10. At this time of year, students' course levels should be at or above 10.00.

Strand	Strand Level	Exercises Correct	Exercises Attempted	Exercises Percent Correct
Foundational Skills				
Concepts of Print				Not yet active
Fluency				Not yet active
Phonics				Not yet active
Phonological Awareness				Not yet active
Spelling	7.65	8	10	80%
Totals		8	10	80%
Making Meaning				
Comprehension	7.72	82	211	39%
Grammar	7.70	11	19	58%
Vocabulary	7.74	30	58	52%
Totals		123	288	43%

Skills Mastery Instructional Performance by Strand - Cumulative

Skills Mastered/Assessed

6/12

50%

Percentage of skills mastered

● 0-50% ● 51-74% ● 75+%

Strand	Strand Level	Skill Description	Date at Risk
Comprehension	7.56	Use compare and contrast relationships to gain meaning	03/06/2025
Comprehension	7.61	Paraphrase information from text	04/01/2025
Comprehension	7.61	Compare themes	03/31/2025
Vocabulary	7.63	Use Greek and Latin roots to determine the meaning of unfamiliar words.	04/22/2025

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SAVVAS

COMMUNICATIVE (RE)PRODUCTION OF TEACHER AUTHORITY IN A GENERATIVE AI-INFUSED AND GAMIFIED MULTICULTURAL CLASSROOM: AN EXCHANGE ESL TEACHER'S AUTOETHNOGRAPHY 162

APPENDIX F

Lesson Plan

<p>Teacher: Gino Paradedla Department/Subject: English 1 Week: 3-7, March 2025</p> <p>CCS Pacing Guide: Unit 3, Week # 5 Unit Documents/Text Plan: Unit 3: Analyzing the Development of Theme/Analyzing Structural Choice</p> <p>Codes: TW - Teacher will SW - Students will HTYS - High Yield Teaching Strategies NH - Numbered Heads DS - Distributive Summarizing HOTS - Higher Order Thinking Strategies</p>					
Week #1	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday
<p>Focus Standard(s)</p>	<p>RL 9-10.2 Determine a theme of a text and analyze in detail its development over the course of the text, including how it emerges and is shaped and refined by specific details; provide an objective summary of the text.</p>	<p>Standards Focus: RL9-10.2, RL 9-10.5</p> <p>RL 9-10.2 Determine a theme of a text and analyze in detail its development over the course of the text, including how it emerges and is shaped and refined by specific details; provide an objective summary of the text.</p> <p>RL 9-10.5 Analyze how an author's choices concerning how to structure a text, order events within it, and manipulate time create effects such as mystery, tension, or surprise.</p> <p>Supporting Standards: L9-10.4, L9-10.5</p>	<p>Standards Focus: RL9-10.2, RL 9-10.5</p> <p>RL 9-10.2 Determine a theme of a text and analyze in detail its development over the course of the text, including how it emerges and is shaped and refined by specific details; provide an objective summary of the text.</p> <p>RL 9-10.5 Analyze how an author's choices concerning how to structure a text, order events within it, and manipulate time create effects such as mystery, tension, or surprise.</p> <p>Supporting Standards: L 9-10.4, L 9-10.5</p>	<p>Standards Focus: RL9-10.2, RL 9-10.5</p> <p>RL 9-10.2 Determine a theme of a text and analyze in detail its development over the course of the text, including how it emerges and is shaped and refined by specific details; provide an objective summary of the text.</p> <p>RL 9-10.5 Analyze how an author's choices concerning how to structure a text, order events within it, and manipulate time create effects such as mystery, tension, or surprise.</p>	<p>Standards Focus: RL9-10.2, RL 9-10.5</p> <p>RL 9-10.2 Determine a theme of a text and analyze in detail its development over the course of the text, including how it emerges and is shaped and refined by specific details; provide an objective summary of the text.</p> <p>RL 9-10.5 Analyze how an author's choices concerning how to structure a text, order events within it, and manipulate time create effects such as mystery, tension, or surprise.</p> <p>Supporting Standards: L9-10.4, L9-10.5</p>

				Supporting Standards: L 9-10.4, L 9-10.5	
Essential Question: Unit or Lesson	Do we determine our own destinies?				
I can...	1. Determine a theme of a text and analyze in detail its development over the course of the text, including how it emerges and is shaped and refined by specific details; provide an objective summary of the text. (RL 2) 2. Analyze how an author's choices concerning how to structure a text, order events within it, and manipulate time create effects such as mystery, tension, or surprise. (RL5)	1. Determine a theme of a text and analyze in detail its development over the course of the text, including how it emerges and is shaped and refined by specific details; provide an objective summary of the text. (RL 2) 2. Analyze how an author's choices concerning how to structure a text, order events within it, and manipulate time create effects such as mystery, tension, or surprise. (RL5)	1. Determine a theme of a text and analyze in detail its development over the course of the text, including how it emerges and is shaped and refined by specific details; provide an objective summary of the text. (RL 2) 2. Analyze how an author's choices concerning how to structure a text, order events within it, and manipulate time create effects such as mystery, tension, or surprise. (RL5)	1. Determine a theme of a text and analyze in detail its development over the course of the text, including how it emerges and is shaped and refined by specific details; provide an objective summary of the text. (RL 2) 2. Analyze how an author's choices concerning how to structure a text, order events within it, and manipulate time create effects such as mystery, tension, or surprise. (RL5)	1. Determine a theme of a text and analyze in detail its development over the course of the text, including how it emerges and is shaped and refined by specific details; provide an objective summary of the text. (RL 2) 2. Analyze how an author's choices concerning how to structure a text, order events within it, and manipulate time create effects such as mystery, tension, or surprise. (RL5)
Content Vocabulary or Academic Vocabulary	Theme – The big idea or message the story wants to tell. Determine – To find out or decide something after thinking carefully. Analyze – To study	Theme – The big idea or message the story wants to tell. Determine – To find out or decide something after thinking carefully. Analyze – To study	Theme – The big idea or message the story wants to tell. Determine – To find out or decide something after thinking carefully. Analyze – To study	Theme – The big idea or message the story wants to tell. Determine – To find out or decide something after thinking carefully. Analyze – To study	Theme – The big idea or message the story wants to tell. Determine – To find out or decide something after thinking carefully. Analyze – To study

something carefully and explain how it works or is put together.	something carefully and explain how it works or is put together.	something carefully and explain how it works or is put together.	Analyze – To study something carefully and explain how it works or is put together.	something carefully and explain how it works or is put together.	
Development – How something grows or changes over time.	Development – How something grows or changes over time.	Development – How something grows or changes over time.	Development – How something grows or changes over time.	Development – How something grows or changes over time.	
Emerge – To come out or become clear.	Emerge – To come out or become clear.	Emerge – To come out or become clear.	Emerge – To come out or become clear.	Emerge – To come out or become clear.	
Refine – To make something better or clearer.	Refine – To make something better or clearer.	Refine – To make something better or clearer.	Refine – To make something better or clearer.	Refine – To make something better or clearer.	
Detail – A small part or piece of information that helps explain the big idea.	Detail – A small part or piece of information that helps explain the big idea.	Detail – A small part or piece of information that helps explain the big idea.	Detail – A small part or piece of information that helps explain the big idea.	Detail – A small part or piece of information that helps explain the big idea.	
Text – Any written work (like a story, article, or poem).	Text – Any written work (like a story, article, or poem).	Text – Any written work (like a story, article, or poem).	Text – Any written work (like a story, article, or poem).	Text – Any written work (like a story, article, or poem).	
Objective – Based on facts, not personal feelings or opinions.	Objective – Based on facts, not personal feelings or opinions.	Objective – Based on facts, not personal feelings or opinions.	Objective – Based on facts, not personal feelings or opinions.	Objective – Based on facts, not personal feelings or opinions.	
Summary – A short version of the text that tells only the most important ideas.	Summary – A short version of the text that tells only the most important ideas.	Summary – A short version of the text that tells only the most important ideas.	Summary – A short version of the text that tells only the most important ideas.	Summary – A short version of the text that tells only the most important ideas.	
Analyze – To study something carefully and explain how it works.	Analyze – To study something carefully and explain how it works.	Analyze – To study something carefully and explain how it works.	Analyze – To study something carefully and explain how it works.	Analyze – To study something carefully and explain how it works.	
Author – The person who wrote the story or text.	Author – The person who wrote the story or text.	Author – The person who wrote the story or text.	Author – The person who wrote the story or text.	Author – The person who wrote the story or text.	
Structure – How the	Structure – How the	Order – The way things happen or are arranged in a	Structure – How the parts of a text are organized or put together.	Structure – How the	

parts of a text are organized or put together.	parts of a text are organized or put together.	story.	Author – The person who wrote the story or text.	parts of a text are organized or put together.	
Order – The way things happen or are arranged in a story.	Order – The way things happen or are arranged in a story.	Manipulate – To change or control something in a smart or skillful way.	Structure – How the parts of a text are organized or put together.	Order – The way things happen or are arranged in a story.	
Event – Something that happens in the story.	Event – Something that happens in the story.	Time – When things happen in a story (past, present, future).	Order – The way things happen or are arranged in a story.	Event – Something that happens in the story.	
Manipulate – To change or control something in a smart or skillful way.	Manipulate – To change or control something in a smart or skillful way.	Effect – What happens because of something; the result.	Event – Something that happens in the story.	Manipulate – To change or control something in a smart or skillful way.	
Time – When things happen in a story (past, present, future).	Time – When things happen in a story (past, present, future).	Mystery – Something in the story that is not explained right away and makes the reader curious.	Event – Something that happens in the story.	Time – When things happen in a story (past, present, future).	
Effect – What happens because of something; the result.	Effect – What happens because of something; the result.	Tension – A feeling of worry or excitement about what will happen next in the story.	Manipulate – To change or control something in a smart or skillful way.	Effect – What happens because of something; the result.	
Mystery – Something in the story that is not explained right away and makes the reader curious.	Mystery – Something in the story that is not explained right away and makes the reader curious.		Time – When things happen in a story (past, present, future).	Mystery – Something in the story that is not explained right away and makes the reader curious.	
Tension – A feeling of worry or excitement about what will happen next in the story.	Tension – A feeling of worry or excitement about what will happen next in the story.		Effect – What happens because of something; the result.	Tension – A feeling of worry or excitement about what will happen next in the story.	
			Mystery – Something in the story that is not explained right away and makes the reader curious.		
			Tension – A feeling of worry or excitement about what will happen next in the story.		

				of worry or excitement about what will happen next in the story.	
Do Now - Bell Ringer & Entrance Ticket (<:10) Teacher submits attendance in PS.	Quizizz: RL 2 Academic Vocabulary Adaptive learning: Mastery/Peak	Quizizz: RL 5 Academic Vocabulary Adaptive learning: Mastery/Peak	Quizizz: RL 2 Theme and Central Idea Adaptive learning: Mastery/Peak	Quizizz: RL 5 Mystery, Tension, Surprise Adaptive learning: Mastery/Peak	Gimkit: Common Core Vocabulary
Distributive Summary Example:					
Inspire - Activity 1 (Direct Instruction) "I do" (:20) Teacher models lesson & expectation.	Frayser Model Word Cards 	Students do 20 minutes of Khan Academy: - Finding Theme and Central Ideal - Inferences - Citing Textual Evidences	Close Reading: Class will read Act I from <i>The Tragedy of Romeo and Juliet</i> as a class with students assigned parts. (Whole Group) After reading, students, complete activities in the workbook.		
	RL 2 Vocabulary Students do 20 minutes of Successmaker.		RL 5 Vocabulary Students do 20 minutes of Successmaker.		
Challenge - Activity 2 (Student Demonstrations & Connections) "We do" (:20) Teacher monitors student engagement/facilitates collaborations.	Students are asked to work by pairs and and create a <u>one sentence</u> theme statement for Salvador Dalí's <i>The Persistence of Memory</i> .	Students are asked to Think-Pair-Share Considering "Dream's Winter" and referring to their T chart: THINK: What final	Students do MagicSchool.AI / AI tutor for 20 minutes: Prompt: Teach me how to find the components of an Objective Summary	Students answer <i>Shakespeare Webquest</i> worksheets for the entire period.	Close Reading: Class will read Act I from <i>The Tragedy of Romeo and Juliet</i> as a class with students assigned parts. (Whole Group)

	<p>Magicschool AI - AI Tutor</p> <p>Generative AI tutor Prompt:</p> <p>Teach me how to find the elements of a theme statement:</p> <p>Author's + text + analytical verb + lesson.</p> <p>Analytical verbs to consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expresses - Illustrates - Conveys - Illuminates - Stresses - Teaches 	<p>element/instance/interaction refined the theme?</p> <p>PAIR: Turn to an elbow partner and initiate a thumb war.</p> <p>SHARE: The winner of the thumb war gets to <i>listen first</i> and <i>share second</i>.</p> <p><u>1st speaker:</u> What details did you notice along the way in the text that helped share the theme? What were some of the "mini lessons" you noted on your chart?</p> <p><u>2nd speaker:</u> How did the denouement refine the theme and clarify the main message? What is that main message</p>		<p>After reading, students, complete activities in the workbook.</p> <p>Break into groups of 4 and complete the following:(Small Group)</p> <p>Annotate the dialogue between Benvolio and Romeo.</p> <p>Identify the moments of dialogue that characterize Romeo, contribute to the conflict, are motifs, and contribute to the inevitable death of Romeo.</p> <p>Get construction paper or white poster/computer paper and title it "Queen Mab Analysis".</p> <p>They should then complete the following activities:</p> <p>Reread the Queen Mab speech by Mercutio from Act I, Scene 4.</p> <p>As you read, draw what Queen Mab looks like according to Mercutio. Label each component with a short explanation as to what it means from Mercutio's point-of-view.</p>

					<p>Finish off the poster by coloring it and writing a sentence explaining the importance of the Queen Mab speech.</p>
<p>Empower - Activity 3 (Student Release) "You do" (:20) Teacher monitors student engagement, answers questions, and ensures differentiation.</p>	<p>Students will practice and annotate with the text "Dreamer's Winter"</p>	<p>Students do EdPuzzle videos: - Tone - Mood - Figurative Language, Tone, & Mood</p>	<p>Numbered heads: <u>Student #1:</u> Identify the topic sentence and the concluding sentence in the example. Read them aloud to your partner. <u>Student #2:</u> Identify and explain the similarities and differences between the two sentences.</p>	<p>Pre-reading activities for "The Tragedy of Romeo and Juliet" Act I. For this lesson, you will read The Prologue and Act I of <i>The Tragedy of Romeo and Juliet</i> in order to examine: 1. How an author crafts a text in order to convey their theme. 2. How an author creates unique characters and conflicts in order to convey a message and develop the plot.</p>	<p>In your notebooks or on a Google Slide, write summaries for Scenes 1-5, where you list important lines of dialogue and mark them with their importance, i.e. motifs, figurative language, imagery, and other concepts related to the standards. You will then complete the performance task on your own using the notes/ideas brought about and created with your partners. (Independent Learning)</p>
<p>Distributive Summary Example:</p>				<p>Mini-lessons are found in Canvas. Videos will be shown followed by a short class discussion for each:</p>	

				<p>Mini Lesson #1 - Shakespeare historical context and language</p> <p>Mini Lesson #2 - Terminology related to Dramas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soliloquy • Monologues • Acts/Scenes <p>Mini Lesson #3 - Motifs and Character Foil</p>	
<p>Closure/Exit Ticker/Wrap Up/Reminders (:10) Teacher releases students with a reflection.</p>	<p>Writing a theme Statement</p> <p>Project in class:</p> <p>ChatGPT: Using generative AI to "award" best work according to rubric.</p> <p>Show strengths and weaknesses for each submission.</p> <p>Prompt: Randomly assign a number for these submissions (Student A, Student B, etc.). Award the best work based on these details - a theme statement:</p>	<p>Going back to theme statement submissions and talking about them.</p> <p>Project in class:</p> <p>ChatGPT: Using generative AI to "award" best work according to rubric.</p> <p>Show strengths and weaknesses for each submission.</p> <p>Prompt: Randomly assign a number for these submissions (Student A, Student B, etc.). Award the best work based on these details - a theme</p>	<p>Using your notes from the last lessons, write an objective summary of the text.</p> <p>Step 1: Topic Sentence (Name it + Verb it + Motif it)</p> <p>Step 2: 3-5 key details (Think "beginning, middle, end," also, "emergence, general idea into that poignant</p> <p>Step 3: Conclusion Sentence (Refine the general idea into that poignant</p>	<p>Writing an objective summary.</p> <p>Project in class:</p> <p>ChatGPT: Using generative AI to "award" best work according to rubric.</p> <p>Show strengths and weaknesses for each submission.</p> <p>Prompt: Randomly assign a number for these submissions (Student A, Student B, etc.). Award the best work based on these details - a theme statement:</p>	<p>Completion of summaries act as Exit Ticker for today's class encounter.</p>

	<p>Author's + text + analytical verb + lesson.</p> <p>Provide the strength and weaknesses for each.</p>	<p>statement: Author's + text + analytical verb + lesson.</p> <p>Provide the strength and weaknesses for each.</p>	<p>Review:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Check your capitalization, punctuation, and spelling. Did you format the title? - Look for language that illustrates your bias (Watch out for adjectives that didn't come from the text/are not simple observations of fact!) - Do you have a paragraph? - Look at your topic and concluding sentences, do they complement each other to give the whole theme statement that encompasses the shaping and refining.) 	<p>Step 1: Topic Sentence (Name it + Verb it + Motif it)</p> <p>Step 2: 3-5 key details (Think "beginning, middle, end," also, "emergence, general idea into that poignant</p> <p>Step 3: Conclusion Sentence (Refine the general idea into that poignant</p> <p>Provide the strength and weaknesses for each.</p>	
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Quizizz Adaptive Data

ⓘ This report displays results derived from the students' all attempts.

Questions

No.	Question	Time	Accuracy	Responses			Standards Tagged
				Correct	Incorrect	Unattempted	
1	Which central idea develops over the course of the text?	169 secs	10%	1	9	0	CCSS.RI.9-10.2
2	What is the meaning of the word frenetic in paragraph 1?	200 secs	20%	2	8	0	CCSS.L.9-10.4
3	How was the art of lacemaking in the New World viewed differently than it was viewed in Europe in the seventeenth century?	342 secs	20%	2	8	0	CCSS.RI.9-10.6
4	How does the author order events to develop her points?	517 secs	20%	2	8	0	CCSS.RI.9-10.3
5	How is paragraph 1 significant to the author's claims?	270 secs	30%	3	7	0	CCSS.RI.9-10.4, CCSS.RI.9-10.5
6	How does the art of making lace represent Brazilian cultural heritage?	450 secs	30%	3	7	0	CCSS.RI.9-10.3
7	How does the author advance her purpose in the sentences below from paragraph 5? "If you want to see lacemakers in action, take a day trip to the seaside towns of Iguape or Prainha, both of which boast lacemaking centers where you can watch women and girls making lace. Ask the lacemakers to indicate which patterns are most traditional, as each town is known for its own patterns."	418 secs	40%	4	6	0	CCSS.RI.9-10.6
8	Which statement from the text supports the author's claim that making lace is laborious?	490 secs	40%	4	6	0	CCSS.RI.9-10.8
9	What is the meaning of laborious based on the sentences below from paragraphs 1 and 2? "Incongruously, her frenetic movements produce a minuscule lace fragment. In fact, a full day's work yields just a few inches of delicate finery. "The extraordinarily laborious craft of bobbin lace (renda di bilros in Portuguese) came to Brazil along with Portuguese colonists who claimed its beautiful northeastern coastline as their own in the seventeenth century."	320 secs	70%	7	3	0	CCSS.RI.9-10.4

Magic School AI Tutor

Output History for [REDACTED]

BETA AI summaries are currently in beta. Your feedback will be valuable in making these summaries more accurate, timely, and relevant. We can't wait to hear from you!

Student Summary

Tools Used:
AI Tutor

Behavioral Notes:
No misbehaviors or concerns observed.

Strengths & Interests:
Strong critical thinking and comprehension skills; expresses complex ideas well. Strategies: Encourage analysis of thematic developments.

Areas for Improvement:
Focus on expanding thematic analysis to new genres. Suggest exploring diverse texts for broader perspective.

AI student summary generated: Thu, Jul 31, 2025, 7:10 PM ET

[Refresh Summary](#)

AI Tutor: Development of central idea

Highly Engaged

Brandonlopez68 engaged deeply in analyzing how the central idea develops and changes in various texts, showcasing strong comprehension and critical thinking skills

AI thread summary (last student message: Mon, Jun 16, 2025, 10:07 AM ET)

Grade level: 9th grade

What topic do you want the AI tutor to help with? "Teach me how the central idea develops and changes over the course of a text."

June 16 at 9:35 AM

Hi! I'm Raina, your AI tutor, and I'm excited to help you understand how central ideas develop in texts! Let's start by exploring what you already know. Could you tell me what you understand about "central idea" in a text?

Note: I'll wait for your response before we continue, so I can better tailor our discussion to your current understanding.

Copy Read Aloud Report

June 16 at 9:38 AM

What I know about the central idea is when you find the message of the story and find different evidence to support what you think is the main point the author is trying to tell you

Copy

June 16 at 9:38 AM

What I know about the central idea is when you find the message of the story and find different evidence to support what you think is the main point the author is trying to tell you

 Copy

June 16 at 9:38 AM

That's a great start! You're absolutely right that the central idea relates to the main message and requires evidence to support it. I like how you mentioned looking for what the author is trying to tell us.

Let's build on that knowledge! Think of a central idea like a plant that grows and changes throughout a text. Just as a seed develops into a full plant, a central idea often starts small and becomes more complex as we read more.

Here's a simple example: In the beginning of a story about friendship, the central idea might start as "making friends is difficult." But as the story continues, it might develop into "true friendship requires both trust and compromise."

Can you think of a story or text you've read recently where you noticed the main message becoming clearer or changing as you read further?

 Read Aloud

[Report](#)

June 16 at 9:40 AM

can you give me a text to read and understand the central idea

 Copy

June 16 at 9:40 AM

Here's a short passage to analyze together:

The Last Leaf
(Adapted excerpt)

When Sue and Johnsy became roommates in their Greenwich Village apartment, they were young artists full of dreams and ambition. They painted side by side, sharing their hopes of making it big in the art world. But when winter came, a severe pneumonia epidemic swept through their artist colony. Johnsy, unfortunately, fell ill and became bedridden. She grew weaker each day, convinced she would die when the last ivy leaf fell from the vine outside her window. Sue, desperate to help her friend, enlisted their neighbor, old Mr. Behrman - a failed artist who had never created his masterpiece. That night, during the coldest storm of the year, Mr. Behrman climbed out in the bitter weather to paint one perfect, lasting leaf on the wall. Though he caught pneumonia and passed away, his painted leaf never fell, giving Johnsy the hope she needed to recover. What Mr. Behrman considered a failure of an artistic career ended with creating his masterpiece - not on canvas, but through an act of sacrifice that saved a life.

Let's start tracking how the central idea develops. What do you think the central idea seems to be at the beginning of the passage?

 Read Aloud

[Report](#)

June 16 at 9:42 AM

At the beginning of the passage, the central idea seems to be centered around the struggles and dreams of young artists in a challenging environment.

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June 16 at 9:42 AM

Excellent observation! You're right about how it starts with the artists' dreams and struggles. Now, let's track how this central idea develops and changes.

In the middle of the passage, when Johnsy becomes ill and fixates on the falling leaves, how does the central idea start to shift? What new elements are introduced to the story's message?

(Remember, we're watching how the author builds and transforms the initial idea about struggling artists into something deeper!)

 Read Aloud

[Report](#)

June 16 at 9:46 AM

When Johnsy becomes ill and fixates on the falling leaves, the story's central idea shifts from the initial focus on artistic ambition and shared dreams to themes of hope, despair, life, and death. The following new elements are introduced into the story's message

 Copy

June 16 at 9:46 AM

Excellent analysis! You've noticed a crucial transformation in the central idea. The story does shift from artistic ambition to deeper themes of life, death, and hope.

Let's track this development even further. In the final part of the story, with Mr. Behrman's sacrifice, the central idea transforms one more time. How does his action with the painted leaf change or add to the message of the story? What does the author ultimately want us to understand?

(Think about how different this final message is from where the story began with just young artists and their dreams!)

 Read Aloud

[Report](#)

June 16 at 9:48 AM

Mr. Behrman's sacrifice in "The Last Leaf" significantly changes and deepens the central idea of the story. Initially, the story focuses on the themes of hope and the power of belief in overcoming illness. Johnsy's determination to die when the last leaf falls highlights how despair can become a self-fulfilling prophecy

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June 16 at 9:48 AM

Fantastic analysis! You've really grasped how the central idea evolves through the story. Let's map out this development to see the complete transformation:

Beginning → Middle → End

- Artists' dreams → Life & death struggle → Ultimate sacrifice & true artistry

You've identified how the central idea develops from:

1. Simple artistic ambitions
2. To the power of hope vs. despair
3. Finally to the deeper message about how true masterpieces can come from acts of sacrifice and love

To check your understanding: Can you explain in your own words how this central idea is different at the end of the story compared to what readers might have expected from the beginning? What clues did the author give us along the way to help develop this change?

 Read Aloud

[Report](#)

June 16 at 9:50 AM

In O. Henry's "The Last Leaf," the central idea shifts from the artistic ambitions and struggles of young artists to the power of hope and the profound impact of selfless sacrifice, particularly through the character of Mr. Behrman.

 Copy

June 16 at 9:51 AM

Outstanding analysis! You've beautifully captured how O. Henry transforms the central idea through the story. You've shown a clear understanding of how the message evolves from surface-level artistic ambitions to much deeper themes about sacrifice and hope.

Let's apply this skill to help you identify central idea development in any text. Here's a strategy you can use:

1. Track the focus at different points:
 - Beginning (What does it seem to be about?)
 - Middle (What new elements or complications appear?)
 - End (What deeper message emerges?)
2. Look for shifts through:
 - Character changes
 - New conflicts
 - Turning points
 - Resolution

Would you like to practice this strategy with another short passage, or would you prefer to explain how you might use these steps with a text you're currently reading in class?

 Read Aloud

[Report](#)

June 16 at 9:52 AM

I would like to explain how you can use these steps in a text

 Copy

June 16 at 9:52 AM

Excellent choice! This will help reinforce your understanding.

Think of a text you're familiar with (it could be from your class or a book you've read), and walk me through how you would:

1. First identify the central idea at the beginning
2. Track how it changes through the middle
3. Show how it develops by the end

You can use those three steps I listed above to explain your example. Which text would you like to analyze?

(Remember, just like we did with "The Last Leaf," focus on how the message grows and changes throughout the story!)

 Read Aloud

[Report](#)

June 16 at 9:55 AM

1 This is usually the author's initial statement of the main point or topic.

Track how it changes through the middle: Look for supporting details, examples, or explanations that elaborate on or modify the central idea.

Show how it develops by the end: Consider how the conclusion or final statements summarize or reiterate the central idea, possibly with added insight or a call to action

 Copy

June 16 at 9:55 AM

Excellent explanation! You've outlined a very clear and systematic approach to tracking central idea development. Let me help you make this even more concrete:

Think of this process like a detective gathering evidence:

Beginning: The "First Clue"

- What topic is introduced?
- What initial message does the author present?

Middle: "Following the Trail"

- How do new details expand the idea?
- What examples deepen our understanding?

End: "Solving the Case"

- How has our understanding grown?
- What final insights transform the initial idea?

Let's test your understanding: Can you apply these steps to a specific example? It could be from a news article, story, or essay you've read recently. What would you look for first to identify how the central idea starts developing?

 Read Aloud

[Report](#)

June 16 at 9:58 AM

Analyzing the development of a central idea in a text involves understanding its beginning, middle, and end, and the different ways the author builds upon it throughout

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June 16 at 9:58 AM

Analyzing the development of a central idea in a text involves understanding its beginning, middle, and end, and the different ways the author builds upon it throughout

 Copy

June 16 at 9:58 AM

That's a good theoretical understanding! Let's make it more practical with a simple example:

Think about a news article with this headline: "Local Teen Starts Neighborhood Recycling Program"

Beginning: Might start as a simple story about a student wanting to help the environment

↓

Middle: Could develop to show:

- Challenges faced
- Community involvement
- Unexpected benefits

↓

End: Might evolve into a larger message about:

- Youth leadership
- Community unity
- How small actions create big changes

Would you like to try tracking a central idea's development with either:

1. A text you're currently reading in class
2. Another short passage I can provide

This way, we can see how these concepts work in actual practice!

 Read Aloud

Report

June 16 at 9:59 AM

I don't know any news article headline

 Copy

June 16 at 10:00 AM

No problem! Let me share a short news article with you, and we can practice tracking how the central idea develops:

Title: "School Garden Transforms More Than Just Campus"

When Madison Middle School started their small vegetable garden last spring, their only goal was to beautify an unused corner of the schoolyard. Students planted a few tomatoes and herbs, expecting nothing more than a green space to enjoy during breaks.

By summer, the garden had become an outdoor classroom where science teachers held lessons about plant growth and ecosystems. The cafeteria began using fresh herbs in school lunches, and students started taking home vegetables to their families.

Today, one year later, the garden project has grown into something no one expected. Local senior citizens now volunteer as garden mentors, sharing their knowledge with students. The excess produce is donated to the local food bank, feeding dozens of community members each month. What began as a simple beautification project has bloomed into a powerful lesson about community connection, environmental responsibility, and the unexpected ways small actions can create lasting change.

Let's analyze this together. What do you notice about the central idea at the beginning of the article? What seems to be the main focus in those first few sentences?

 Read Aloud

Report

June 16 at 10:01 AM

the initial focus likely emphasizes that school gardens are not merely plots of land for growing plants but are dynamic spaces that nurture learning, well-being, and a strong sense of community.

 Copy

June 16 at 10:01 AM

Excellent observation! You've identified how the central idea starts to transform right away. Let's track its complete development:

Beginning:

- Simple beautification project
- Just a small garden in an unused space

How does this central idea develop in the middle section? Look at the part about the outdoor classroom and cafeteria use. What new layers are added to the initial idea of "just a garden"?

(I'm asking about the middle section specifically because I want to see if you can identify how the author builds on that initial simple concept of a beautification project.)

 Read Aloud

[Report](#)

June 16 at 10:02 AM

the middle section develops the central idea that school gardens transform more than just the campus by adding these crucial layers:

 Copy

June 16 at 10:02 AM

Fantastic analysis! You're right - the middle section really expands the central idea by showing how the garden's impact grows beyond just campus beautification.

Let's look at the final transformation of the central idea in the last paragraph. The article ends with mentions of:

- Senior citizen involvement
- Food bank donations
- Community connections
- Environmental responsibility

How does this conclusion change or expand the central idea from where it started? What's the bigger message the author wants readers to understand now?

(Think about how different this final message is from the initial "beautify an unused corner" concept!)

 Read Aloud

[Report](#)

June 16 at 10:04 AM

the central idea from focusing solely on the school's educational benefits to a broader message about the positive impact of school gardens on the entire community

 Copy

June 16 at 10:04 AM

Excellent analysis! You've perfectly captured how the central idea transforms from a simple school improvement project into a powerful message about community impact and connection. Let's map out this development to solidify your understanding:

Beginning → Middle → End
Simple beautification → Educational tool → Community transformation

You've shown you understand how to track central idea development by identifying:

1. The initial narrow focus (school beautification)
2. The expanding scope (educational benefits)
3. The final broader message (community impact)

To practice this skill further: How could you use this same pattern of analysis to track central idea development in other texts? What kinds of changes or shifts would you look for?

(Think about the signals or transitions authors might use to show their ideas are developing!)

 Read Aloud

[Report](#)

June 16 at 10:05 AM

The pattern of analysis used to track the central idea development in "School Garden Transforms More Than Just Campus" can be applied to other texts by focusing on how the main message or argument is introduced, explained, and supported throughout the text.

 Copy

June 16 at 10:06 AM

Excellent! You've grasped the universal approach to tracking central idea development. Let me help you break this down into a practical strategy you can use for ANY text:

 Universal Analysis Pattern:

1. Introduction Phase

- Look for the initial topic/message
- Note the author's starting point
- Identify key words that set up the main focus

1. Development Phase

- Watch for:
 - New supporting details
 - Expanding examples
 - Shifting perspectives
 - Deeper layers of meaning

1. Final Phase

- Observe how the message has grown
- Look for broader implications
- Note how far the idea has come from its starting point

Would you like to practice applying this pattern to a different type of text? I can provide either:

1. A short poem
2. A brief speech excerpt
3. A paragraph from an informational text

Which would you prefer to analyze?

 Read Aloud

[Report](#)

June 16 at 10:07 AM

i would like to finsh

 Copy

June 16 at 10:07 AM

You've done an excellent job today understanding how central ideas develop in texts! Let's recap what you've learned:

- ✓ Central ideas start with a basic focus and transform throughout the text
- ✓ Authors build and expand their message using supporting details and examples
- ✓ The final message is often broader and deeper than the initial concept
- ✓ You can track these changes by analyzing beginning → middle → end

You've shown particularly strong skills in:

- Identifying how ideas transform
- Recognizing how supporting details develop the main message
- Understanding how conclusions broaden the initial concept

Remember, you can use these analysis skills for any text you read in your classes. I'm here if you need help practicing this skill again or have questions about analyzing other texts!

Have a great day! 😊

 Read Aloud

[Report](#)

